

An Investigation of Female Entrepreneurs:

Challenges and Barriers faced by Ethnic Minority Female
Entrepreneurs (South Asian and Black Caribbean) in the Small
Businesses in the United Kingdom

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**Thesis submitted in partial fulfilment of the requirements of
the University of the West of Scotland for the award
of Doctorate of Business Administration**

September 2022

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Acknowledgement

It was not possible for me to conduct this research without the support and reassurance of some people, I would to extend my deepest regards and love to all of them.

First of all, I am cordially grateful to my Lead Supervisor, Prof. Dr. Jonathan A.J. Wilson, I believe that I am very privileged to have him as my lead supervisor because he is amongst the best people in business studies. I am really thankful for his deep interest and efforts, to bring me to this stage of completion of my research. Being at this stage of my life is only because of his trust, appreciation and encouragement that he gave me throughout this journey. His sentence “you will do it” always gave me energy at times when I was low and used to think that I won’t be able to do it, but he made me do it. Thank you so much Sir for everything.

Secondly I would like to thanks the members of staff in Doctoral College at University of West of the Scotland, for helping me whenever needed.

On a personal note, first of all I would like to thank my beloved husband, Abdul Qureshi who stood by me as a strong pillar and always encouraged me throughout this journey. His love, support and trust is the asset of my life.

Secondly I am very grateful to my lovely parents who have supported me in all my decisions and provided me with whatever I have asked for. Their dedication and confidence that one day I will do it, made me successful in my life.

Abstract

In this research, the researcher aims to investigate the challenges and barriers faced by female entrepreneurs of ethnic minority that is South Asian and Black Caribbean in the United Kingdom. Female entrepreneurs are emerging all over the world. The intensity of challenges faced by them are different in different parts of the world. This research will identify the challenges and barriers they encounter during entrepreneurial process.

The qualitative research design will be used and for the data collection snowball sampling will be done, semi structured interviews will be conducted and thematic analysis with triple coding system will be used to analyze the data.

Key Words

Female Entrepreneurs, Challenges, Barriers, Urban Entrepreneurship, Rural entrepreneurship

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Chapter 1: Introduction

1.1 Title

An Investigation of Female Entrepreneurs: Challenges and Barriers faced by Ethnic Minority Female Entrepreneurs (South Asian and Black-Caribbean) in the Small Businesses in the United Kingdom.

1.2 Introduction

In this research, the challenges and barriers faced by female entrepreneurs will be emphasized and an in-depth literature review will be done for the chosen topic. Female entrepreneurs are defined as Ladies who enclosure autonomous work by producing their own associations/organizations (Santos, 2018). Entrepreneurship can support females' financial independence and enhances stability and position in society. The progression in entrepreneurship permits the society to recognize their abilities, which enhances their prestige and allows them to be a part of the advancement of both the society and the economy.

Dorothy Perrin Moore, (1997), defined female entrepreneurs in their book, a female who has commenced a business and vigorously aboard in the administration, and who possess a minimum of 50% of the shares of the business and being in the management for more than a year or longer.

Entrepreneurship can aid women's fiscal individuality and improve their standing in society. The advancement of women's entrepreneurship allows society to identify and understand their capabilities. It improves their status and also advances the incorporation of women in developing the state and also in the advancement of the economy.

Buttner and Moore, in their book described a woman entrepreneur, as a woman who has started a business and is energetically engaged in administrating it, who holds a minimum of 50% of the business and has been in management for one year and longer (Buttner and Moore, 1997). Michael Fay, (1993), explained that the approach of females into entrepreneurship appears to be an intense union of limitations and expectations of outlying pressure and subject objectives. Though businesses run by females cannot surmount without the support of the male family members. Lately, females are coming out and are spotted all over the world; they are currently present at the top positions working in prominent places organizations in a high-level world. A female has to play different characters in her life as a daughter and a sister to take care of her family, as a mother, she looks after her children and

as a partner, her duties are to provide support to her husband by being a perfect life partner. They can perform all of their duties or responsibilities perfectly, but after all, if she wants to start her own business, she has to provide more attention and extra effort towards her family to maintain symmetry in her family and professional life.

1.3 Research Rationale

There are two main reasons why the researcher wants to conduct this research, first is to find out the gap in the research, to the best knowledge of the researcher there is not much research has been done on the female entrepreneur and also the researcher has found that there are only few research papers which were published on the selected topic. The second reason is the personal motivation of the researcher as researcher is female and faces the multiple barriers in pursuing her carrier.

1.4 Personal Motivation of Aiming the Study

I have completed my BDS (Bachelor's Dental Sciences) from Baqai Medical University, in Pakistan. After completing my degree, I have started working as a Lecturer/Demonstrator in my college, later; I have started clinical practice and worked in the dental hospital, where I was promoted as an administrator In-charge of the hospital. Meanwhile getting back to studies was always in my mind because I want to develop myself and also there was a need for advancement in my field, I have decided to step into the Master's program. I got admission to the University of East London, in the program of Masters in Public Health. After completing my Master's degree I went back to my country. I planned to rejoin my university as an Assistant Professor, meanwhile, I was waiting for my documentation to be completed, I was motivated by my family to set up my dental practice, which I did and worked as a full-time dentist and as well as an entrepreneur. Getting exposed to the business and teething problem of setting up a new business was a good experience and I had several problems in running my practice because I had no knowledge of business but I had experience of working as an administrator in the hospital previously was a good help.

After working for about two years, I faced several issues and problems especially dealing with males in society. My suppliers, technicians, and co-workers were all males and my competition was also with the male dentist running their clinics in the same area. I was situated in the city of Karachi, being a metropolitan and biggest city of Pakistan; Karachi has advanced life but conventionally. Although Pakistan is going towards the developmental side with the parallel production part of women but the country is a male-dominated society with a stereotype mindset and a lady working independently is still taboo in many areas.

Looking forward and to enhance my experience, I have decided to get some professional knowledge regarding business administration which is why I have selected the DBA program and the reason for selecting this topic was to investigate the problems faced by female entrepreneurs because I have experienced several issues with myself.

Initially, the plan was to conduct the research in the urban and rural areas of Pakistan and to compare the results. Then the world has been changed due to the pandemic of COVID-19, lock-down situation and restriction to many daily life activities restrain me to collect data, traveling to Pakistan, and then to different cities and villages. Keeping that in mind I have then decided to amend the topic and to research the issues and barriers faced by the ethnic minority female entrepreneurs in United Kingdom.

1.5 Research Justification

Global Entrepreneurship Monitor (2010), suggests that almost 42% of entrepreneurs in the world are females. Entrepreneurship plays a significant role in economic development and growth worldwide, although this is normally considered a male-operated activity, the findings from the global entrepreneurship monitor highlighting the importance of female entrepreneurs is considerable. Among the most critical difficulties in numerous pieces of the present reality are work creation and producing income sources. This is generally a direct result of the complex improvement in all-out people and vast joblessness. Whereas numerous companies are scaling down their staff, the subsequent significant degrees of joblessness are of incredible social, political, and monetary concern. For a few, substitute techniques for work creation and monetary improvement have become essential and the ones involved in entrepreneurship will survive through these circumstances.

Beqo and Gehrels, (2014) considered the insight of the excessive needs of females to maintain their work and family lives and responsibilities will result in extra demanding entrepreneurship rather than the salary generating jobs to females. Even self-employment mostly requires long working hours and flexibility in arranging the daily schedule. Recently, the number of new business establishments by females had overtaken considerably than the proportion of brand new business establishments by males through each cultural setting in America (Marlow, Susan, Sara Carter, 2008). Similar inclination has been discovered throughout the countries which are still in the phase of development. Still, females possess and progress a considerably larger number of enterprises than men.

In the past 30 years, a major alteration has been seen in the rank and governmental influence of female entrepreneurs, and also a swift upsurge of awareness and exploration has been

recorded. Moreover, beginning with the first article in 1970, the study of female private enterprise has extended to a category of fields, modes, and nations. In the initial 1990s, as females acquired extra noticeable positions as both businesspersons and governmental performers, papers of female business functioning self-motivated by female activists' theories. Most women's liberation enthused research stayed experimental, though did not discourse hypothetical matters directly. In a similar period, a substitute to the female activists' attitude, a noteworthy effect on the research of females' occupational options came from the financial side, when Claudia Goldin issued her book "Understanding the Gender Gap". Though in the book there is no discussion about self-employ or entrepreneurship openly, it validates the study of female's work conduct and also with studies by (Francine D. Blau, 2007; Gary S. Becker, Chiappori, 1965) encouraged a noteworthy extent of studies, both hypothetical and experimental, on matter connecting females private enterprise to the provision of domestic funds, marriage, and motherhood choices, self-assurance and scarceness, amongst others.

1.6 Entrepreneurs of Ethnic Minority

The world has become a global village and this globalization has empowered humans to migrate from their native countries to a place where they can have more opportunities to get better jobs or to start their businesses. People travel from developing countries to developed countries to earn money and to acquire a good quality of life. The International migration report 2006, stated that a large number of the total labor force in the OECD countries is comprised of immigrants (OECD.org, 2006; Affairs, 2006). The Annual Global Entrepreneurship Monitor reports 2010 shows that South Asians being innovative and opportunist groups and are leading the entrepreneurial activities in the country (Donna J. Kelley, Niels Bosma, 2011). National Statics (2001), indicates that the self-employment rate for native British people is around 12%. In contrast for migrants, the rate of self-employment for Indians is 15%, Pakistanis and Bangladeshis are 19% and Chinese is 18%. This shows that South Asians are more into self-employment than native people. Pakistanis are mostly running businesses like garments, and are more active in the textile industry (Robin Ward, Richard Randall, 1986; Werbner, 1984) while Indians are into different fields and owing firms (Robinson and Flintoff, 1982) whereas Bangladeshi's are more into restaurant businesses Pakistanis, Bangladeshis, and Indians have a common culture and are classed as South Asian Entrepreneurs (Anuradha Basu, 2002).

In this research, the main target of research in South Asian and African-Caribbean female entrepreneurs. The comparison of the issues and barriers encountered by them will be highlighted.

1.7 Female Entrepreneurs of Ethnic Minority

A large number of females from ethnic minorities contribute to the UK's economy. Females bestow their family by their income, as working professionals, by supporting a family business, or setting up their businesses (Gopalkrishnan R. Iyer, 1999). From 1965 to 1997, the frequency of female immigrants has increased all over the world by 63 percent which is from 35 million to 57 million. The scientists and the researchers were intrigued to investigate ethnic minority business people since they are propelled to work (Anuradha Basu, 1998), due to their background (Daphne Halkias, Chinedum Nwajiuba, Nicholas Harkiolakis, 2011; Radba Chaganti, 2002) their attributes towards entrepreneurial activities and due to their entrepreneurial experiences (Baycan-levent and Planning, 2006; Levie, 2007).

1.8 Research Aim

To investigate the challenges and barriers faced by the female entrepreneurs from ethnic minorities (South Asians and African Caribbean) in the United Kingdom. To compare the challenges and barriers faces during their business period in the United Kingdom according to their ethnic background.

1.9 Research Objectives

- To study the challenges and barriers encounter by female entrepreneurs of ethnic minorities in the United Kingdom.
- To investigate the impression of these challenges on the private and professional life of FE's.
- To suggest practical methods to encourage the potential performance of female entrepreneurs of ethnic minorities in the United Kingdom.

1.10 Research Questions

RQ 1: What are the main challenges and barriers faced by female entrepreneurs of an ethnic minority?

RQ3: What is the difference between the challenges and barriers faced by South Asian and African-Caribbean female entrepreneurs?

RQ 3: How do they deal with these challenges?

1.11 Research Philosophy

The thought that the world has several perspectives, and procedures that function inside the world, is called philosophy. Philosophy is apprehensive with the views regarding how the world mechanism is in place and emphasis mainly, on realism, wisdom, and the ways of life. The personal belief regarding the world is directly related to what we observe as realism and that personal belief of realism is based on the knowledge you gain and also will influence the methods of conducting the research (Mason, 2014).

The word research philosophy describes arrangements of viewpoints and suppositions regarding the improvement of the understandings. It is mainly based on what you are executing when conducting research and acquiring information in a specific discipline. The information acquired may not be as expected as a new concept of human inspiration, nevertheless responding to a particular setback in a specific arrangement will lead to the development of a new theory (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019).

The two principle rules of research philosophy are Epistemology and Ontology. Epistemology is defined as a “theory of knowledge” (James Fieser, 1995), Internet encyclopedia of philosophy, “episteme” is a Greek word that means knowledge, and “logy” means study or theory. The theory of knowledge particularly concerning its methods, authenticity, scope, and the discrepancy between validated belief and opinion. Whereas ontology is defined as “a branch of metaphysics dealing with nature of being” (Oxford Dictionary), ontology is also defined “as a set of perceptions and categories in a focused field or sphere of influence that demonstrates their properties and the relations between them. So, in simple words, epistemology is the way we know things and ontology is about what things are.

There is a need for vigorous research to be done over a chosen topic and the philosophy of that research will be qualitative. The epistemological approach will be used because the topic is about the challenges faced by female entrepreneurs, so we know that there are some challenges but the impact of those challenges is different in various parts of the world. As discussed in the justification, that female entrepreneurs undergo different problems in developing countries than they have to face in the developed world. As epistemology is all about realism and interpretivism, in realism, the positivist approach will be followed which will lead to a quantitative method of research. As the topic is showing the phenomenology that the problems are being faced are dissimilar and also explained differently in various parts of the world, then there is a need for interpretivism which will eventually lead to a qualitative research method. As the interpretivism approach, there is no single reality.

The critical literature review is done on the chosen topic, it does not appear as a single reality, and instead, there are multiple truths about the challenges being encountered by the women entrepreneurs in the developed world.

1.12 Research Overview

1.13 Chapter Summary

In this chapter, a brief introduction is given regarding female entrepreneurs of ethnic minorities in the UK. The research questions, aims and objectives are presented as well. The author has explained the research rationale and personal motivation of conducting this research. Justification of the research is also discussed along with the research philosophy. A brief discussion about FE's of ethnic minorities is also done.

Chapter 2: Review of Literature

Before getting on with the research, it was essential to go through, explore and be familiar with the work done in this area by other researchers. It was expected that this practice would offer a better understanding of the problem and develop a way that will eventually shape the study. The literature was searched to find the answers of the research questions which are to investigate the issues and barriers faced by FE's in their journey of entrepreneurship, how they deal with them in order to run their businesses smoothly and the comparison of those problems in South Asians and Afro Caribbean.

2.1 Background

The idea of “the males are the bread earners” and “the females are the caretakers” was believed globally up till the mid of the last century (Irene Padavic, 2002). The jobs of males and females are appointed by the general public and the way of life they are living at (Watson *et al.*, 2008). The circumstances that impact the entrepreneurial activities of females are cultural background, sociological factors, ethnicity, and their experience; all are taken into consideration while researching female entrepreneurs (Malin Tillmar, 2007). The available data is very limited to obtain a full picture of the role, female entrepreneurs play to run their businesses (Carter, S. Cannon, 1989).

Prior to depicting scholarly networks in female business venture research, the meaning of female business venture should be explained. Various researchers have various meanings of the idea of female business venture. A few researchers demand a thin description of business for females. For instance, Humbert and Brindley (2015), stress the connection between the idea of hazard and female business venture and contend that female business people need to face immense individual and monetary challenges to assemble a business and show some advancement in this cycle (Laure *et al.*, 2015), similarly as in any case, different creators, including (Jennings and Brush, 2013; Kwame Adom, 2016; Hechavarría, Diana, Amanda Bullough, Candida Brush, 2019) contend for an expansive definition for female business venture that embraces both "independent work," where ladies are entrepreneurs however don't make another endeavour and "business venture" in the exemplary sense, where ladies step up, prepare assets and face challenges to make another endeavour. (Deng *et al.*, 2021). Different researcher defined the female Entrepreneurs through their research and experiences expressed as the Table No. 01

Table 1 Definition of Female Entrepreneurs

Definition of female Entrepreneurs	Researchers
Conventional business run by females alludes to ladies as individual proprietors who extend their home-grown assistance and related abilities into the market. In any case, present day female business venture, in which ladies see their responsibility for business as a profession, rather than basically an upgrade to family pay, has moved into usually male-overpowered ventures	Moore (1997)
Describe as far as ladies entrepreneurs and their innovative practices	Welch (2008)
Distinct as woman entrepreneurs and their drives	Hughes (2012)
Characterized as the cycles by which ladies start as well as maintained their own organizations (counting the individuals who are independently employed)	Jennings (2013)
Ladies face gigantic challenges to fabricate a trade and frequently spectacle some development to the system.	Humbert (2015)
A sequence started by ladies, arrange and maintain an undertaking	Adom (2016)
Ladies who enclosure autonomous work by producing their own associations/organizations	Santos (2018)

Characterized as the ladies entrepreneurs them-selves and their endeavours	Hechavarria (2019)
A female business person is along these lines a certain, imaginative and inventive person wanting monetary autonomy exclusively and all despite the fact making business openings for other people	J. Schumpeter (2020)
Female entrepreneurs are innovative impresarios, women who create, imitate or take up an enterprise.	Muhammad Abrar ul Haq (2021)

Although a large number of females are stepping in the businesses as a proprietor, manager or an employer but the gap in research in this area is still present (Goffee and Scase, 1985). The rate of small firm formation rises at the beginning of the 1980s (Ganguly, P., Bannock, 1985) continued with some differences in the economic conditions of recent times. Around 1400 per week was the rate of founding new businesses, since females aim to achieve their dream goals regarding business but often they faced multiple issues in starting and improving their business. The research shows that females because of their gender face hindered limited time freedoms to senior situations in the working environment and look to business as a system to beat the impediments that block the accomplishment that they want. The business entrepreneurship is a troublesome undertaking for all kinds of people. Though, many researches come up with the demonstration that females when contrasted with males experience more noteworthy boundaries to becoming business people. The central points of interest to be learned in this manner are whether there are explicit hindrances that females face, and regardless of whether these boundaries are aggravated for females due to gender discrimination (Spence, 1999; McGowan *et al.*, 2012).

The ontological establishments of business research were started after uncovering positivist connections between factors which would empower and build paces of pioneering conduct. Once more, the supposition that being that business is above all else, a method of significant worth creation whereby, with regards to empowering economic situations, positive financial

results follow for people and society. Proverbially, consequently, effective innovative exercises have a monetary rationale that thus, produces positive social results; these may be as occupation creation, the effect of abundance creation on prosperity or the critical thinking field of social business. This ontological position has been sustained since the 1980s given the expanding strength of neoliberalism as a supporting state philosophy across the globe (Couldry, 2010). The advantages of neoliberalism are commended through the guarantee of remunerations from agentic independence made conceivable by the evacuation of aggregate administrative limitations inciting different types of entrepreneurialism (Du Gay, 2004). This may, for instance, appear as diminishing state government assistance arrangement to provoke more prominent individual duty or empowering more noteworthy entrepreneurialism incorporates (Harvey, 2007). Outstandingly, in any case, this talk has empowered and extended business in the appearance of independent work and new pursuit creation as a course to self-actualization and individual award (Ahl and Marlow, 2012; Marlow, 2020).

Various investigations have analyzed the basic query of whether male and female member of the society contrast in their affinity to take part in business deals. The aggregate proof appropriate to this inquiry is extremely clear (Murray and Graham, 2007). Females are significantly less possible than males to be engaged with different types of pioneering movement and this is unpretentious not to one region but around the world. What's more, just a modest bunch of economies had about equivalent quantities of females and males business visionaries; by far most had a larger number of males than female entrepreneurs (Jeannette A. Colyvas, Kaisa Snellman, 2012; M. Mar Fuentes-Fuentes, Sarah Y. Cooper, 2012).

Different investigations, in view of work market datasets, further uncover that females are more outlandish than male to compete in every field of self-employment and associated with scholarly business; that is, in the commercialization of logical considerations (Jennings and Brush, 2013).

Among one-tenth of the working population, the UK has now seen a larger proportion of self-employment since 1920. There was long heave inescapable tumble off in the measure of little firms and pioneering exercises in the UK and most mechanical social orders, from the mid-1930s to around the mid-1970s. This tumble-off was considered as an indication of monetary turn of events, as modern social orders developed, it was announced that the independent company area gradually thin before the headway of the super-capable huge associations partaking in a heightening expansion in their financial prudence (Bolton, 1971). Different creators legitimize the lower benefit of female organizations in the light of a lower hazard

hunger of ladies contrasted with men (Christine R. Harris, Michael Jenkins, San Diego, Dale Glaser, 2006). Due to this diverse demeanor, female business people are more arranged towards settling on decisions that are situated on an alternate and lower point on the danger return bend (He, Inman and Mittal, 2008). Then again, there is an arising stream of examination, which thinks about that ladies in business, business visionaries and chiefs, focus on various objectives, contrasted with those of men, being more keen on accomplishing a balance between fun and serious activities, laborers' prosperity, and local area government assistance as for simple corporate benefit (Justo, DeTienne and Sieger, 2015). Thus, the achievement of females' organizations can't be estimated and assessed with the regular presentation pointers utilized in past investigations. Our examination draws on this discussion and investigations the monetary presentation of a chose test of imaginative female-drove new companies. Thinking about the pitiless speed of innovative, social, and social changes, we puzzle over whether the presentation hole referenced above is still valid for new companies brought into the world after the world's monetary emergency (Demartini, 2018).

A setback of an inevitable dropping inclination of the small businesses has to turn out to be endured broadly whereas others have aggravated some disagreements in the 1980s. The first disagreement was the fluctuations in the economy itself. The opportunities for entrepreneurship and small businesses increase after the mammoth economic restructuring which commanded the growth in services and knowledge-based activities, due to which a significant decrease seen in the size of the basic business and manufacturing sector (James Curran, 1991). Small businesses are overcoming the challenges by competing with their peers and utilizing a compliant workforce, and private capital was the answer to many of the UK's economic and social problems (Jenkins, 2006).

The growth of the small firms was much faster in the UK than in other parts of the World, such as the United States and Japan, as these two countries have relatively the same size business sector (Kincaid, 1994). The 1991 Census of Population stated that ethnic minorities comprise 3 million people or 5.5 percent of the total Great Britain population (Shaper, 1994). The Labor Force Survey, (1993), stated that the rate of the ethnic population working as self-employed is 25 percent. As considering the portion, Pakistanis, Bangladeshis and Indians live in wards; these were the regions in which the public all in all encounters high joblessness and packing with generally low rates of families' proprietor involvement. There is an exceptionally stamped contrast between South Asian and other ethnic gatherings, for none of

whom does the general public living in this area which some time surpass 20% of the whole population residing there. (Marlow, 1992; Haskey, 1994).

Although comparative patterns can be found among medium-sized and enormous firms, these bigger firms in any case showed higher action levels in natural and outer social issues and were likewise more judicious with respect to functional and burden issues than they had concerns about promoting issues. This experimental proof demonstrating the distinctions in insight among more modest and bigger firms can be clarified by the ethical basic that is capable along the three good force measurements as summed up by McMahon and Harvey. To start with, size affects the apparent Probable Magnitude of Outcomes (McMahon and Harvey, 2006). While the impacts of dishonest conduct in showcasing issues are frequently entirely apparent what's more, open to outside examination, monetary issues are not as generally reviewed in little firms as they are by the formal controls in bigger firms (Murphy, Smith and Daley, 1992; Lepoutre and Heene, 2006).

Population from the Indian subcontinent was at a higher rate to be stated as self-employed. Between 1979-1983 and 1989-1991, small business owners and entrepreneurs emerge were South Asians that are from Pakistan, Bangladesh, and India. The minority businesses have significant growth and were discussed broadly (Robin Ward, 1984). There was an increase in the number of ethnic groups turning towards self-employment due to various reasons, it was discovered that “the opportunity structure outweighs any cultural predisposition towards entrepreneurship” (Aldrich, H., Jones, T.P., & McEvoy, 1984).

A typical finding is that ethnic venture is regularly overrepresented in the independent company area, i.e., members of some ethno-cultural bunches ordinarily have a higher pace of business arrangement and proprietorship than do others. It is likewise grounded that while a high pace of independent work is a steady quality of some ethnic networks all throughout the planet and in differentiating conditions, among different gatherings, business visionaries and proprietor supervisors are substantially less normal (Dana, 1997).

If the chances of mainstream work hire are not available to ethnic minority groups and the racism persists then most probably the minorities will be adapting an alternative route to generate income. To overcome racism, several migrants began with the “rag” trade where fewer funds and expertise were required (Phizacklea, 1990). According to Werbner, Asians in the West Midlands and Manchester and according to Anthias; Cypriots in the East of London, were not concerned about low salaries and poor working conditions, instead, they were all set to replace white people who left their jobs. (Werbner, 1984; Floya Anthias, 1983).

Therefore instead of having a multicultural workforce the ethnic minorities had limited choices and were mostly seen in the businesses like retail and clothing (Ram, 1992) the 1980s, self-employment by men and women risen rapidly in the UK. Equal Opportunities Commission (1989) reported that since 1977, the employment rate for females has increased in all businesses. The rate of self-employed females was risen by 81 percent as compared to males which were 51 percent between 1981 to 1991 (Boyd, 1991).

Schooling is a multidimensional factor, dissected by numerous logical disciplines, yet in addition inside financial aspects, by numerous sorts of hypotheses. The most persuasive speculations seeing schooling as a factor molding business as a word related choice according to the monetary perspective are: human resources hypothesis (training as entrepreneurs , and information, abilities and capabilities as results), or institutional hypothesis (instruction as the consequence of formal and casual establishments). Exploration on the effect of human resources on business venture is fundamental and has been progressively applied for more than twenty years. The distinctions in determinants between nations with high and low female business can be seen when auxiliary schooling is thought of. It is something similar for the entire gathering of European nations; likewise, for both sub-gatherings, the portion of guys with auxiliary schooling isn't carried out as a free factor (Gawel, 2021).

Females are comprised of 43 percent of the entire workforce in the UK, around 10 million females were working in the UK in which 6 million was a full-time worker and 4.5 million was working part-time (Meager, 1992) (Foley, 1992). It was reported in the Labor Force Survey in 1992 that 7 percent of females are working as self-employed, which is almost double the size of the self-employed females in 1979, but less than the 17 percent of self-employed males. In accordance to ethnic groups 26 percent of men were from India and 24 percent were from Pakistan and Bangladesh, from 7 percent of self-employed females, 11 percent of them were from India. Bangladeshi women are at the lowest numbers in self-employment among South Asian females' business owners. In the Midlands, the frequency of self-employment is higher in the minorities groups (Monder Ram, Trevor Jones, 2016). 1 in 5 Chinese females is self-employed as compared to the 1 in 50 African-Caribbean. While in South Asia, especially in Chinese females contributes to a vital basis of paid work (Nathanael Ojong, Amon Simba, 2020).

Mainly the studies conducted on female entrepreneurship were with a small sample size and the presence of the data globally is low. Though the female business persons have hurried up fundamentally into the global entrepreneur competition, the pace of innovative movement for

male members is as yet higher than that of females. Likewise, the organizations run by the females are regularly less fruitful contrasted with male-claimed organizations. By a similar token, minority-claimed organizations have lower bounds of progress than the organizations being run by non-minority community. The progresses of any Business not only rely on the management but also the area matters which are additional part of the system. It has been reported by the As per The State of Women-Owned Businesses in 2017 that the organizations ad companies managed by female entrepreneurs are more successful as the availability of their business is in the more populated areas. (Cho, Moon and Bounkhong, 2019).

According to the survey 13 million females are business owners out of which 5 million directly own the business or are self-employed and the rest of them are involved in their family businesses with their partners or parents. This was proved in this survey that the females conducting business are dealing at a very scale in the industrial sector. Most of the females with children step into self-employment in the search of “coping strategy”, by which they can use their business as an alternative escape from the limitations they suffers from as mothers (Susan, 1987). Although developing magnitudes of females referring to adaptability and childcare commitments as a solid inspirations for beginning a business, somewhat little consideration has been paid to investigating their inspirations, assumptions and genuine encounters of business, and the degree to which business endeavor truly offers a further developed work/family equilibrium (Brush and Cooper, 2012). A study shows that the research on the financing and capitalization of female-claimed dares to an expanding accentuation on milder issues including inspirations, work/family balance and non-monetary meanings of achievement. For instance, the degree to which females business visionaries might be comparable or not quite the same as their male partners, or how much there are varieties among gatherings of women as far as gaining for a fact, improvisation in the enterprising interaction, or approach and execution on promising circumstances would be of interest (Corbett, 2005).

The need of self-sufficiency and to earn their own money to enhance and support their family is also another motivation for a women to start a business (Robert Goffee, 1987). The motivation of setting up the business for females is almost same as men, which is being independent and the challenges of owing a business. Hence challenge and independence are two main motives for females to step in entrepreneurship (Carter, S. ; Cannon, 1989). A study of 64,420 female entrepreneurs in Sweden, stated that the main motivation for a women to start a business is to achieve something which give them independence and a good income

which they can combine to have good family life (Sundin, Elisabeth, Holmquist, 2006). Holmquist and Sundin mentions, “Entrepreneurial theories are created by men, for men and are applied to men”, this suggests that women do not associated with small business, or own them and if they do then they only act likes a men. Studies based on females and their place in the public eye has a significant extensive history; like the exploration on the role of females in working life that include both inside and outside home jobs. The execution of the choices taken was doled out to people previously working in the organizations dealing with industry, trade and local turn of events. With the development of the field, more people were associated with a unique unit taking care of females' business until these errands became mainstreamed and the unit was shut. Females as proprietors and directors appeared to be a point where they could consolidate their capabilities, and furthermore participate in the competition with the male community (Holmquist and Sundin, 2020).

Vokins listed that absence of opportunities, encouragement and appreciation in well-known organizations, knowing that they can do much better than men in the same sector, all of these are combine causes of frustrations leads to setting up their own business which give them satisfaction (N. Vokins, Allen S, 1993). Both males and females have almost same motivations to set up their own businesses. Among various day to day life factors, unemployment is the main motive for them to look for their own enterprise. While females possessed organizations are expanding in number, insights show that there are as yet less female business people when contrasted and their male partners. The world can't just overlook this reality, since, ethic concerns to the side, females' support is essential for monetary progression. Regardless of whether inferable from powerlessness or absence of ability, nations that neglect to offer compelling help for female business will support significant opportunity costs versus full monetary development (Pardo-del-Val, 2010).

The mid 1990s, as ladies obtained more perceptible jobs as the two-business people and political entertainers, saw investigations of female pioneering execution being inspired by women's activist speculations. Most ladies' freedom propelled examines stayed exploratory, in any case, and didn't resolve hypothetical issues straightforwardly. At about the comparable period, a substitute to the women's activist methodology, a vital impact on the investigation of ladies' business decisions came from monetary side when, in Claudia Goldin distributed her book *Understanding the Gender Gap*. However her book didn't discuss independent work or business transparently, it legitimized the investigation of ladies' work conduct and, along with concentrates by Blau and Kahn, and Nobel Laureate Gary Becker supported a critical

measure of exploration, both hypothetical and exact, on issue associating females business venture to the arrangement of family assets, marriage, and childbearing decisions, opportunity insights, confidence and scarceness, among others (Francine D. Blau, 2007). The remarkable growing of the small businesses in 1980s, lead to a substantial amount of academic resources being used up researching entrepreneurship, as establish by new business start-ups. In this field growth of the business, the issues of managing and running the small business and closure of business due to untrained people, have been the area of research and investigation (Sue Marlow, 2016).

In this chapter the main focus is at the research did by different researcher on female entrepreneurship. The available data has been categorized as follows:

- 2.1.1 Past picture of small businesses.
- 2.1.2 Rate of female entrepreneurs.
- 2.1.3 Profile, characteristics and performance of female entrepreneurs.
- 2.1.4 The limitations encountered by female entrepreneurs.

2.1.1 Past Picture of Small Businesses

A growth rate of small business sector in early 1980s. In 1989, the net rate of establishing a new business was 1400 per week. Britain has a substantial part of self-employed people since 1920s, which accounts one-tenth of the working people (Ganguly, P., Bannock, 1985). The spectacular growth of small business sector is the United Kingdom was over all as unpredicted and was as amazing. From late 1930s until mid of 1970s, there was a very long apparently inevitable decrease in the statistics of small business and self-employment in the UK and in the business populations. This decrease was taken as a sign of financial development as business population developed, it was declared that the small business sector will slowly emaciated as the advancement of large business sector was blooming and the financial state of the country was increasing as well (JE Bolton, 1971).

Refereeing back to 1980s, some thoughts are that the downfall of the inevitable small business sector was broadly accepted, whilst few has brought about argument and controversies. Firstly, the least provocative thought was the variations in the economy itself. The size of primary manufacturing sector was greatly reduced after the mammoth economic restructuring and lead to the development of knowledge-based activities which has increase the opportunities for self-employment and revival of small business sector. Difficulties to enter in small business sector and level of absorption was lower in the new field of finance but the scale of economies was not evenly extends, as it was before in the field of finance (Anuradha

Basu, 1998). Most of the momentum following the development of small business sector was due to alterations in the administrative activities and commissioning procedures of large business sector. Due to the increase in the financial pressure and competition, the large business sector were setting up their branches in order to give attention at the essential activities, production and services were usually done internally, and reducing the permanent employees and mostly employing part time workers (Graham Bannock, 1987). The most routinely happening part of system variety identifies with the sort of arrangement used to set up establishment activities. Organizations may likewise fluctuate their strategies in regards to franchisee charges and sovereignty installments while building up worldwide establishments. Changes might need to be made in advertising techniques, staff enrollment, preparing, the board and bookkeeping systems and strategies. Lawful curiosities of unfamiliar business sectors, which will influence the privileges of the franchisor and franchisee and the general activity of the framework, should likewise be well-thought-out (Quinn, 1998). The small business sector was in competition with peers by utilizing the part time work force, in house support was the main criteria for UK's financial and social problems. A recent and more dominant position was given to small business sector which was imagined as minor sector by large business sector's financial experts and organizations (Atkinson, 1984; Boyer, 1987; Charles F. Sabel, 1982).

Because of the alterations in the governmental policies, the position of the government in the UK became critical in disintegrating the labor procedure, and generally it was debated that the development of small business sector and self- employed people is the outcome of the new policies and strategies being introduced by the government and international investment (Curran and Storey, 2002; Santos *et al.*, 2017). 1990's Bolton report on small business sector, mentions in their 20 years report that the expansion of self- employment was 1.9 million in 1979 and 2.9 million in 1989. There was an even growth in the number of business registering for VAT, which specifies the growth in the number of small businesses (Stanworth J, 1991).

The small business sector was then considered as a significant contributor in the prosperity of the UK. Around 3 million firms were registered as small businesses and self-employed in the UK in 1981. The report from Department of Employment in 1992 most of them usually hire less than 20 workers, which indicates that majority of the enterprises were small. These firms were accountable of more than 40 per cent of hiring people other than the national and local government levels. The total number of small business along with self-employment was 1.8 million in 1980 was increased to 2.7 million in 1991. Companies registered for VAT was

386,000 in 1979 and then increased to 1.7 million 1992. The number of self-employed people was 1.9 million in 1979 and in 1990 it was increased up to 3 million. Small firms who were hiring less than 20 employees were responsible for one third of the total work force in the Britain in 1991. In British urban communities, this governmental issue of perception has taken on especially unpredictable and challenged structures. Deindustrialization has left critical plots of empty, brownfield land in numerous metropolitan regions that present critical advancement difficulties and openings. One reaction has been to utilize incredible, local offices to 'quick track' drives and guarantee that major, property-drove projects are done on destinations with at least neighborhood resistance furthermore, association. This approach arrived at its apex during the 1980s also, 1990s with the foundation of Urban Advancement Corporations whose assets also, improvement dreams were given over by focal government offices (Raco and Tunney, 2010).

The fastest developed sectors from 1979 to 1992 were finance, property, and mainly small businesses. The amount of business became more than double in those fields. The highest increase was recorded in South-East which was up to around 45 percent and slowest was in North-West where the increase was only 22 percent. The development of small business sector was as fastest pace in the UK as compares to United States and Japan. In 1991, the rate of self-employment in the UK was a bit less than the EC average of 13. There were roughly 1.7 million organizations enrolled for VAT in the United Kingdom in 1990. More than 95% had a turnover of within 2,000,000 pounds and in this manner can be considered as rudimentary over whole. The absolute number of organizations in the economy at any one time is alluded to as the 'supply' of organizations; after some time, this stock changes because of new firms being made and firms stopping to exchange (Storey, 1994).

The SME (small and medium size enterprises) administrator might be liable for a few business errands on the double and mindfulness of issues past the everyday running of the business might be low (Tilley, 2000; Spence and Schmidpeter, 2003) SMEs can be hard to control as they are both hesitant to embrace intentional guideline but on the other hand are suspicious of organization and are less receptive to institutional pressing factors e.g., legitimate, contender benchmarking, government offices, public and private vested parties. Be that as it may, SMEs can likewise "be exceptionally versatile, quickly changing their exchanging limits as per changing business sector openings" Ideas connected to SMEs, for example, "local area" also, "entrepreneur" have become more unpredictable recommending a divided, a long way from homogeneous area working in various financial circles, in a scattered inventory network, with

varying administrative styles and proprietorship structures. In this way, the idea of the benefit boosting, levelheaded monetary business person as the standard picture of the independent venture proprietor supervisor is probably going to be bogus. Regional independent endeavor local area has a specific component in the regional independent endeavor local area, nonetheless, been advanced by the nearby position and the restoration of the nearby office of trade. To start with, the committee set up a business club in 1990. By 1994, with additional consolation, this small set-up promoted to chamber level. (Dex, S. and Scheibl, 2001; Curran, Rutherford and Smith, 2000).

A range of reasons motivated the ethnic minority communities to migrate to the UK, the requirement of the finance was crucial at the arrival of the Black people, forcing them to isolate in the work force (Bhavnani, 1994). The past examples prospers in the support of the nation that the ways of life, traditions, cultures of the migrants is directly proportional to the occupation for example small businesses and economy (Aldrich *et al.*, 1986; Burns, 2001). The term “middleman minority” was created to represent the migrated group, which creates a large portion of their employment from entrepreneurial activities, by trading and marketing of the goods to the native population of the country where they have been migrated to. The population of the migrated groups has evenly escalated over the years. It was reported in 1991 Census, that ethnic minorities were consist of 3 million people or 5.5 per cent of the total UK’s population (Bonacich, 1973; Cobas, 1986).

A general idea emphasizes the possibility of ethnic groups moving into the small business proprietorship which means that in 1993 according to Labor Force Survey stated that 25 per cent of ethnic minorities’ people in work are self-employed whereas from white people the rate of self-employment is only 16 per cent. This figure clarifies the susceptibility of start working as self-employed by ethnic minorities and the most of them are from Indian subcontinent. People from India, Pakistan and Bangladesh are among the highest rate of entered in small business ownership and self-employment (Campbell, 1992).

The development of the minority businesses was discussed extensively (Robin Ward, 1984), the large number of minority groups are self-employed and there several reasons present for this change. Aldrich stated that “the opportunity structure outweighs any cultural predisposition towards entrepreneurship”. For the ethnic groups, if the chances of getting the normal jobs are rare or they are not being employed due to discrimination then substitute methods of making money can be adopted as that’s the only method to survive. To overcome this racism, most of the migrants began with “rag” trade system which normally needs low

investment and experience (Aldrich, H., Jones, T.P., & McEvoy, 1984). Asians present in the West Midlands and Manchester (Werbner, 1984), and ethnic groups in the East of London (Floya Anthias, 1983) were ready to accept the jobs left by white people, by ignoring the little income and bad working conditions. Therefore instead of having a vast styles and variety from ethnic minority people in business they are mostly limited to retail and clothing sector, rather than having other choices (Ram, 1992).

2.1.2 Rate of Female Entrepreneurs

Study female entrepreneurship and their responsibility as being an owner, and employer has been often ignored as a topic of research although a large number of females are selecting self-employment as their career. In 1980, the estimated number of self-employed men and women increase at fast pace in the UK (Goffee and Scase, 1985) (Curran James, 1986). From 1981 till 1991, rate of self-employment for men was increase by 51 per cent whereas for women the rate of self-employment was 81 per cent (Daly, 1991). The increase in the rate of female self-employment correspondences the higher participation of females in the market. From 1977, the rate of working women has increase in almost all fields except from technicians and laborers. In 1991, more than 10 million females were working in the UK, among whom 6 million were working as full-time worker and 4.5 million was working as a part time workers. Over all female are accountable of 43 per cent of total work force in the UK (Curran., 1990). Researcher in the field of female studies have elaborated the condition of modern female employment in the UK (Martin J, 1984; Dex Shirley, 1987; Hakim, 1989).

A secondary analysis was conducted by Curran and Burrows they have utilized the General Household Survey (GHS) (1979-1984), data which shows that the ratio of male to female is more than 3 is to 1 in the small business ownership (Curran James, 1988). Another secondary analysis of the General Household Survey 1985, was carried out by Burrows suggested that although higher education, class and background was taken as probability factors, the rate of self-employed females is not more than one-half that of males. Though the range of this gender difference is reducing largely, it is estimated that in between 1978 to 1988, the rate of self-employed women was rose as doubled whereas the rate for men self-employment only risen by 50 per cent (Department of Employment, 1988). Therefore, these findings deny the statement given by Curran and Burrows from 1979 to 1984, the proportion of females and male stayed somewhat steady while the rate of male self-employment was higher than females. Conversely, Meager study has given a significant aid to the official data that the rate of female self-employment has increased much faster rate than males (N Meager, 1989).

A Labor Force Survey (1992) stated that 7 per cent of the female who are in working age are self-employed, this rate almost more than double than it was in 1979, but it is still less than the rate of self-employed males which is 17 per cent. Whereas 81 per cent males of ethnic minorities, who are in working age are employed, 20 per cent were Government workers or were on training programs and 17 per cent were self-employed (Steinhardt and Wedemeier, 2012; Bell and Smith, 2005).

The ratio of self-employment was maximum in the Indian males which was 26 per cent, males of Pakistani and Bangladeshi origin was 24 per cent and the females who were in working age and were working as self-employed was 7 per cent, which includes 11 per cent of females from India (Clark and Drinkwater, 2010; Dustmann and Fabbri, 2005; Dustmann *et al.*, 2003). Bureau of Labor Statistics report indicated that since 1979, the rate of self-employment has risen more than 2.3 million in United States of America, which suggested that the increase is more than five times faster than males' self-employment (Daphne Halkias, Shehla Arifeen, 2011).

In the United Kingdom, the growth in self-employment between 1981 and 1987 was estimated as 46 per cent (Owen and Green, 1992). The rate of female self-employment was more than double 1979. Therefore, females are now accountable for 24 per cent as self- employed than was in 1979 which was only 19 per cent 1994 (Meager, N., Court, G. and Moralee, 1994). Whereas black ethnic group was consisted of 10 per cent of 3.4 million of self-employed pupil (P. M. Bakshi, 1992).

If a comparison can be drawn between females of different origin than White women like to be self-employed than Black ethnic women but women from India, Pakistan and China are more into self-employment than any other ethnicity. In South-Asian, Bangladeshi women are least in number as self-employed. The self-employment rate of females is highest in the Midlands (Owen, 1994). Chinese women are more into self-employment as compared to Black women, that is one in five women of Chinese origin are working as self-employed whereas, Black-Caribbean are only one in fifty. However self-employment is a small contribution in the life of White and Black women but this plays a very important role and the main source of income, in the lives of South Asian women (Bradley, Don E, 2019). International data based on female self-employment is not easily available and if it does available then the studies has only used small sample sizes. The largest study was done by EEC on female entrepreneurship, the study was conducted in ten states (Markovic', 2007). This research stated that altogether 13 million females are engaged in business ownership out

of which 5 million have ownership of their business and the rest of them are involved in their family businesses. This study shows that mostly females owing their own business deals in less likely in industrial sector, these results are as similar as the finding of British Labor Force Survey.

A total of 17000 participants interviewed in this study, out of which 46 per cent were working in the retail sector, 12 per cent were in the beauty and health care sector, 10 per cent were in the “liberal professions”, 9 per cent were in handicraft and agriculture and almost 1 per cent were working in the industry. This study also mentions that females working in the agriculture sector are least privileged, they are old age and less educated and receiving less income. The labor Force Survey stated that there are two main industrial sectors where mostly females are working as self-employed (S Creigh, C Roberts, 1984). The biggest sector is “Distribution, Hotels and Catering” where 41.8 per cent of women working as self-employed and in “Other sectors” where 30.5 per cent women are self-employed, whereas only 10 per cent of males are involved in self-employment in these sectors. However men are mostly working as self-employed in Construction sector which is the third biggest sector for self-employment (Walker, 2009).

A case study was conducted in West Midlands suggested that 55 per cent of Asian males are self-employed, whereas the rate of female self-employed is lower than males which was only 30 per cent (D Kaur, 1993). Sunderland Household Survey discloses that 40 per cent of men has setup their construction business and are working as self-employed, whereas no women are involved in this field. However, women appeared to work as self-employed in the sectors such as distribution, hotels, caterings, repair of goods, and other sectors. This is amazing that the ratio of females is more than males in other sectors but still the total number of working women is less than men and this could be because of the reason that the large number women working as self-employed in the clothing sector (Groves, 2009).

2.1.3 Profile, Characteristics and Performance of Female Entrepreneurs

a. Background Data

A research conducted by Watkins and Watkins (1984), in which the sample size comprises of 58 women and 43 men. They have found that men like to have some experience of working in the same field prior to start any new business, by having an experience after commencing their new venture they feel more independent in their work. In this study they also found that mostly women are not prepared to start new business especially in the field

where they did not work before. As a result of this women always take more risk than men. They established that with restricted experience females has less choices of the field they want to work in and apply practical knowledge in their business. Selection of new business for a women is regulated according to the field which has less difficulties and hurdles to achieve success (Hafer, 2017). These fields are supposed to have low technical and economic obstacles as well as does not required managerial expertise to start up a new business and gain success in it. They have also observed numerous differences in regards to their age, marital status and educational prerequisites (Minniti and Naudé, 2010).

The females were notably few in numbers than males when compared for marital status that is men were mostly married. The comparison for age, two significant age groups were found in females that are between 25-35 years and 55-60 years old, whereas the mean result for men to start up new business was 39 years. The comparison for educational background fluctuates significantly between men and women business owners, but males are more likely to have professional qualification than females (Assudani, 2009). Business venture can include various real factors, yet these have the characterizing burn of activities that make something else and important. Business visionaries devote the fundamental time and exertion, expect to be the monetary, mental, and social dangers intrinsic in these activities, and, all the while, get the resultant prizes of financial and personal fulfillment. In any case, business advancement relies upon a bunch of organizing factors, including, among others, the accessibility of money, state-supported help arrangements and projects, the quality and content of schooling and preparing, the exchange of the consequences of R&D from the logical to the business local area, admittance to business and actual foundations, the disguise of development perspectives and inventive practices in the key callings, the transparency of target markets, and the impact of social of social and social standards, among others. Because of the restricted examination distributed so far on the specificities of ladies business visionaries' associations with established researchers, the current investigation zeroed in basically on female business venture overall (Santos, Marques and Ferreira, 2018).

The Labor Force Survey shows that self-employed females are slightly does not want to employ others pupil, and are far more likely to get involved in the fields like distribution, hotels, catering, repairs and others. Female business owners seem to work less hours than their male equivalents. LFS stated that there is no significant difference in age groups for male and female business owners. Lastly, around 44 per cent of female business owners come in the “managerial-occupational” group, whereas only 29 per cent of males are included in this

group. This huge difference is understandable due to the large number of males involved in constructions business are categorized as self-employed. This research was supported by Curran and Burrows who studies the GHS and discovered that women business owners (have 1-25 employees) are less likely than men to have any professional or specialized education (Warnecke, 2013).

The suggestion given by Curran and Burrows was supported by Watkins and Watkins (1984) that there is no considerable dissimilarity in the inclination of men and women self-employment, of attending any training in the early years of their self-employment. Female business owner hardly has any prior experience of owning a business and mostly were unemployed before starting up their own business, whereas men have had some sort of experience and mostly working as part time prior to the start of their business where they have started working as full time. Both males and females tend to have support from the government or other financial support organizations in the very first year of their business start-up, in order to run their businesses smoothly (Terjesen and Amorós, 2010). White women tends to have experience prior the start of their business whereas Black women mostly have no experience (PA Burdette, 1994). But this statement opposes the statement given by (DeCarlo and Lyons, 1979) that a significant number of women from ethnic minority are experienced before stating up their businesses, after evaluating the Sunderland Household Survey, stated that among self-employed, three quarter were married, forty nine per cent have experience of more than five years and eighty per cent of self-employed only had one year of experience of working as self-employed. Seventy per cent had no academic education and eighty-two per cent had no practical or professional education. The age group of most self-employed was 35-44 years. This age group's result confirms the finding of Meager's (1989) who also stated that higher rate of self-employment found in age 35-44 years and then the rate reduces and then again increase after the age of 65 years (Meager and Bates, 2009). In Meager's (1989) secondary analysis of 1984 Labor Force Survey, he stated that people who don't have any professional qualification on only have GCE-A level education, are most likely working as self-employed.

A study was conducted by Gitobu and Gritzmacher in rural Kenya, the target population was female entrepreneurs and the results stated that about two-third of the female entrepreneurs were at the age of 40 years or younger but the average age was around 35 years. Among those women only half of them has school education and a small number of them had professional business related education, and about half of the total sample size were married (Gitobu, J.K.;

Gritzmacher, 2013). A research in the 350 companies and their finding was that twenty per cent of the companies were owned by females among that thirty one per cent were in the age group of 34 years or younger and twenty eight per cent were of 45 years or above (Link and Strong, 2016). Men were more likely to be educated than women but women were less likely to have no education. Most of them were in the age group of 39-45 years age at the start of their business and have got higher secondary school education. There are various resemblances among people little firm proprietors, there are critical contrasts in their way to deal with, and experience of, independent work. This is obvious in thought processes in firm beginning up and issues of the executives and development. Contentions on the side of gender orientation as a separating trademark for independent work are generally drawn from discrete investigations of people in business. To embrace a more powerful assessment of any gender orientation impact, female and male independently employed, shows various key regions in little firm possession. From the information acknowledged, it arises that gender may intrude upon the encounters of the entrepreneur in beginning and dealing with their own firm. It is obvious that this examination reflects others in setting up resemblances among people who decide to possess their own endeavors, yet through this coordinated with concentrate there arise contrasts that should be situated in the gender of the proprietor (Marlow, 1997).

Generally, the proportion of self-employment in males and females is maximum in the young age groups that is between 16-19 years, whereas males have higher rates if self-employment than females. By the age of 25-34 years the proportion of self-employment among men and women reduces to 2:1 but the proportion increases again in the age groups of 35-54 and reduced again in older age groups, controlled the marital status in the study and reported the same pattern of inclination of the proportion of males and females throughout the life span. The rate of self-employment is considerably low in single pupil as compared to pupil in other categories. There are variances in the self-employment rate according to age. Though the age has been controlled, but the ratio of self-employment remains low in single people than married (Burrows and Ford, 1998; Müller, 2004) .

Females who run their own business don't just react to the work economic situations as "financial man," yet in addition as friendly entertainer, relative, ethnic gathering part, and member of neighborhood social and monetary networks. Female business visionaries and their organizations are profoundly implanted in their nearby networks as their different jobs are formed at both home and work place. Their individuals group doesn't just give a unique situation or a "compartment," yet in addition connect with the social entertainer in fashioning

their enterprising encounters. From their inspirations to make the undertaking, to explicit functional methodologies, and to estimating business achievement, collaboration with neighborhood local area has been interwoven between the private and open arenas in their social and financial lives (Wang, 2019).

Studies showed that being divorced separated or widowed have higher rate of self-employments. Meager used Labor Force Survey 1984 and stated that separated, divorced or widowed males have higher rates of self-employment even if compared to married females. However, he stated that widowed females have higher rate of self-employment, whereas divorced or separated females has lower rate as compared to married women but bit higher than single females. The above mentioned findings corresponds with the small research of women owing the small businesses found that their sample size is comprises of large number of widows (Wiklund, Patzelt and Shepherd, 2009). This research outcome opposes the findings of Curran and Burrows where by using GHS and proposed that widowed women does not have high proportion of self-employment than other categories (Curran James, 1988).

b. Reasons for Choosing Business Proprietorship

Due to the limitations of the labor market and methods of avoiding the continuous isolation, as a reaction of both people consider self-employment. Therefore, the increase in the number of women self-employment can be perceived similarly as rise in the participation and mainly static position of females in the labor market (Goffee and Scase, 1985; Cromie and Hayes, 1988). Female entrepreneurs have similarities with male entrepreneurs except in the industrial sector where females are like to trade (Schreier, 1975). The motivation of stating up the business for women is almost same as men, such as seeking freedom and impartiality, and the challenge of owing a business (Schwartz, 1976). Disappointment due to the absence of chances and prospects or not getting promoted in the companies, feeling that they can do better than men and the ability of accepting the challenge are the main reasons for female to start up their own business (N. Vokins, Allen S, 1993).

Koper and Vermunt stated that an increase of self-confidence with in their skills, approachability to education, and the desire to be financially self-regulating than their husbands or partners promotes females to go for paid work or to start up their own ventures (Koper and Vermunt, 1988). Holmquist and Sundin's conducted a study in Sweden with 64,420 women entrepreneurs, stated that major motivation for the females to generate something with which they can achieve their freedom by following their family responsibilities together with a decent income (C Holmquist, 1989). The conservative females

are inspired by the independence and the idea of earning their own money by harmonizing their home responsibilities (Robert Goffee, 1987).

Labor market studies (Cockburn, 1983; Rubery, 1988) suggested that females are distinguished in different groups in the employment market. Therefore, if single, married or divorced, owning a business is one of the most appropriate ways to by-pass the prejudice in the job sector. The two major reasons for females to start up their own business is being independent and they can work as when they want (Hakim, 1979). Female entrepreneurs in Kenya mentions their reasons for self-employment are being flexible and liberty to work and the financial autonomy. Females from ethnic minorities or Black women stated that, owning the business is the only option for them to stay alive (M Morokvasic-Muller, 1988; Mann and Thorpe, 1998). This was verified by Rees he stated that females from ethnic minorities are underprivileged and manage to survive on low income, they have the only option to start their business by which they can step out of the deprivation (T Rees, 1992). Freedom and the idea of working for themselves, the pleasure of being their own boss, displeasure for working other, the belief that they could do better than others, are all the reasons given by the people who step into self-employment (James Curran, 1991). Owning a business can provide the chance to amalgamate the career gratification and the economic autonomy, along with fulfilling their family responsibilities and duties.

Whereas the peculiarity and the drawback of facing discrimination as Asians when they apply for the jobs is another factor which encourage them to start up their own businesses, but Asian women who experience restrictions from employers may suffer from some difficulties in starting up their enterprise (Robin Ward, 1984). People from ethnic minorities have only one option to set up their own business to overcome the discrimination they have gone through in employment in regards of getting good jobs and getting promotions (J Stanworth, 1973). A study conducted by Marlow (1990), she included 400 small businesses in the West-Midlands and concluded that rarely any business was owned by Black people and she refers this to problems in getting funds and no marketing option outside their communities. According to (RW Brown Jr - S. III. ULJ, 1984), Asian people, who incline to work in the labor industries, are more likely to be self-employed than White people, though they are more likely to be self-employed than Afro-Caribbean (Etim and Iwu, 2019).

In one of the studies conducted by (Hisrich R. D, Brush, 1984) in America, they have stated that independence, achievement and job satisfaction are the main inspiring aspects to start up a business. It is also an alternative to unemployment (Bevan, 1989; N Meager, 1989; H

Metcalf, 2000). Moreover Hakim (1988) also mentions that there is some kind of a link between self-employed and unemployment and the level of insecurity is also believed, although there are doubt present regarding the significance of unemployment which is also taken as “push” factor which commands people to work as self-employed. For females entrepreneurs, economic necessity is main reason for setting up their own ventures (Goetting, Marsha A.; Muggli, 1988). Age, gender, social class, background, marital status, ethnicity and education all are the motivating factor for women to start working as self-employed (Stanworth J, 1991). Community antagonism encourages small business set up because it also limits the ethnic minorities to what they want to do. They face discrimination as a worker and their unstable societal status provoke them to step out and start working as self-employed and get successful (E Bonacich, 1980).

c. Business Characteristics

Women mostly run their businesses more melodramatically than men, they admit their mistakes easily and think less and take decisions very quickly. They are more outgoing than men and are capable to encourage their workers more easily. “Creativeness”, “intuition” and “expertise” are vital for an entrepreneur and these characteristics are mostly present in women (Koper, 1993). Bolton 20 years report on small firms, discovered the main features of people owing the small firms are “need for achievement”, “locus of control”, “risk-taking propensity”, “need for independence” and “innovative behavior” (Stanworth J, 1991).

Whereas (C.A., 1992) stated that “creativity”, “risk taking”, “self-esteem” and “dedication” are the main characteristics for an entrepreneur. While Fortenberry also stated that “moderate risk taking”, “creativity”, “competence”, “high achievement”, “human relation” and “mental capacity” are main characteristics for entrepreneurs (Fortenberry, 1988) (C.A., 1992). Chell (1986) illustrates “competency”, “encoding strategies in personal constructs”, “expectancies” “subjective values” and “self-regulatory system and plans” are the characteristic that must be present in the female entrepreneurs (Stanworth *et al.*, 1989). The characteristics of entrepreneurs are presented in Table No. 02.

Table 2 Characteristics of New Entrepreneurs (Koper, 1993)

Characteristics	Masculine	Feminine	Neutral

Desirable	Influential Rationale Self-conscious Ambitious Firm	Attentive Cooperative Tactful Understanding	Active Daring Improvisational Serious Versatile Enquiring Flexible Persistence Enthusiastic Creative Dynamic Independent Incorruptible Imaginative Logical thinking Purposeful
Undesirable	Dominant Inattentive	Emotional Gentle Irresolute	Absent minded
Neutral	Cheerful Formal	Spontaneous Sensitive Intuitive	Attractive

2.1.4 Business Performance

Performance in business is mostly associated with the success of the business. For women, to keep a balance in their business and family life and capable of managing their business along with the ample profit achieved to keep the business running successfully. Actually, the small firms who are only looking forward to follow the ambition of their owner are neither growing in terms of accounts, nor being able to be a significant employer, which mostly happens with women owing the small firms (Marlow and Strange, 1994).

Table 3 Characteristics of Entrepreneurs Defined by different Researchers

Dates	Names of Authors	Characteristics of Entrepreneurs
1848	Mills J.S	Comportment of any Hazard
1917	Weber	Having official authority foundation
1934	Schumpeter	Availability of Novelty/Ingenuity
1954	Sutton	Sense of accountability
1959	Hartman	Source of proper consultant
1961	McClelland	Menace captivating; prerequisite for success
1963	David	Aspiration; responsibility; self-confidence; ongoing for freedom; duty; fearlessness; relationships with people and interchanges capacity, specialized information
1971	Homaday and Abound	Essential for accomplishment, Autonomy, Power Recognition, Independence, Innovative, Aggressive
1973	Winter	Requisite for authority
1974	Borland	In-house Locus of Control
1974	Liles	Necessity of accomplishment

1977	Grasse	Particular value direction
1978	Timmons	Drive/fearlessness; objective arranged, directed daring individual, inside locus of control; imagination; inspiration
1980	Sexton	Fiery, aggressive, positive response to set-backs
1982	Welsh and White	Need to control, obligation searcher, self-assurance/drive, challenge taker, moderate daring person
1982	Dunkelberg and Cooper	Development arranged; freedom situated, expert arranged
1998	Blanchflower and Oswald	Entrepreneur -- the self-employed individual
2006	McMullen and Shepherd	<i>“To be an entrepreneur, therefore, is to act on the possibility that one has identified an opportunity worth pursuing”</i>
2006	Herbert and link	An entrepreneur is an innovator
2008	Burke, Fitzroy and Nolan	“The simplest kind of entrepreneurship is self-employment,” and we follow these authors, and many others, by using ‘entrepreneur’ and ‘self-employed’ interchangeably.
2013	Sharma	An individual who can who initiate, organize and run a business enterprise

2020	Kataria, Nandal and Malik	A true entrepreneur is a person who has independence of spirit. "One should be innovative, dynamic and willing to try every avenue towards success."
2021	Eniola	An entrepreneur is identified as an innovator, creator, locator, and risk-taker through leadership exercise. In this context, an entrepreneur is described as the maker of something new and a creator in the economy of today.
2022	Newman, Obschonka and Block	Entrepreneur is the focal actor and owner in a businesses

The education level of the owner of the business directly associated with performance of the business. The highly educated and experienced the owner the greater the performance of their business. Whereas Monck stated that prior experience of working in the same field, surveillance of the opportunities available in the market and the managerial experience all are correlated in the success of the small firm (Monck, C. S. P., 1988). The Natwest Quarterly Survey led by Small Business Research Trust (1993) discovered that rise in sale, rise in employment and investment are the main condition required in the performance of the small business. The income and viability of the business owned by females are more successful than the business owned by males. Therefore the rate of employment has reduced instantly in the businesses owned by males than that of owned by females (Johnson, 1993).

Thorpe mentions that the success more often is related to the creation of jobs and the creation of profit. However he also debated that the success and failure of the business needs to be initially evaluated in relation of the motivation with which the business was set up (Thorpe, 1989). In regards to the comparison of the South Asians and African Caribbean's, the main competition for the ethnic minorities and the White people is the numbers of hours of worked by ethnic minorities as they are more willing to search for the business and sales in the evening, at weekends or in the holiday. This can be seen in Table 04.

Table 4 Competitive Behavior of South Asian and White Entrepreneurs

	South-Asians Entrepreneurs	White Entrepreneurs
Days Open per week	6.2	5.6
Hours open per day	10.1	8.9
Percentage open Sunday	52	17
Percentage in co-operative buying organization	14	13
Percentage making deliveries	36	44
Hours worked per week	61	57
Percentage selling on credit	37	38

However still there are few reservations in regards to the dominance and performance of the South Asian business owners. In comparison of South Asians and White female entrepreneurs, White always showed more profit in their ventures, half of the White entrepreneurs showed some saving in comparison of the only a quarter of South Asian showed some savings in their businesses (T Jones, 1986).

Iyer and Shapiro stated that entrepreneurs from ethnic minorities link up with self-employment due to bond they have with their ethnic group (Gopalkrishnan R. Iyer, 1999). The causes of an increase in the self-employment amongst South Asian Entrepreneurs, are explained by Oc and Tiesdell that the “the substitution of bank loans with access to a strong social network of friends and extended family” is the main reason that South Asians has got advantage over the other ethnic groups (Oc, Taner, 1998; Ram *et al.*, 1999).

2.1.5 The Barrier and Issues Encountered by Female Entrepreneurs

The interest of females in innovative practices remains vulnerable by the latitude of obstructions and limitations. There are number of different issues and barriers encountered by female entrepreneurs which are discusses in detailed below.

Mainly females suffer from double problems that are at work and at home. Female entrepreneurs can't depend on their partners to get any kind of support and therefore they have bare the load of running their business and home simultaneously (Goffee and Scase, 1985) (Kirkham, 1987; Rosa, Peter, Daphne Hamilton, Sara Carter, 1994). Whereas male entrepreneurs always look forward for the voluntary support from their partner in their business as well as at home (Goffee and Scase, 1982).

a. Culture/ Norms (Gender Inequality)

Male entrepreneurs usually expect to get emotional and practical support and assistance in maintaining their business females particularly wives. However in the field of female entrepreneurs, there is more competition and more struggle and stress than male entrepreneurs (Hassan Hend, 2021). It is mostly doubtful for female entrepreneurs to achieve success and benefits by being self-employed, especially for those who chose this field to accommodate the needs of domestic labor but are still completing their domestic tasks as well as running their business. Self-employment is not as easy task for females when they don't have any support from their family members in their house hold work and they have fulfill the demands of work and home both simultaneously (S Marlow, 1994a).

Gender specified responsibilities and generalizations by implication sway ladies' business venture through a promising circumstance assessment and asset obtaining. Gupta suggested that manly cliché data about business people (e.g., business people are forceful and daring individuals) supports men's chance assessments. In the event that business people are depicted utilizing the gender impartial data, people will assess business openings as similarly good. Moreover, some male pictures of effective business people are held by potential asset suppliers, for example, investors and bank officials, which can set females in a difficult situation with respect to admittance to significant assets (Wu, Li and Zhang, 2019).

On the other hand male entrepreneurs, always prioritize their business and its their wife's duty to run and manage the home, while female entrepreneurs struggles to perform both roles together that is their duty to look after their home and children and to look after their business as well, this will often give them stress from work and guilt that they may not be able to give time to their home (Galanaki *et al.*, 2013; Židonis, 2015).

The working profiles of females claimed firms additionally reflect summed up feminized working examples which oblige caring duties close by their financial movement. In this way, the accessible information demonstrates about portion of independently employed ladies work low maintenance (under 30 hours out of each week) and around a third base their organizations

inside the home. Male entrepreneurs, anyhow contend with their cliché business profile with much lower paces of low maintenance and home working. The econometric scrutiny of profits from independent work, gives an unequivocal proof that females without kids beat men as far as income. Accordingly, "the presence of little kids and more noteworthy long stretches of housework negatively affect female profit. Analyzing this information through a presentation focal point it is clear that area decision, area and working profiles fundamentally sway the capability of such organizations as far as sturdiness, development and abundance creation. (Marlow and McAdam, 2013)

For a long time, a female's place in non-industrial nations (some might contend, in created nations, too) has been viewed as in the home. Financial specialists have consistently battled with the novel difficulties introduced by socially built the jobs of male and female separately: these have both set out open doors for ladies' headway and have restricted their development as experts. The innovative undertakings of ladies include gender orientated issues; women's activist writing contends that pioneering conduct is intrinsically one-sided gender and thus is slanted to repeat a constituency which is man-centric relationship (Minniti, 2009; Yetim, 2008) expressed that elements like hindrances of genders roles, male mastery, low compensation, bias and separation keep female members from attempting to progress in their professions and power them to start their own organizations. Of the relative multitude of elements related with female business venture, the customary pretended by female members inside the family is quite possibly the main contemplations impacting ladies' choices to become business people. In both created and non-industrial nations, ladies will in general work in lower-usefulness organizations: this incompletely clarifies the gender orientation wage hole, where ladies are paid not as much as men. (Kalemci Tuzun and Araz Takay, 2017).

Carter and Cannon stated that unsupportive behavior of male counterpart of female entrepreneurs may make their relationship worst, but they found that only a small number of female entrepreneurs' mentions that their husband and wife relation deteriorate ever since they have become a business owner. Most of them stated that their spouse relationship has become stronger. Most of the female entrepreneurs mentions that their relationship with their children has also improved since they have start their business (Sara Carter, 1992).

Females have various encounters as females in the working environment from those of their male friends. They structure practically a large portion of the labor force, however possess just 33% of administrative positions, and those are bunched at the lower levels. Ladies are likewise paid not as much as men directly from introductory graduation, where the hole is

15%, to the executives levels, where the hole increments to 20 percent (Cabinet Office, 2002). Ladies will in general float towards lower-paid areas and, even in high-flying vocations, they will in general move out of practical positions towards staff capacities like work force and preparing, obliged by glass dividers just as the discriminatory limitation. Ladies are rejected from the senior casual organizations by their gender. Furthermore, numerous ladies have a twofold work shift, dealing with the majority of the childcare and homegrown duties when in double vocation connections or as single parents. (Vinnicombe and Singh, 2002) (Abraham, 2020).

Mostly around half a number of female entrepreneurs are settled in married life or are in a relationship alike marriage whereas around 90 per cent of male entrepreneurs are settled in their married life and running their businesses successfully because their wife's are playing an important and usual family role or even supporting them in their businesses. On the other hand, mostly, husbands of female entrepreneurs are not ready to accept that they have to support and help their wife's in the domestic tasks if they are working as self-employed. The few families where husbands are engaged with their wife's in their business they usually play an external or ADHOC role instead of being supportive and complaint with their wife (Shen, Osorio and Settles, 2017).

Male-controlled relationship in their home and unfair distribution of household work leads to the type of business mostly females had started. Phizacklea (1988) attempted to analyze the noticeable growth in business expertise amongst some females from Asian background by explaining them that their mistreatment in their families is now also spread in their work lives (Parminde Bhachu, 1988). The feat in some business owned by ethnic minorities are because of the male-controlled relationships which permits females to be a vital part of low earning labor. For Asian entrepreneurs, family and community support is very important in the provision of low demanding workers for their newly set up business (TL Rees, 1992). They have the financial help from their families is the biggest advantage for Asian women whereas that's not been seen in any other nationalities (Peter Wilson, 1986).

b. Lack of Proper Training and Schooling for Female Entrepreneurs:

Endeavors run by female business visionary's faces assortment of issues at each stage, from gaining essential assets to run venture and keeping up with the outer relations. Specifically for little undertakings of ladies in creating economies need bearings and imperatives to business advancement are associated with work, helpless accounting, less market openings and item understanding (Della-Giusta and Phillips, 2006). In any case, this wonder of

enterprising advancement among ladies is viewed as very progressive; the pace of ladies innovative action in creating parsimonies is corresponding to 45.5%, that is much more than other alternative economies. To the extent ladies claimed undertaking's beginning up, development and conclusion are apprehensive, it's brought up by (Naser *et al.*, 2009) that countless ladies participates in new businesses because of nature of exercises generally required like low abilities, Low schooling prerequisite and low section boundaries. During the development stage, ladies claimed business experiences organizing issues absence of market and item data, balance between serious and fun activities and absence of capital. The referenced issues during development stage conclusion rate are high in the event of ladies business visionaries. In the year (1997) Lerner introduced an analysis which expressed that ladies business visionaries assume significant part in creating economies like any created economy. However, they don't have any set model to follow that assistance to track their enterprise efficiently (Lerner, Brush and Hisrich, 1997). He additionally asserted that ladies business visionaries execution like the size of business, productivity, net incomes and pay is subject to factors that all meet up to improve her direct in business. Openings and boundaries looked by ladies business visionaries are impacted by both formal and casual area and interior and outer elements.(Jha, Makkad and Mittal, 2018; Garg and Agarwal, 2017)

Understanding the nature and wellsprings of the gender orientation holes in pioneering returns is essential to endeavors at fostering a lively private area just as advance female work market support. The industriousness of gender orientation segregation in independent work might limit the section of female into pioneering exercises and lessen the capacity of females to completely take part and receive the rewards of enterprising turn of events (Bögenhold and Klinglmair, 2015). What's more, the inability to address gender incongruities in pioneering returns and gender orientation wage holes in conventional pay business might sustain financial and social disparities saw on the mainland. For strategy purposes, information on the nature and wellsprings of gender orientation holes in big business execution will empower governments and strategy producers to plan gender delicate strategies to help the presentation of female-claimed firms and advance female business venture. (Agyire-Tettey, Ackah and Asuman, 2018)

c. Lack of Resources and Financial Support:

Regarding the issues and barriers in business, Research shows that the biggest barrier in the success of the businesspersons who are female often have shortage of financial assets, they mostly dearth the basic of knowledge process to run their business, and understanding the cost

of maintaining the industry (Halkias *et al.*, 2011). Discrimination always stays as an issue for females in entrepreneurship as they used to encounter whilst working as an employee, and the availability of funds is the main issue (Sara and Peter, 1998). Female entrepreneurs encounter more difficulties in obtaining finance than male entrepreneurs, for the reason that their proposal or plans are or may not be taken seriously by investors (D Deakins, 1991; Nicola Patterson, Sharon Mavin, 2012; Koper, 1993) stated that mostly female entrepreneurs think that they are exposed to prejudiced behavior from the banks (Melorose *et al.*, 2008).

Organizing impacts ladies business visionaries' venture in a viable manner (Brush, Bruin and Welter, 2009). Predominantly ladies business people are the piece of the casual systems administration framework, their investment in formal systems administration is not as much as men (Orban, 2001). Ladies' organizing is principally affected by family associations, which isn't quite thought to be ready to go terms. Her absence of systems administration makes boundaries in business mindfulness also (Manolova, Tatiana S. and Manev, Ivan M., 2007; Hossain *et al.*, 2009). Systems administration assumes a fundamental part in teaming up and restricting firms together in all various levels independent of the formal and casual undertaking. Likewise, organizing gives financial specialists an expansive scope of sources which help in maintaining the business in every single odd circumstance (Staber, 2001). Another research shows that pioneering action like systems administration is one of the main considerations which impact the presentation of ladies business people. Accessibility of monetary assets is one of the serious issues looked by ladies business visionaries all through her enterprising excursion. Practically all the previous examination and reports show the absence of capital, absence of security and monetary institutional constraint as the factor that impacts ladies' her capacities to maintain a business (Naser *et al.*, 2009; Morris *et al.*, 2006). Past examinations show that ladies face a greater number of challenges than men to start and seek after business exercises (Carter, S., Anderson, S., Shaw, 2001; Mckinsey, 2011; Jayawarna, Rouse and Kitching, 2013). Exploration work by Afrin brought up that on the grounds that getting finance is one of the significant difficulties, generally provincial business venture is taken up by ladies' which is upheld by microcredit plans with simple accessibility (Afrin, S., Islam, N., Ahmed, 2010; Jha, Makkad and Mittal, 2018).

The bank managers are mostly hesitant to provide funding to female owned businesses, especially those who are outside the usual feminized enterprises (S Marlow, 1994b). Capital Planning Information (1985) suggested that management, finance, marketing and advertising, employing or hiring the workers, rules, regulation and location of their business are the main

issues and barriers for the entrepreneurs. The small business generally faced two types of issues that is lack of main administrative or organizational skills and lack of appropriately skilled workers (Tripathi and Singh, 2018).

The issue of gender orientation and business has been very much perceived, e.g., the absence of integrative structures for understanding the nature and ramifications of issues identified with gender and business has been a significant hindrance. Different discoveries, more noteworthy monetary flourishing and more noteworthy financial opportunity cultivate business all through the conveyance of in general and female business, while higher corporate duties have a comparably predominant adverse consequence. Nation size (by means of populace) is reliably immaterial, as in prior outcomes tables. At last, the impact of majority rules system is moderately less critical for countries with broadly predominant by and large business venture; though the general importance is lower around the middle for female business (Goel, 2018).

The Bolton report (1991), mentions that the main barrier encountered by the small businesses are the accessibility of finance, interest rate, cash flow, shortage of business, tax loads, government's laws, paperwork, shortage of skilled workers, race and opposition from big businesses and increase in the prices (Dhaliwal, 2000). Advertising of products and services, competition within the market, organizations of business, delivery and supply of goods, recognition from clients and relationship with clients and the legal issues are the main barriers encountered by female entrepreneurs. Even after the decision of starting a business, discrimination always effect the course of the business owned by ethnic minorities (Ram, 1992). This condition is elevated when discrimination occurs in the well-established areas, such as unfair and inequity from the banks (Ward, 1987; Jones *et al.*, 1989) insurance companies which is mainly seen in the female entrepreneurship (Handler, 1994).

d. Networking and Management Skills:

Carter and Cannon (1992), gives attention grabbing vision regarding the consequences of owing the business upon the quality of life, friendships, social life, time for themselves and the income. The connection with friends weaken because of shortage of time, in order to satisfy the responsibility of owing a business have negative effect upon the social life (Howell and Nanda, 2019). Mostly entrepreneurs don't have time or have very less time for themselves. Mostly at the start of the business, income is low and if the business gets success then entrepreneurs can expect higher returns over time. Inappropriate child care due to work load, accessing the business training and shortage of networks and role models are the

problems encountered by female entrepreneurs and lastly the shortage of time and sometimes inadequate income becomes the main reasons for the worsening the quality of life (Department of Employment, 1992).

The main gender based constraints encountered by female entrepreneurs are social, legal, market information, economical, organizational and management capabilities (Gayen, McQuaid and Raeside, 2010). As females are more likely work in small-firms setting, the banks and other financial supporting organization would rather like to support large firms due to the fact that small less business deals whereas the large firms have guarantee of getting business (Seaman, McQuaid and Pearson, 2014).

Small firms are more likely to rely on informal financial support with very high interest rates because the small firms are not included in the microfinance businesses. Therefore, female entrepreneurs are comparatively more affected. The barriers from government also extremely affect the business led by female entrepreneurs. Small business owned by females have limited opening times because their customers are also females. Female entrepreneurs also have limited times to move around in the community due to their family, security and religion obstructions. Insufficient organizational skills are another factor affecting the smooth run of their business. Female business visionaries may not just have less organizations than their male partners yet are probably going to be inserted in various kinds of organizations. Also, Munch et al. (1997) propose that because of their childrearing obligations, ladies will commonly improve their organization creation to support kinfolk (loved ones) over different types of organization contacts. Male SME proprietors are bound to get to formal organizations, while female SME proprietors are bound to get to casual organizations (especially loved ones). In synopsis, apparently past research recommends that, contrasted with men, ladies are probably going to have less organizations, less time accessible for systems administration and organizations that favor loved ones (in number binds with not many underlying openings) over proficient counsels (feeble binds with numerous primary openings) (Watson, 2012).

Business visionary gender is free of organization benefit and business achievement. I then, at that point delve into the substance of the organizations and discover three person characteristics:

(1) Generally comparable sorts of contacts and connections in the organizations around people,

(2) Gender orientation homophile as men bound to have networks made completely out of men, and ladies bound to have numerous ladies among their business contacts,

(3) comparable utilization of male and female contacts predictable with the male-situated sentiments (Burt, 2019).

In 2013 a research was conducted in Brazil, outlining the private and occupational challenges of female entrepreneurs. The result was categorized in two key sections, first was their emotional viewpoints; for example, the connections with their family, life partner or with their friends who are also acting as their business partners and second was their business management and administration challenges. To provide the solution of the challenges female entrepreneur's participants were facing, a training program was introduced to support and empower them with management skill and also to provide awareness regarding their daily problems in their businesses (Maria Hagan and Wassink, 2016).

Business visionaries' interpersonal organizations are dynamic, changing all through the lifetime of their new pursuits and pioneering vocations, yet surviving examination has commonly ignored an interaction situated methodology (Hoang and Antoncic, 2003). Until this point in time, most examination regards business people's interpersonal organizations as static, inspecting the impact of informal communities at a solitary period of the business interaction (for example startup), instead of across numerous stages. Business people require various assets at various periods of the business venture measure. As they continued looking for new assets, business people are probably going to initiate and design new organization binds to help developing exercises and openings (Majbritt Rostgaard Ewald , Klyver, Kim, 2006; Majbritt Rostgaard Ewald , Klyver, Kim, 2006; Greve and Salaff, 2003; Johannisson, 1996; Larson and Starr, 1993; Lin, 2001; EH Buttner, 1997). The connection between having a business visionary in one's organization and cooperation in innovative movement might be more grounded or more fragile at various stages in one's enterprising profession. For instance, enterprising systems administration might be more significant for disclosure business visionaries, who need to recognize, access, and assemble assets, than for startup and youthful business people who have more evolved assets and schedules (Klyver and Grant, 2010). The research which was conducted in 5 different cities of Pakistan by (Roomi and Parrott, 2008). In the interviews, researcher asked about the three most common challenges or barriers female entrepreneurs, encountered. The first challenge stated was to acquire the finance for the commencement of their business, the second challenge stated was the absence of the managerial skills to run their business, and the third challenge stated was at the beginning

phase of their business, very inadequate rules and strategies provided by the government. The researcher also mentioned that the majority of the females entrepreneurs were facing a problem of moving freely in the society and the implementation of veil was mandatory for them. The barrier highlighted was in the male dominated society, they have to deal with the illiterate or less educated males, where most of them have a believe that if they listen to female advise or instructions than their self-respect will compromise. These barriers are very disappointing that only a strong female with lots of passion can overcome them. The researcher has provided some solutions of those challenges and barriers. Firstly, he has mentioned about Quran (The Holy book), permits women to trade and setup their businesses and also Prophet Mohammad (P.B.U.H) wife (Hazrat Khadija) was an entrepreneur and the religion permits females to get education and also females are entitled to own assets and businesses. According to Islam, females can also be benefited from equality and respect. The researcher also pointed out that there should be some training programs introduced which are for females only and based on management skills (Roomi and Parrott, 2008).

A research was carried out in 2015 by Sweety Gupta and Aanchal Aggarwal in India, they have also emphases on the challenges encountered by female's entrepreneurs, the main challenge they mentioned was "the absence of attentiveness in professional responsibilities". Indian female entrepreneurs cannot concentrate in their business or in their professional responsibilities as they do in their private or family life, irrespective of they have outstanding entrepreneurial capabilities (Gupta S., 2015).

This lack of attentiveness towards their business creates difficulties in inspiring the new female entrepreneurs. The next point they have discussed about "financial uncertainty of female entrepreneurs", the females in India are in really underprivileged and the lack of education which plays a vital role if a female wants to be independent. The education system for females in India is primordial, which doesn't permit the recognition of the capabilities. The third challenge they have mentioned was "the female entrepreneurs doesn't want to take chances in their business", Most of the females cannot perform any risk-taking activities because they are lacking in the abilities to take risks or take chances in their businesses. They discussed about the dispute which unconsciously occurred between males and females regarding their business, which makes it more difficult for an Indian female entrepreneurs to perform in this competition and to give their hundred percent. Marketing of the product is also difficult for them because the market is mostly run by males, female entrepreneurs need to

hire some agents thru them they can access the market or to the retailers to market their product.

Another aspect discussed was “the lack of family encouragement”, women have to dedicate their long periods of time in the establishment of their businesses, which as a result create difficulties to fulfil the requirements of their family members and the society also. They are not being able to perform their household activities, and also it is difficult for them to pay attention towards the requirements of their offspring, which is the cause of a dispute in their own family lives. These disputes will lead to reduce their confidence levels, which eventually becomes difficult for them to perform their duties as a women entrepreneur (Gupta S., 2015).

The importance of females as a business holders or administrations has become a substantial occurrence in current era throughout the developed countries, expressing it appropriate to reassess the perception of females in occupation as a businessperson and their status in the societal and domestic structure as familiarized by gender, which allows or interrupts their job or business pursuit (Peris-Ortiz, Rueda-Armengot and Osorio, 2012). Roomi and Harrison indicates several gender disparities between business owners at different levels that is personal, individual and institutional. Personally they are not taken serious by their partners or the absence of respect or the eagerness of the males to do business with females (Harrison and Roomi, 2011). Individually they are discouraged to run their business, lack of time management skills and planning and on the institutional basis access to the training or advice-giving services, the criteria of selection in the training is difficult. The females are victimized in the name of societal and traditional morals and for the sake of religious belief. It is always difficult for the females to go on board regarding their financial decisions (Roomi and Harrison, 2010). Though in this kind of societies it is hard for females to go on board upon financial plans, but the one who are courageous or sufficiently privileged to go on board will suffer from absence of approach or the control to the wealth, land, business locations, information and expertise. The limited communication with males seemingly bounds their chances to obtain skills regarding business management and therefore the lack in the potential entrepreneurial developmental skills. To conclude the paper of Roomi and Harrison (2010), they suggested that there is a dire need of training which particularly designed for females to enhance their skills.

2.2 Aspects of Women Entrepreneurs' Accomplishments

Females are more in to micro-level and small-scale initiatives but they encounter same issues and barriers in the progression of their business. There are certain problems which they

normally faced but most common issues that female entrepreneur's encounters are the gender prejudice in the socio-economic setting where they are operating their business. As compared to men they encounter social, cultural, educational and technological issues more whilst setting up their business and gain access to financial supplies (Isaga, 2019; Mayoux, 2001). Moreover, this is obvious that females from different ethnic groups bare the additional load of their family and home duties, and this can sometime limit their capability to earn in their business (Hattab, 2012). Exploration has revealed insight into different factors influencing female business venture (for example character qualities, age, schooling, inspirations, conjugal status, business attributes, kinds of exercises, government arrangements, monetary assets, socio-social elements, and so forth) Accessible examination to date has assisted shed with lighting on a scope of issues identifying with female business, shifting from what inspires ladies to become business visionaries at the miniature level (for example push and pull factors) to the micro and full scale level limitations they experience, for example, lopsided admittance to capital business sectors and biased systematized cultural qualities in certain specific situations (Naguib and Jamali, 2015).

Recent studies show a tireless hole among people in the degree of enterprising action (Arenius and Minniti, 2005), in innovative direction and affinity (Langowitz and Minniti, 2007) and in the inspiration, want and goal to turn into a business visionary (Minniti and Nardone, 2007). There is additionally proof that the challenges encountered in beginning and working a business varies among male ad females (Neider, 1987). The primary justification the previously mentioned persistent hole is that ladies have become progressively disappointed with the limits society has put on their exercises (Mirjana, 2007). Shockingly, men are even bound to be advanced than a female partner with equivalent experience (Barnes-farrell and Piotrowski, 1991). Be that as it may, notwithstanding all kinds of people being similarly equipped for being acceptable administrators, there are still contrasts between the initiative of male and female chiefs and business visionaries (Mirjana, 2013; Marković, Radović-Markovic and Minović, 2015; Radović-Marković, 2015).

Limitations looked by ladies business visionaries in agricultural nations emerge from gender orientation separation, work-family struggle, trouble in raising capital, absence of framework, unsteady business, monetary and political (BEP) conditions, absence of preparing and schooling and character contrasts. The examination recommends that notwithstanding monetary imperatives, unsteady BEP conditions should be tended to as main concerns. Ladies business is particularly difficult in non-industrial nations on the grounds that such ladies need

openings, are asset compelled and face special difficulties (Panda and Dash, 2014; Verheul, Stel and Thurik, 2006). Adjusting work and day to day life, women claimed organizations are thought inside generally female-composed fields with below business receipts than male-composed fields. Besides, even inside the equivalent mechanical subcategories, ladies proprietors make less financial progress than men proprietors. Albeit a portion of the prompt hindrances looked ladies in the independent venture field, for example, absence of admittance to capital and government contracts-vary from those that stand up to ladies representatives, the hidden causes are comparative e.g. care of male centric social orders and gender orientation separation are only a portion of the novel difficulties confronting females (Panda, 2018).

While there are contrasts as far as characterizing what a SME is according to its size and workforce, it shows the findings that the boundaries SMEs face identifying with setting up and development are comparative all around the world. Kuratko and Hodgets (1995) set up that the vital obstructions for SMEs are opportunity direction; resilience of disappointment; human relations abilities; drive and duty; uprightness and unwavering quality; inner placement of control; specialized skill; high accomplishment drive; and mental capacity. Existing writing recommends that these obstructions have not changed over the most recent 23 years and are addressed worldwide in examinations from the 1990s onwards. For instance (Rahmatullah and Zaman, 2014; Bilal, 2015; Alam Khan *et al.*, 2021; Bilal, 2015) all recognized these issues in their investigations. Notwithstanding, new obstructions have additionally risen up out of their examinations that incorporate political imperatives, absence of foundation, debasement, low usefulness, laws and guidelines, and an absence of clear direction and strategy for the improvement of the area. (Islam *et al.*, 2019). The previous researches show that the intricacies included when constructing the summed-up presumptions about the females' casual miniature business both with respect to persuasive components and the presentation of their organizations. There is no question that the primary challenges which females face in the work market, mostly the ones having less advanced education for instance, age separation and absence of youngster care offices, have a critical effect upon the options ladies make concerning their pay acquiring exercises. Be that as it may, decisive with discoveries from past considerations, "compulsory rejection" from the work market or "destitution" isn't adequate to divulge females' inspiration to enter into the casual miniature business. As demonstrated in different investigations on thought processes in business that female-business persons can settled on the decision to enter miniature business dependent on the normal result for themselves and their families (counting gains in pay, autonomy,

adaptability, time went through with their youngsters and admittance to a sound public activity), out of revenue and through assessing their skills and abilities (Franck, 2012).

This is observed in the United State, that businesses owned by Black ethnic group are 20% more prone to collapse in the first four years the business owned by White people. The reason behind this is that African-Americans do not have an advantage of many generations in their family and have less social connections that can help them in running their business (Kwame Adom, 2016). According to US Census Bureau (2009), due to the gender discrimination, and to overcome the joblessness, Black women starts to engage in the small services sector, for example setting up their beauty salons. Also, Black women have set up their business more quickly in the US even though they have some limiting factors due to the ethnic group they belong to. National Foundation for Business Owners, mentions that in 2004, among all the privately-owned business 50% were owned by women. From 1997 and 2004, there was 9% increase in all the business but the business owned by females increased by 20%, but it was also seen that females does not get much of financial support as compared to males, but the reason for that was that females prefer to get loan from their family and friends rather than to ask for it from investors (Correll, 2004).

Culture spikes pioneering aims and in the long run public beginning up rates. Additionally, a steady climate communicates beneficial innovative mentality and qualities, which draw in individuals to become business people, Mueller and Thomas proposed that if the apparent enterprising worth is high in the general public, the individual will have a more uplifting perspective toward business (Mueller and Thomas, 2001). Gaganis (2019) concurred that some social measurements deals with the critical relationship to the presentation of European Small and Medium Enterprises whereas few of them don't have to show measurements (Gaganis, Pasiouras and Voulgari, 2019). Alternately, Naidu and Chand found that culture is an obstruction to females business visionaries, which demotivates females from turning into a business visionary (Naidu and Chand, 2017). Absence of fit hypothesis additionally upholds the various jobs of ladies inside society. Besides, revolutionary woman's rights have confidence in the achievement of male organizations over females' accomplishment in the public arena. A research done on the female running small business, found that positive impact of connection between family support and the achievement of running business. Support from family members is observed as a possible obstruction in certain nations, like Middle East and South Asia and some Areas of Africa (Tlaiss, 2014). This might be because of the manly idea of the general public, community, or vulnerability aversion (Hofstede, 2016). The uncertain

outcomes give a hole to be filled by future investigations in arising economies. (Shakeel, Yaokuang and Gohar, 2020).

Business is in this way one manner by which females can acquire a nice job for themselves and their families. Regardless of the potential chances emerging from business, the conceivable outcomes are regularly not completely misused. Female business people in the creating scene are seriously failing to meet expectations. Such is the finish of a few investigations which highlight a gender usefulness hole (Aterido, Beck and Iacovone, 2013; Bruhn, 2009; Ronald B. Davies, 2021; Hallward-Driemeier, 2013; Goby and Erogul, 2011). Aside from an efficiency part, contrasted and their male-possessed friends, firms claimed and oversaw by females are typically more modest. In addition, an excessively high number of female business visionaries are situated in lower gifted areas, for example, materials. For African financial specialists to understand the maximum capacity structure business, it is significant to comprehend the drivers of the exhibition hole. Up until now, the reasons set forward for this gender execution are to a great extent narrative, best case scenario, interpretative. Exact clarifications for the presentation hole are inadequate. For nations in Africa, females might confront separation in sourcing finance, in addition to other things (Stöterau, 2019).

The Prince's Trust, was a charity organization in the United Kingdom. This organization was started by the Prince of Wales, and the purpose for this was to support and help youth between the age of 14 and 30. This organization was running the business programs in order to provide them practical and financial support. The programs had the less interest rates and includes development awards and cash awards. This organization was not gender focused but mostly young women and singles moms were mainly benefitted by this organization and they have started their profitable businesses across the country (The Prince's Trust, 2021). Subcultural issues are main barriers and restrictions for a middles class women even though they are well educated but they are taken as unreliable in businesses until they involve their male counterparts in the business especially while dealing with finances and getting loans they need their partners to represent them in order receive any economic support (Danish and Smith, 2012).

Bangladesh, which is one of the poorest nations of the world and education especially for women, is not very common. Gender biasness in setting up a business is very common because women more likely are less educated and business skills are scarce. However, there are several social and working barriers that stop women to set up or run their own business. Asian

Development Bank mentions that gender centered issues seriously effect female entrepreneurs where they have to stick to societal traditions and standards which can also affect them in choosing the business and costing of the business they want to set up as well the maintenance and success of their business (Asaduzzaman, and Kabir, 2015).

2.3 Gap in the research

The literature rarely discusses the ethnicity of female entrepreneurs, despite the fact that study on ethnic entrepreneurship is expanding. According to Jones et al. (2010) and Dhaliwal (2000), ethnic minority females especially those with South Asian ancestry had historically been excluded from academic studies on entrepreneurship. Additionally, there is very little study on FEs in the UK, despite the fact that there are over a million Pakistanis (48% female) residing there and that they are known to be diligent workers with an entrepreneurial mindset (Collins & Fakoussa, 2015). The major causes of the restricted research are the linguistic and cultural limitations that limit access and make it difficult to establish the trust required for more thorough study (Collins & Fakoussa, 2015). Due of this, earlier research has been unable to fully comprehend the function of FEs. Therefore, by incorporating institutional theory, this empirical study adds something significant and novel to the corpus of knowledge and increases the reach of entrepreneurial research.

Females are comprised of 43 percent of the entire workforce in the UK, around 10 million females were working in the UK in which 6 million was a full-time worker and 4.5 million was working part-time (Meager, 1992; Foley, 1992). It was reported in the Labor Force Survey in 1992 that 7 percent of females are working as self-employed, which is almost double the size of the self-employed females in 1979, but less than the 17 percent of self-employed males. In accordance to ethnic groups 26 percent of men were from India and 24 percent were from Pakistan and Bangladesh, from 7 percent of self-employed females, 11 percent of them were from India. Bangladeshi women are at the lowest numbers in self-employment among South Asian females' business owners. In the Midlands, the frequency of self-employment is higher in the minorities groups (Monder Ram, Trevor Jones, 2016). 1 in 5 Chinese females is self-employed as compared to the 1 in 50 African-Caribbean. While in South Asia, especially in Chinese females contributes to a vital basis of paid work (Nathanael Ojong, Amon Simba, 2020).

Mainly the studies conducted on female entrepreneurship were with a small sample size and the presence of the data globally is low. Though the female business persons have hurried up fundamentally into the global entrepreneur competition, the pace of innovative movement for

male members is as yet higher than that of females. Likewise, the organizations run by the females are regularly less fruitful contrasted with male-claimed organizations. By a similar token, minority-claimed organizations have lower bounds of progress than the organizations being run by non-minority community. The progresses of any Business not only rely on the management but also the area matters which are additional part of the system. It has been reported by the As per The State of Women-Owned Businesses in 2017 that the organizations and companies managed by female entrepreneurs are more successful as the availability of their business is in the more populated areas. (Cho, Moon and Bounkhong, 2019).

However, this research concentrating on females entrepreneurs. Mostly research done in small business sector does not take gender in to account as a variable, which may affect the criteria of business development or the experience of the business owner. The absence of academic studies of gender related suggests male dominated attitude which postulates that female's motivations are alike males and they expect same incentives as men. Knowing that owing a business is a profession with which one can generates income. There has been a regrettable gap in the academic research field about the female entrepreneurs and their experience of owing a small business. Recently studies mentions the absence of the data and difficulty in finding exact role of women in entrepreneurship (Carter, S. ; Cannon, 1989).

2.4 Problems Faced by Female Entrepreneurs before COVID and after COVID Situation:

2.4.1 Situation before COVID-19

Female entrepreneurs faced multiple problems which include gender discrimination, lack of support from the government and family. There have been various speculations that attempt to clarify the distinctions in the manners markets treat separated gatherings. One of the principal writers to expound on the issue was Becker (1957), who proposed the taste-based segregation hypothesis. This hypothesis depends on the social convictions and feelings that drive banks' choices. This happens when the individuals who need to support the credit have biases against ladies and along these lines choose not to give them financing, in any event, when it doesn't bode well as far as financial aspects or benefit. Another kind of separation is the thing that is called factual segregation (Phelps, 1972). As per this hypothesis, segment attributes can be associated with unseen qualities of credit, and moneylenders can utilize sexual orientation as an intermediary of financial soundness. This implies that if females will in general be bound to default, banks could apply this normal to each female-drove organization, without get-together explicit data about the borrower and, thusly, hurting the

odds of ladies' business people getting financing. At last, Bertrand et al. (2005) featured a new and more inconspicuous method of segregation. It is considered implied separation and implies that there could be segregation in any event, when the bank would not like to separate. This method of segregation doesn't suggest that moneylenders need to separate, in actuality; they could even need to treat ladies similarly, and however, there are sure implied factors that could influence their choices. In this manner, ladies would be more averse to acquire an advance or credit, not on account of a reasonable assessment but since of accidental guidelines and mentalities not unequivocally communicated.

With regards to the 2008 emergency, a few examinations analyzed how much ladies drove organizations were influenced by the emergency. In the majority of the nations inspected (for example Italy, Finland, Slovakia, or Austria), no huge contrast was found between organizations run by men or ladies. Albeit in Poland, France, and Spain, female-drove organizations were seriously influenced by the emergency (OECD, 2012; Buratti, Cesaroni and Sentuti, 2018).

2.4.2 Situation after COVID-19:

In 2020, the COVID-19 pandemic has represented a double test to countries and economies around the world. Governments need to handle the quick wellbeing difficulties of a worldwide pandemic, and the monetary and government assistance ramifications of pandemic measures and terminations. New companies and little endeavors are among the weakest parts of the economy. The COVID-19 emergency has drastically affected every one of these unique female personalities also. As per an overview among private companies in the USA (Bartik et al., 2020), business visionaries are monetarily delicate in light of the fact that middle organizations (month to month expenses more than \$10,000) had barely sufficient money to keep working for about fourteen days under COVID-19 limitations, while more modest organizations (month to month expenses under \$10,000) just had sufficient money for four. This implies that business people unfit to fund-raise or assume extra obligation might be compelled to slice expenses or even to petition for financial protection.

This pandemic has driven us to a "powerful coincidence" circumstance, as it has likewise affected banks, improving their probability of non-performing credits and monetary misfortunes (Goodell, 2020) and diminishing their affinity to loan cash. Business people face numerous difficulties as they continued looking for financing, for example, recognizing, drawing in, and convincing individuals or associations that can work with admittance to the fundamental monetary assets (Scott, 2000; Shane and Cable, 2002). These financing

specialists, anticipating a profit from their ventures, might be hesitant to expect the dangers intrinsic in another movement particularly when the danger that they are accepting that is higher on account of the COVID-19 monetary vulnerability (Villaseca, Navío-Marco, and Gimeno, 2020). Simultaneously, ladies who run organizations have gotten essentially less consideration, despite the fact that they have been tested in various courses lately. From one perspective, as business people and bosses, they needed to bargain with the limits of epidemiological measures and the going with financial impacts. On the other hand, as ladies and moms, they normally additionally assumed the largest part of family and home care undertakings, like concentrating with youngsters, cooking for the family, or caring for old family individuals (Fodor et al., 2020).

Research done on the effects of a pandemic on female business persons revealed that 79% of the ladies drove organizations were adversely influenced by the monetary emergency. 11% of them detailed that the pandemic and the present circumstance made it incomprehensible for them to keep working their business. 66% of the respondents said that their possibilities had disintegrated to a lesser or more prominent degree, while almost 8% of them accepted that the pandemic had worked on their organizations' openings. 68% accepted that the effect of the pandemic will be felt all through 2020 and that the entire year's incomes would diminish contrasted with last year. Generally speaking, in the nations analyzed female business-people, gauge they could lose about 28% of their yearly pay this year. The greatest income misfortunes were accounted for by Austrian (47%), Andalusian and Bulgarian respondents (32- 31%), and the littlest by Hungarian and Transylvanian Hungarian respondents (22 and 20%). The number of workers of reacting business visionaries diminished by a normal of 10% during the pandemic. Because of severe limitations, female business people confronted a fast diminishing in incomes (62% of respondents), and a drop-in requests and orders (52%). Likewise, the suspension of exercises and production network disturbance had genuine adverse consequences. A few respondents have likewise announced that this could fortify their business over the long haul. 23% had the option to present new items and 14% had the option to grow online deals (Koltai *et al.*, 2020).

2.5 Chapter Summary

The researches cited under this section show that from the last part of the 1930s to around mid-1970s there was a decrease in the quantity of independently employed and few firms in Britain and most mechanical social orders. This pattern switched during the 1980s. The main reasons for the growth of small businesses have been changes in the organizational and sub-

contracting practices of large firms. This growth has continued in the 1990s. In 1992, there were 2.7 firms, 97 percent of which employ fewer than twenty people, so the vast majority of firms are small. Minority ethnic population has also played an important role in the growth of small businesses as it derives a large part of its livelihood from self-employment.

Female self-employment has also increased rapidly during the 1980s. In 1991, about a quarter of the self-employed were females and between 1981 and 1991 their number increased by 81 percent (Daly, 1991). This rise in female entrepreneurship has brought with it a growing literature seeking to explain the phenomenon. Various accounts are offered of the entrepreneurial background and profile (Carter S., 1989; Curran James, 1988; Watkins, J. M. and Watkins, 1983; Allen, S., and Truman, 1993; Johnson, 1993) personality characteristics (Chell, 1986; Fortenberry, 1988), business performance and the problems faced by them (Kelmar, J.H, 1990).

The picture which results from these findings is mixed and cannot be described as conclusive and also provides little information about some issues like, management practices, trading profile, family support systems, the constraints faced and the performances of the businesses run by these females. This reflects a need for further investigation on the above underdeveloped issues. An analysis of the LFS data Employment Gazette, 1994 shows that a higher proportion of Asian men and women are self-employed as compared to either white or black groups. There has, however, been little research on this group and the few researches that have been conducted have concentrated upon the male entrepreneurs (Aldrich *et al.*, 1986; Aldrich, 1990; Curran and Jarvis, Robin, and Blackburn, 1993). There has been, to the author's knowledge, no work on the South Asian female entrepreneurs in the UK. These issues provide a reasonable basis upon which to undertake comparisons between South Asian and Black Caribbean female entrepreneurs and their businesses.

This research attempts to fill the gaps in our knowledge by utilizing a data (collected through personal interviews) on South Asian and Black Caribbean female owned businesses and examining the nature of their businesses, their demographic profile, business characteristics, entrepreneurial background, family support systems, socio-economic constraints and their business performance.

Chapter 3: Discussion

In this chapter a detailed discussion of the topic is done with the help of different theories, frameworks and concepts. Entrepreneurship is explained in detail in terms of Institutional theory. Further, regulative, normative and cognitive institutions are also discussed in detail. How entrepreneurial process is relates to these institutions is also discussed. What are the social expectation with the FE's, entrepreneurship compared to time is also discussed.

3.1 Entrepreneurship in terms of “Institutional Theory”

“Institutional theory” is profoundly concerned with social structure. It looks at how structures such as “schemes”, “patterns”, “norms”, “rules”, “and routines” are founded as commanding rules for “social behavior” (Scott, 2008). Lawrence and Suddaby (2006), “Institutional theory” is a “theoretical framework” of examining “Social Phenomena” which sees social environment as largely composed of “institutions”.

“There is no single and universally agreed definition of an 'institution' in the institutional school of thought” (Scott, 1995, 2001). Giddens (1984), Institutions are said permanent components of societal life, providing stability to “social systems” across space & time. Zucker (1977), said they passed down through generation are retained & replicated, evolve as time passes. The involvement of these “institutions in channeling the process of entrepreneurship has been highlighted through research (Baumol 1990; North, 1990; Scott, 1995; Wright et al., 2005). Roles and boundaries are defined by these institutions encouraging a behavior and actions & building social behavior predictable (Krasner, 1988; North, 1990; Scott, 1995). Individuals and organizations engage with this institutional framework.

“Formal and Informal institutions” established by North (1990), “Formal institutions” involve “political”, “economic”, & “legal institutions”, whilst “Informal institutions” pertain deeply embedded cultural standards, codes & values of behavior. Institutions either facilitate or confine entrepreneurship. As per Welter (2005), while “formal institutions” can be altered, modifying “informal institutions” is challenging & time-consuming process because of “cultural inheritance”, “specific historical experiences” and “path dependency”. This "path-dependence can and will produce a wide range of patterns of development, depending on [each] country's cultural heritage and specific historical experience" (North 1997, p. 17). Which is why, even if all entrepreneur from ethnic cultures in the United Kingdom, follow the very same formal rules, their performance will vary greatly due to cultural differences.

In contrast, Scott (1995, 2008) presented a famous “institutional frameworks” of “three pillars” in defining the function of these institutions towards the advancement of

entrepreneurship process, which asserts that institutions are largely made up of normative, cultural-cognitive and institutions that, together along with affiliated resources and activities offer steadiness & purpose to societal Life. Institutions rely at various compliance bases, use different mechanisms, elicit different logics of activity, utilize various indicators, and provide distinctive legitimacy bases. Whereas each institution is unique in its own right, many institutional forms involve different patterns of components from “three institutions” rather than individual features of institutions in FEs business (Scott, 2008). Each of “three institutions” have both informal & formal features.

A visible aspect of the situation is the “Regulative institutions”, while the hidden feature is the “Normative factors”. “Regulative institution” focuses towards “rule-setting”, sanctioning & monitoring actions, “informal and formal”, whereas “cultural-cognitive institution” focuses on “*common schemas*”, “frameworks”, and several mutual representative which guides the behavior (Scott, 1995); then accepted as approaches to doing things.

The “normative” component comprises of values & norms that flow via “institutions” and serve as a basis for its personality, ethics or individuality. These provide examples of appropriate behavior and performance. Cultural cognition and normative institutions, in my opinion, do not differ significantly. As normative institutions, I will consider the two together.

3.1.1 Regulative Institutions

The entrepreneurial process is likely to be fundamentally impacted by elements such as regulative aspects of environment and forces of the market, like policies and laws introduced by government impacting the businesses, according to theorists who value the “regulative dimensions of institutions” (e.g. Barnett & Carroll, 1995). They typically concentrate on explicit regulatory processes such activities that involve creating laws or rules, monitoring, and restraints. Political, economic, and judicial institutions and rules are among them. Regulatory institutions are formal, legally binding, and compliant with regulations. The ability to establish rules, monitor adherence of the rules, if necessary, govern behavior via prize or penalty—“positive or negative reinforcement”—are all considered regulatory processes under this view. These punishment procedures may be carried out informally (via behaviors like boycotting and shame) or extremely formally (tagged to specialized actors such as the judiciary and police). In this context, it is important to note that normative and

cultural-cognitive elements can significantly affect whether laws and legislation have the desired impact.

Government policies including “tax”, “social security”, “labor market”, and “financial resource policies” are examples of regulatory factors. These policies may have an impact on a business venture's entry and exit considerations. Although the regulatory institutions that govern the business environment should be the same for all entrepreneurs in the UK, this is not often the case due to cognitive and normative reasons. The study reveals that these aspects of taxation, company rules, and labour laws were the same in all of the situations. However, it is commonly found that business regulations, taxation and finances are always for a man in the house to trade with them otherwise this side is left unattended.

3.1.2 Cognitive Institutions

“Cognitive theorists” emphasize influence the ideas and understandings of mutual senses while a person is going through process of entrepreneurship (e.g. Powell & DiMaggio 1991; Stubbart & Porac 1996; Fiol 2002). We must evaluate that in these scenario and circumstances & person’s understanding in those conditions in order to comprehend a behavior. Interaction produces meanings that are then preserved and changed as they are applied to the interpretation of new circumstances. This institution-building component highlights the critical role that socially mediated composition plays in the creation of a shared meanings schema (Scott, 2004). According to this theory, the more rigid and congealed cultural structures is not required a high standards in upkeep via customs strengthening & elaborate representational meanings, for example societal responsibilities (Jepperson & Swidler 1994).

Social roles are seen differently by cultural theorists than by normative theorists. They place more emphasis on the effectiveness of templates for certain actor types and action scripts than they do on mutually reinforcing obligations (Shank & Abelson 1977). By linking specific activities with specific actors through public understanding, roles—such as what a female in comparison to a male in a society is supposed to do—emerge (Berger & Luckmann, 1967). Who adhere to standard action script and template may experience a sense of community, while those who do not may encounter hostility. According to Scott, "The emotive dimension of this pillar is expressed in sensations from the good influence of certitude and confidence on the one hand vs the bad feelings of uncertainty or disorientation on the other."

They might offer a more comprehensive “cultural framework” which affects personal ideas, and person understandings might functions reshape various principle regularities. In contrast to their colleagues who are white British women, ethnic female entrepreneurs must cross a

double route. I have dealt with all the additional, stronger ethnics aspects and components in this study that were at play.

The degree of institutionalization, or the degree to which cultural aspects are woven into routines and structures, varies (Scott, 2001). Particularly during times of societal transition and disorder, cultural ideas frequently shift and are challenged (Swidler 1986; DiMaggio 1997; Martin 1992; 2002; Seo & Creed 2002). This organization focuses on the daily cultural reality of the business journey. Scott (2008) writes, “*The cognitive dimensions of human existence: mediating between the external world of stimuli and the response of individual is a collection of internalized symbolic representations of the world*”.

3.1.3 Normative Institutions

An uncoded attitudes and beliefs that are ingrained in a society and serve to provide appropriateness are of importance to the normative institution (Welter et al., 2003 and Scott, 1995). When normative standards and expectations are upheld, they become broadly accepted and take on the role of rules in society (Covaleski & Dirsmith, 1988). People adopt these principles as their own and abide by their limitations. The normative systems are made up of values, which are the benchmarks against which actions can be measured and evaluated, such as aims and objectives for financial gain. According to Blake & Davis (1964), “Normative systems” do possess standards which instructs in what way to conduct ourselves and specify the proper approaches to attain those aims and objectives, for instance, the notion of fair business procedures and game rules. These normative components may have an impact on how much society values female entrepreneurs and their business initiatives, and how this affects how female entrepreneurs go about starting their own businesses.

Some rules, principles, and codes of conduct apply to all members as a whole, while others are specific to particular roles or job descriptions. When norms and values are applied to specific people or positions, such as notions of appropriate aims and activities for specific people or social positions, roles are created. Roles may be explicitly created, or they may grow over time through contact, differing expectations, or the development of guidelines for behavior (Blau & Scott 1962/2003). For instance, South Asian societal structures, males and females have various levels of access to material resources as well as varied privileges and duties. In addition to placing restrictions on social activity (via obligations, mandates, and responsibilities), normative systems also empower and permit social action (through rights, privileges, and licences).

We are aware that institutions change gradually and drastically even if their main function is to maintain stability and order. Therefore, institutions should be investigated as both a process and as a condition of an existing social order, including both the institutionalisation and deinstitutionalization processes (Tolbert & Zucker, 1996). Researchers are paying more attention to how institutions evolve than just how they form and are maintained. Change is largely sparked by internal processes, such as disagreements and conversations between institutional components. However, exogenous forces like war or economic crises can also cause institutions to become unstable.

3.1.4 Entrepreneurial Process and Institution's Impact

That's possible to draw the conclusion that, within Scott's institutional framework, "Normative and regulatory institutions" complements one another in symbiotic styles, with different variables taking center stage as time and circumstances change. Different ethnic groups are influenced by regulative and normative influences in different ways (Fregetto, 2004). Additionally, studies on gender-related topics by Aldrich and Cliff (2003) and Elam et al. (2010) imply the milieu in which generally entrepreneurs but particularly FEs are entrenched influences their success ("cultural", "political" or "family").

"Normative" components (Scott, 1995) otherwise "Informal institutions" (North, 1990), unwritten regulations that specify what roles are appropriate for members of a social group and have an impact on their behavior. These characteristics not only affect the viability of business within an ethnic community but also, sometimes unintentionally, the availability of resources. As was mentioned in the previous section, this research demonstrates that traditional South Asian and Black Caribbean ethnic standards, for instance "family", serve as main source for South Asian and Black Caribbean female entrepreneurs, giving them simple approach to finance in order to setup businesses, and a group of devoted members of the family to work for them.

Scott (1995, 2008) claimed that culture, social structure, and routines are some of the aspects that influence how institutions are ingrained. In contrast to cultural norms, or the concept of "social stratification", which comprises on the structured prospects encoded in role systems, cultures comprise attitudes, values, limits, and normative expectations. These influences have an impact on female entrepreneurs' entrepreneurial processes, such as their "choice of business" endeavours (Baughn et al., 2006). According to Mitra and Rauf's (2011) study, a potential motives for South Asian or Black Caribbean woman to choose a less income

business in order to keep it easy for her so that she will be able to demonstrate her abilities as a decent wife, responsible mother, and humble daughter. Some countries, including Pakistani society, still firmly connect women's roles with raising families, looking after children, and managing the home. Although if they work same amount of hour as their male partner, the female spouse is nonetheless responsible for looking after dependent parents, kids, and elderly relatives (Marlow, 2002; Greer & Greene, 2003). This makes juggling household and professional responsibilities more challenging (Gilbert, 1997). Because of this intricacy, they could be more inclined to choose businesses that let them choose their own working hours.

3.1.4.1 Social Expectations

Social norms prohibit some activities for women and judge them unsuitable, particularly when the sources are able to follow back to the male line “Patrilineage” when woman lives with otherwise is close to her spouse’s or parent’s group “Patrilocality” (Coltrane, 1992; Kantor, 2002; Welter et al., 2003; Emrich et al., 2004). Group relationships happen to believed that both impose constraints on individuals and open up opportunities for their activity.

Entrepreneurs are frequently characterized as assertive, courageous, and risk-takers. In various communities, such as South Asian and Black Caribbean society, these traits are linked to masculinity (Marlow, 2002; Ahl, 2003). Female entrepreneurs face limitations as a result of this entrepreneurship stereotype, which may also affect how they interact with other business stakeholders such as investors, suppliers, and potential clients.

3.1.4.2 Social Pyramids (Hierarchies)

Proved that severe prejudice, against FEs is contradictory (Carter & Brush, 2004). But for a while, women have endured rudeness and casual behaviour toward them, which is a barrier to starting a business. Their attitude and potential as entrepreneurs would be affected if they feel inferior to their male counterparts (Achtenhagen & Welter, 2003). The social dominance hypothesis can be used to explain these social hierarchies and the patriarchy phenomena. Societies may continue to exist in a way of grouped supremacy orders, where however, single “socially constructed group” is much powerful as compare to other, such as the patriarchal system where men are viewed as superior to women and adults as superior to infants (Pratto et al., 2013). Lawful procedures, either transcribed or proclaimed through authorities, place individuals in groups, such as a person before the law as a father or a landowner. These “social categories”, such as “gender” and “age”, are produced by “Institutions” and related to the control (Kane, 2012).

Additionally, it enforces people's opportunities and limitations. According to social dominance theory, people become accustomed to group-based hierarchies as a result of being embedded in them, such as patriarchy in their families or ethnic biasness within communities (Lee et al., 2007).

3.1.4.3 FEs and their Household

Homes or family have equally beneficial & bad effects in female's life, who run their own businesses. An impact of the household in business decisions has reportedly been little studied by entrepreneurship experts, according to Alsos et al. (2014). The study of sociology and anthropology, however, has given researchers in-depth knowledge and understanding of the dynamics of households. This is seen as a crucial platform for both intangible and tangible resources, in addition to its function in identifying chances for both new and established companies.

According to the research, families have a significant impact on entrepreneurial choices. In corporate planning and strategy, consideration is paid to both family viewpoints and approaches. The household is "the smallest social unit where human and economic resources are controlled," according to Wheelock and Oughton (1996). A context in which "Normative elements" ("values", "affect", "expectations", "support", and "altruism") and practical reasons (economy) co-occur makes for an interesting review of entrepreneurship (Brannon et al., 2013). The home and the workplace are intertwined. Both domestic and commercial decisions are made there, and household and business strategy are intertwined. Therefore, decisions about starting a business or growing an existing one will significantly affect home strategy.

Women occasionally start small businesses as a coping mechanism to co-locate their work and domestic duties. However, this can jeopardize the company's ability to grow or its overall performance. For many business owners, success might have different meanings. For some FEs, it can entail striking a balance between their entrepreneurial endeavor and domestic responsibilities. Success can't always be gauged in financial profit. According to Williams' (2008) research, self-employment can permit for extra time with family because of its flexibility, but it is also inversely correlated with accomplishment.

Alsos et al., (2012) mentions, family members may feel that a business should be started in order to offer employment or income prospects by utilizing available resources inside the family. The goal of their research was to establish how household dynamics and resources played a part in the relationship between company and household. There are numerous

benefits for the home in the entrepreneurial process (Stewart, 2003). These include access to existing clients, financial resources, free housing, social networks, and assistance from others. Family's involvements as a labour and capital "*tangible resources*", moral and emotive support & advice related to business "*intangible resources*" have been extensively studied (Renzulli et al., 2000; and Brush et al., 2004). Furthermore, Brush and Manilova (2004), talked about "race and ethnicity" have an impact on the availability of finance for new businesses. The amount of money that family is investing in newly setup business endeavor also depends on the economic situation of the household (Gentry & Hubbard, 2004).

Pratto et al., (2003), stated that in cultural and institutions processes, both of which transmit behavior outline and with time, ideas too, location, and specific persons, are responsible for the cohesion of societies. This was demonstrated in section above, standards do have some influence on individuals and also absorbed society's members as regulations during the socialization process. According to Meyer (2007), people not only adhere to these standards but also help to develop them. This connection between agency and structure will be examined in the section that follows.

3.2 Interplay of the Agency and Structure

Barley and Tolbert's (1997) understanding of agency "embraces the idea that observable patterns of social action are associated with relational networks (interactional order) that link to larger (trans-contextual) patterns of institutions and institutional change," in line with Emirbayer and Mische's (1998) analysis of agency. Since its inception, institutional theory has viewed "institutions" at the same time results from and restrain societal activity (Barley & Tolbert, 1997). To put it another way, agency and structure interplay with one another. As a result, FEs have an impact on institutions in addition to through their own economic operations, successes, and experience. FEs can have an impact on normative and regulatory institutions through accumulating human capital in the form of education, training, and experience. Entrepreneurship "is not simply influenced by institutions But entrepreneurs frequently help change institutions themselves," claim Henrekson and Sanandaji (2011). Through the interaction of roles, person as budding businesswomen are "accepted", "rejected", "enhanced", or socially determined. This section examines reciprocal and two-way interactions between institutions and business owners.

The majority of institutional study focuses on how institutions influence conduct and distinguish between acceptable and undesirable behaviour by establishing moral, legal, and ethnic restrictions. According to Scott (2014), institutions offer incentives, rules, and sources

for working, but also limitations & restrictions on activity. “Institutions” have complicated effects on people/actors in a variety of ways, from realism to phenomenological frameworks. On the pragmatic side, institutional institutions may have an impact on people by coercive (forceful) means, such as state legal acts. Normative controls over people, like the impact of a code of practise, are in the middle. The settings set standards that people copy at the phenomenological level, such as accepted standards. Ethnic and gender limits are occasionally created for females by these “environmental standards” through “social expectations”, which FEs must navigate through entire journey of entrepreneurship.

“Institutional” structures depend heavily on the institutional parts since they have characteristics that aid in maintaining and creating meaning. They also include related actions and material resources (Scott, 2014). Resources, both human and material, should be taken into account in any idea of social organization in order to take the imbalance of power into account. Rules and norms need to be reinforced by authority and status in order to be effective. For instance, to be viable, cultural beliefs, or "schemas," should narrate it and stated in sources (Giddens, 1984; Sewell, 1992). Similarly, people who hold authority through a surplus of riches want approval and legitimacy for their usage. *“Schemas not empowered or regenerated by resources would eventually be abandoned and forgotten, just as resources without cultural schemas to direct their use would eventually dissipate and decay”* (Sewell, 1992). This is a crucial point because I want to investigate how FEs' entrepreneurial experiences affect how strongly normative institutions influence them.

When examining institutional components, it's important to consider the processes involved in their creation, modification, and maintenance as well as the resources that support them. Hallett et al., (2006) claim that institutions are valuable symbol, however we are not able to overlook the fact that individuals and their relationships enmeshed in institutions. So interactions produce rules, norms, and meanings, which human activity both preserves and modifies (Geertz, 1973; Berger and Luckmann, 1967; Scott, 2004).

Social ideas and norms that are internalized and imposed by others are stabilized by normative institutions (Parsons, 1990). “Normative institutions” have cultural underpinnings, but in order to achieve the desired stage of conformance, actors must be more instrumental and committed (Selznick, 1957; Stinchcombe, 1997; Hecllo, 2008). The interaction between an institution's "appropriateness" and agency or "instrumentality" is crucial, according to research on normative institutions.

In contrast to regulative institutions, normative institutions do not enforce their standards or norms of conduct by coercion. Contravening normative systems, on the other hand, can also arouse intense emotions; breaking rules and laws does not constitute this. This means that if someone behave admirably and adhere to the rules, you will be respected and honored; yet, if someone does not, you may experience feelings of humiliation and disgrace. You would evaluate yourself, which can leave you with feelings of intense regret or poor self-respect. These feelings compel you to follow social conventions.

Various researchers have explored and discussed the activity of FEs and their influence on “institutions”. Henrekson and Sanandaji (2011) suggest entrepreneurs do this through:

“Abiding” - Entrepreneurs abiding by present “institutions” sometimes is upsetting in order to dispute the grounds of usual “institutions”,

“Evading” – Sometime entrepreneurs are able to avoid these “institutions”, who have a habit of undermining the value of the “institutions”, may change the “institutions” for betterment,

“Altering” – by using inventive political entrepreneurship, they are able to alter “institutions”.

Female entrepreneurs, may adhere to cultural discrimination and rule on gender and are able to evade those rules by rebelling in opposition to them. In order to alter them, they might have to challenge the authorities who are deciding on their behalf.

Human agency is defined by Emirbayer and Mische (1998) as "the temporally constructed engagement by actors of different structural environments—the temporal- relational contexts of action—which, through the interaction of habit, imagination, and judgement, both reproduces and transforms those structures in interactive response to the issues posed by changing historical situations." As a result, a concept of “individual agency” is rendered richly, complicated, time-context-dependent. It’s also shaped & impacted by “culture”, “social stratification”, “interpersonal interactions” (Abdelnour et al., 2017). Researchers like Garud et al., (2007) emphasized the idea that institutions enable action by using this definition. There are some theorists that hold the view that institutional variables restrain and enable actors, such as Emirbayer and Mische (1998). The entrepreneurial process is taken into consideration in the following section before analyzing the temporal dimensions since the interaction of “agency and structure” and process of entrepreneurship might be considered in terms of time.

3.3 Processes of Entrepreneurship

According to Butler (2006), an entrepreneur is a person who adopts original thinking, turns those ideas into actual enterprises, and then harvests business chances to make money using inventive, creative, leadership, and risk-taking qualities. In addition, according to Burns (2011), entrepreneurs are creative thinkers who exploit change to spur prospects for wealth creation. Entrepreneurship is seizing a chance exclusive of ownership of an available sources (Stevenson and Jarillo, 1990), McMullen and Shepherd (2006: p.132) say, "*To be an entrepreneur, therefore, is to act on the possibility that one has identified an opportunity worth pursuing*". These definitions make this very evident that acting is essential. This study demonstrates that the interviewed entrepreneurs, were not able to wait for approval, to determine available economical sources before acting to launch a new business.

It also demonstrated that these entrepreneurs favored turning a concept into a workable firm through action rather than just coming up with lots of ideas. This is reasonable to presume that starting an enterprise endeavor hold a procedure if entrepreneurship needs action; that is, it necessitates passing through many stages before a new enterprise is founded. Another way to examine the actions involved in entrepreneurship is to take a process-oriented perspective to it. (2012) Kuratko The entrepreneurial process has been modelled and organized by numerous scholars, including Levie and Lichtenstein and Morris, Lewis, and Sexton (1994). The majority of these approaches make an effort to characterize the entrepreneurial process as a synthesis of many elements. The forced which obstruct the development of something new can be disabled, the majority of the models suggest that there is a process through which an entrepreneurs goes through such as "identifying", "locating", "developing", and "evaluating an opportunity". An entrepreneurial process entails opportunity identification and assessment, business plan preparation, resource decision, and organization of a new business. The next entrepreneurship level is an idea or concept of the new business, incident that activates the running, execution, and progress were developed by Bygrave (2004) based on Moore's model.

The major elements that affect each level of business development are depicted in the model below. Bygrave (2004) emphasizes the significance of recognizing and comprehending the character qualities which might contribute to their achievements, refers to these attributes as "*The 10 Ds: dream, decisiveness, doers, determination, commitment, devotion, details, destiny, dollars, and distribution*".

Figure 1 - A model of the Entrepreneurship Process (Based on Carol Moore's Model)

In combination to individual characteristics, environmental elements (economic, institutional, social, and cultural features) have an impact on the entrepreneurial process at various levels of an enterprise, as depicted above (Bygrave, 2004). Given that they comprise “cultural values” and “norms” on one side, & governmental laws & corporate rules on other side, the environmental variables can be divided into normative and regulative institutions. In this research, it has been determined how early in the idea creation process, an entrepreneur's locus of control, vision, tolerance for uncertainty, education, personal values, risk-taking, and experience all have an impact. The initial decision to launch a business may also be influenced by institutions (both normative and regulative), sociological, and cultural-environmental variables, as well as considerations like work unhappiness or redundancy coupled (push and pull forces).

The degree and influence of the entrepreneur's personal characteristics and environmental elements change as they progress through the entrepreneurial process. At the implementation to growth stages, for instance, a new set of characteristics, such as “vision”, “leadership”, “entrepreneurial spirit”, “management aptitude”, & “commitment”, may have a significant impact. This study demonstrates how FEs utilized their strong personal traits to go around

some obstacles and take advantage of chances that they encountered at various phases. The environment, though, sometimes determined their course.

Where business opportunities come from has been a hot topic in entrepreneurial study. Some people argue that opportunities are "identified" through logical information search and analysis processes (Caplan, 1999). Others contend that people who are conscious of their options are the ones who 'find' opportunities (Kirzner, 1997). According to a recent argument, opportunities are "made" through abductive processes (Saravathy et al., 2011). The 3 unique method of prospect represent various presumptions are reliant on various circumstances. The fact that an individual entrepreneur identifies, recognizes, discovers, or generates possibilities is a common thread among all three hypotheses.

Additionally, it is believed that businesspeople with prior knowledge or exposure to the industry are more adept at seeing chances. Therefore, individuals who are raised in business familiar families are more prepared as new entrepreneurship opportunities arise. Additionally, studies have shown that older family members play a significant role in looking for opportunities, sometimes serving as succession plans or role models. But, disagreements and divergent viewpoints can exist within business families as a result of personal objectives (Steier et al., 2009).

There will be different levels of dedication to the company among South Asian households, who might have in-laws, different generations, or own family (sometimes residing in the same home). Due to mistrust and disengagement among family members, this can occasionally be damaging and limiting for opportunity identification. However, these differences may also be fruitful, with some family members starting new companies as a sub-team (Schjoedt et al., 2012; Discua Cruz et al., 2012).

Irrespective of if these phases take place sequentially, according to Carter et al. (1996) and Kim et al. (2015), a businessperson may launch their businesses using a variety of procedures. They must follow specific actions to launch a company venture, and these stages take place over time (Pettigrew, 1997). While few entrepreneurial endeavors require to develop while others get off to a fast start (Baker et al., 2003). As a result, we can describe a "process" as a "series of events", "deeds", and "activities" that take place across time. This description of "process" conceals the characteristics of "temporal transition", or the idea of studying "processes" takes place across time. The need of exploring the notions of the "temporal dimension" in research are also underlined at a few places during writings in order to understand the process of entrepreneurship (Aldrich, 2015; Naldi & Davidsson, 2014).

Therefore, I have included the “impact of time” on the “entrepreneurial process” in this study as well.

3.4 Time & Entrepreneurship

Numerous experts have claimed that time is an essential element in the “entrepreneurial process”. Individual’s activity is also a temporal and contextual concept, as was mentioned in the previous section. According to Ancona et al. (2001) and Langley (1999), time offers a crucial agenda for deciphering & understanding entrepreneurship. Additionally, according to Hammersley and Atkinson (1998), time is a crucial element in many activities, including those in entrepreneurship.

3.4.1 Subjective VS. Objective Time

Time is complicated and may be consider as “Objective” or “Clock-based”, “linear and irreversible”, “incorporating cyclical events”, and “subjective”, and “event-based”.

3.4.1.1 Linear/Objective/ Clock Time

According to Ruef (2005), it is generally believed that “entrepreneurial processes” progress smoothly over “time”, with distinct phases that begin, middle, and conclude. This perspective is known as a “linear concept of time”. For instance, Western business owners and managers use this idea of time to plan ahead and reflect on their past performance to develop estimations and projections, which help them predict their earnings. Their estimations and budgets consider their prior performance. Countries like the USA and Europe frequently use this strategy to manage their time effectively. Regulatory organizations, particularly financial institutions like UK banks, typically base their judgments on objective time. For instance, in order to obtain a loan for future results, FEs may need to demonstrate their credit history and previous performance. Many other financial structures that have an impact on commercial activity, such taxation and company insurances, and dependable on “linear time”.

3.4.1.2 Subjective Time

“Time” can be considered as “socially constructed”, so different civilizations have varied ideas about what it means. Here, time is a multidimensional, socially created, and subjective phenomena that significantly affects how we experience life.

Time also moves at various speeds depending on the geography, economy, or industry (Plakoyiannaki & Saren, 2006). For instance, entrepreneurs in start-up enterprises face more time constraints that they might be well-known organization. “Time” constraints are usual

for FEs since they must balance a variety of obligations, such as socially imposed gender-related expectations and their professional obligations.

Since we have different perspectives on the “past, present, and future, time” is not linear (Nuttin, 1985; Bluedorn, 2022). That is, even if time only moves in one direction, we are able to move backwards and forward among “settled past” and “shadowy assumptions of what lies ahead” (Murray, 1938, p. 49; Wheeler et al., 1997). This serves as an example of how subjective time differs from “objective time” (Bluedorn & Denhardt, 1988; George & Jones, 2005).

3.4.2 Time Focus

Because different temporal foci have an impact on people's present “attitudes”, “decisions”, and “behaviors”, as shown by study on “motivation”, “performance management” (Fried & Slowik, 2004; Bandura, 2001; Nuttin, 1985; Cottle, 1976), and “strategic choice” (Bird, 1988; Hambrick & Mason, 1984; Das, 1987), it is crucial to comprehend them to examine the entrepreneurial journey of FEs in the “institutional context.” Focusing on the past, for instance, can improve learning when you examine your prior acts and draw lessons from them, but it can have a detrimental impact if all you think about are your failures and remorse from the past (Sanna et al., 2003, Holman & Silver, 2005). Focusing on the present can be beneficial if it makes it easier to take advantage of opportunities, but it can also be detrimental if businesspeople impulsive & evasive regarding effects of their actions (Zimbardo et al., 1997; Zimbardo & Boyd, 1999). A person who is future-oriented may work toward accomplishing predetermined goals, which could lead to anxiety because of the strain to do so (Zimbardo & Boyd, 1999; Bandura, 2001; Fried & Slowik, 2004).

If we consider the inclination of entrepreneurs to take risks and tolerate uncertain results, or their risk-taking temperament (Stewart & Roth, 2001), For example, individuals might incur financial risks now in exchange for rewards later on. We are able to say that “risk-taking” has “current temporal” emphasis and a “future temporal” emphasis, since a “risk-taker” assesses potential future outcomes while acting in the present. We may claim that “risk-taking” is powerfully associated with “current” emphasis and “future” emphasis, but thrill-seeking, where people concentrate on maximizing their current experiences, may also be a component of risk-taking (Jackson et al., 1972).

Focus of attention is the best way to describe how people can change their temporal focus within this temporal profile (Shipp et al., 2009). It is hypothesized that people have some control over how much attention they pay to different targets (Gardner et al., 1987 and

1989). People must concentrate on specific things (such as their business goals) and aspects that cause them to have a robust “positive or “negative affective reaction” because of the demands of their roles. According to research on attentional emphasis, people can shift their attention between “job”, “family”, and “personal targets” during the day, motivations from the outside world can temporarily favor some goals (Gardner et al., 1989). For instance, if a significant loss was experienced in the most recent quarter, the entrepreneur would turn their attention there. Research on attention focus, however, stresses that people acquire a recognizable pattern of attention allocation in which they prioritize focusing on some items over others, going beyond these transient swings (Gardner et al., 1987).

During people's formative years, their general, stable temporal focus develops as a result of their “early experiences”, “upbringing”, “national culture”, “social standing”, and “parental attitudes” about “time” (Trommsdorff, 1983; McGrath & Tschan, 2004). A person's concentration on the past, for instance, may be influenced by the national culture, like in Asian cultures where traditions and values are valued but the family prioritizes the future by placing a high value on planning and achievement (Ji, et al., 2009). In a typical situation, this would be the case, but things like schooling, the type of job one has, and other experiences in life could cause this to change. According to recent research, the 9/11 terrorist attacks had an impact on people's attention to the future, which led to a modest decline in future concentration after the incident (Holman & Silver, 2005).

3.4.3 Monochronic VS Polychronic

This is based on Hall & Hall's (1990) theory of polychronic versus monochronic time orientation. In contrast to polychronic cultures, where people are more adaptable and priorities relationships with others over rigorously regulating time, monochronic ethnicities are the one in which people concentrate on single thing on one time, operate in a “linear manner”, priorities duties than individuals. People organize their labour in a polychronic way in South Asian and Black Caribbean cultures. In Pakistani society, family requirements are prioritized over economic needs. Thus, everything else—including business—must wait when immediate family members request something be done. Another reason why FEs are more affected than their white counterparts by normative institutions is because of this. The idea of "Naseeb" or "karma" also rules over religious and philosophic ideas in South Asian culture.

Space & competition are two additional qualities that are related to time focus; a strongly monochronic culture that operates systematically is likely to protect its personal space and be individualistic in attitude. However, polychronic societies are more likely to exhibit the same adaptability and openness toward space as they do toward time, as well as to be more focused on the group as a whole (Collins et al., 2015).. Due to this aspect, FEs in this study may effected by another time constraints as compare to male partners. They would priorities their immediate family and household duties according to social expectations. For instance, it is their duty to care for a sick family member even if doing so necessitates stopping or drastically slowing the expansion of their firm.

3.4.4 Time Orientation

People who are primarily focused on the past, present, or future are said to be time/temporal oriented (Shipp et al., 2009). Ethnic preference for time, demonstrates in what way people give importance to time and in what way they think they have influence over it. When contrasted with countries like United States of America - future-adapted, civilizations with a lengthy past like “India”, “China”, and “Britain” are frequently past-adapte. Future-focused individuals lead a hurried existence, keeping an eye on the time while working hard to realize their goals. On the other hand, time is treated much more laxly in past-focused civilizations like those of Pakistan, Bangladesh, and India.

3.4.5 Event Time

Events take place as a result of a constant interaction between institutions like household/family culture and entrepreneurial actions. These incidents can be used as analytical building blocks to track changes to the entrepreneurial process. Events are cases where alterations are seen to occur in the “temporal dimensions”, according to Abrams (1982). The research of “entrepreneurial process” is concerned with “process” closely related elements, including as “input and output events and human agency”. Event timing offers a different viewpoint on what is causing rapid alterations in the network of entrepreneurship (Gersick, 1991).

As an illustration, first step of the “entrepreneurial process” creates “market knowledge”, which is then utilized as an “input” to create company processes and produce goods and services.

The study to date has mostly concentrated on the alterations as changing and slow stages that take place when network participants' socialisation process happens in order to understand the dynamics of social and corporate networks. However, contemporary business environment dynamics, such as waves of vertical or horizontal integration and cooperation, demonstrate transformation in “business networks” may be upsetting and revolutionary. As a result, there is a shift in emphasis from the linear and chronological sense of time to temporal concepts like event time (Halinen et al., 1999).

The context of an event offers a different viewpoint on what motivates radical transformation in an entrepreneurial process (Gersick, 1991). Event timing affects how female entrepreneurs migrate toward empowerment and agency, for instance through marriage, parenthood, education, and experience. Due to abrupt changes in government regulations, FEs have occasionally had to shut down their operations.

3.5 Chapter Summary

The terms "entrepreneurship" and "entrepreneur" have been introduced in this chapter. Following a brief introduction to these terminology, the chapter goes on to highlight significant research findings as well as the intricate and multifaceted facets of entrepreneurship. Key difficulties and limitations in the field of research have been found through this assessment of seminal research literature. The scant research on female ethnic entrepreneurs in the UK, especially FEs, has been identified as one of the significant knowledge gaps by this evaluation.

The contributions of many academic disciplines to the literature on entrepreneurship have led to a diversity of viewpoints, but they have also made it possible to emphasize the various facets of “entrepreneurship” via various academic disciplines. Others view entrepreneurship as a phenomena that occurs in unique social contexts and benefits society as a whole. For some, entrepreneurship is financial agency conducted to support fiscal development. Some believe that innovation and the development of something new go hand in hand, and that the visions and skills of a particular entrepreneur are what lead to these inventive actions. Entrepreneurship theories were thoroughly reviewed. Each theory of entrepreneurship reviewed in the chapter focuses on a different component of this complex phenomena and advances knowledge of its dynamic character.

The debate also demonstrates the three categories that make up entrepreneurship literature: the person entrepreneur, the environment, and interplay of the two constantly growing “process”. These three viewpoints are in line with the "what," "why," and "how" of entrepreneurship as a topic of study, according to Stevenson and Jarillo (2007). The "what" inquiry, such as "What occurs when entrepreneurs act," is focused on new value creation and asks about the outcomes of entrepreneurial activities. It enables the entrepreneur to be viewed as an economic agent and entrepreneurship as a consequence of the market. Analyzing the part that entrepreneurs play in the expansion and development of the economy is helpful. "Why" inquiries concentrate on the particular entrepreneur and the reasons behind their entrepreneurial acts, such as their history, motivations, and value system. The "how" question, on the other hand, focuses on the traits of entrepreneurs and the variables that influence the entrepreneurial process.

The debate demonstrates that Black Caribbean and South Asian women are devoted to the fundamental institutions and ideals of their own cultures. For instance, they place a high importance on family. Being an entrepreneur while maintaining their culture offers a difficulty since they must fulfil their traditional roles as South Asian and Black Caribbean women. Essentially, this refers to the problem of negotiating gender in a certain situation. This leads to this chapter's next topic of discussion, which is the interaction between “agency and structure”. In addition, reflecting the energetic character of the “entrepreneurial process”, temporal variables gave still another layer to the research, enhancing its depth and richness.

Additionally, the study of human agency, which propels the process and is imbedded in its surroundings (Scott, 1995), is intimately linked to the study of entrepreneurial processes

(Srivastava et al., 1999). It demonstrated the significance and ongoing function of institutions in directing FEs' "entrepreneurial processes". Therefore, it is impossible to study the "entrepreneurial process" in isolation. The research will be conducted within framework organizations and the people who, via their views and behaviors, impact the process. The important elements described in this chapter, supported by theory and previous experience, guide the following research topics, which are further investigated in this study.

Chapter 4: Research Methodology

4.1 Introduction

This chapter presents the research methodology for collecting, analysing and presenting the data in order to achieve the research objectives. This chapter is organized in nine sections. The first section outlines the philosophical foundations of the study and adopts a social constructionist stance based on subjective ontology. The second section specifies the research design within the chosen philosophical framework by dealing with the unit of analysis and the sampling procedures. It discusses the methodological aspects of choosing an individual entrepreneur as the unit of analysis and employs purposive sampling to identify the research population. The third and fourth sections detail the two intertwined aspects of fieldwork in getting access to respondents and conducting the in-depth interviews for collecting data.

The fifth section explains the organization of the interview data to set it up for the analysis. The sixth and seventh sections discuss the data analysis process and the specific analytical procedures applied to the data. It justifies the choice of constructivist grounded theory and details the coding procedure as carried out for the data analysis. The eighth section deals with the reflective account of the researcher during the research process. The final section concludes the chapter.

4.2 Research Approach

The research is inductive in nature, which means the study will start by collecting the data by interviewing the participants, and then to investigate the occurrence of the reality and then the researcher will be able to generate a theory. According to Saunders (2009) inductive approach is more useful and reliable when working with a small sample size than a large number of participants. Researcher will work with qualitative data, which will be collected in various methods in order to establish different point of views of the events.

4.3 Philosophical Foundations of the Research

Every research work is based on the assumptions on how the phenomenon under study is perceived by the researcher and how it can be best understood. This perception of phenomenon and its critical understanding is based on the philosophical approach that a researcher adopts for the purpose of his/her work (Thorpe, 1989). M Easteby-Smith, R Thorpe, (2002), stated three reasons to support the usefulness of understanding philosophical issues for the research. Firstly, it helps in the clarification of an overall research design. The philosophical assumptions of the research provide the researcher with the grounds to conceptualize, justify, explain and present the research work. Secondly, the appropriateness of research design, particularly the research method, can be justified by understanding the

underlying research philosophy. The philosophical assumptions of the research sensitize the researcher about different methodological choices and help them select the appropriate research method. And thirdly, with the help of understanding philosophical issues, the researcher can build his/her own research tools and can design the research according to the research objectives.

4.3.1 Research Ethics

Every research has some ethics to follow. There are Four ethical norms in research was described by (Resnik, Rasmussen and Kissling, 2015), he explained why it is important to stick on to ethical norms in research.

1. To authorize research aims, information, reality, and anticipation of mistakes, such as, preventions against planning data, falsifying data, misinterpreting or twisting data, supporting the reality and evade error.
2. By the time research started, the teamwork and harmonization amongst many individuals taking part in the research from different institutions, ethical norms advance the standards that are significant for combined effort, for instance have faith in, accountability, conjoint respect, and justice. The ethical customs in research like regulating criteria for writing and exclusive rights and, data revealing strategies, and privacy policies in peer review, are created to protect academic material while indorsing collective work (Resnik and Shamoo, 2017).
3. Ethical norms help to safeguard the original data and that the researchers have to provide answers to the public. Such as general guideline and policies on research transgression, clashes of interest, security for humans research, use and care for animals, are essential in respect to make sure that if the researchers are using public's fund to conduct a research, then they are also accountable to answer the public (Wise *et al.*, 2015).
4. The next ethical norms benefits to build public's support to conduct a research, generally people provide funds and encourages the research, only if they believe that the research will be reliable and trustworthy (Smith *et al.*, 2020).

Adopting integrity in research is also very important. National Academy of Scientist (NAS), define integrity of research as a feature of moral character and knowledge, which include devotion and commitment, trustworthiness and individual accountability and liability for their conduct and to perform research. Although science encourages safety of an individual's opinions, viewpoints and work, finally research integrity dememos, evaluating the research

document with impartiality and consider the outcome rather than use predefined thoughts and beliefs.

Implementing research integrity means formulating, proposing, completing, illustrating, and reevaluating research in accord to the ethical standards.

It should be mandatory that the research organizations, research promoters, journals, sponsors and scholarly associations promotes these ethical standards.

The major part of human-being taking part in a research, for instance female entrepreneurs (South Asian and African-Caribbean) in the United Kingdom, are compel as data suppliers. Researchers will be accountable to guard their well-being, confidence, honesty, confidentiality of secret data provided by research participants.

As this research is directed by female entrepreneurs, (South Asian and African-Caribbean) in the United Kingdom, The Belmont Report (1979) is the perfect example to follow. The report encompasses the ethical principles and guidelines for the protection of the data provided by research participants. The Belmont Report was publishing by the “The National Commission for the Protection of Human Subjects of Biomedical and Behavioral Research” in April 1979.

The report specifies three ethical principles:

- Respect for persons – the restraint to acknowledge individuality and also to protect persons with less freedom.
- Beneficence – first of all escape harm, use the possible benefits and decrease potential harm.
- Justice – on an individual and communal level (Belmont Report, 1979).

Mistreatment of research participants is supposed as research indiscretion, no ethical assessment or authorization, failure to follow approved guidelines, neglecting or ineffective consent, exposing of the participants to any kind of physical or mental harm, exposing of participants to any kind of damage due to inappropriate research performs or malfunctioning in keeping privacy of the data provided, getting involved in untruthfulness and unreliability is an offence in the research world.

Comprehending the University of the West of the Scotland’s recommendations regarding research ethics, the collected data is saved which does not harm the privacy of the participants and the trustworthiness of the collected data is managed by using coding matrix.

The main ethical concern encountered is to retrieve the accuracy and reality of the collected data as the female entrepreneurs are or have faced problems in their businesses but they hesitated to bring this up in front of the researcher. To avoid this building confidence with the participants was necessary.

4.3.2 Research Philosophies and Paradigms

Any research philosophy is based on some underlying assumptions that can be categorized into ethics (axiology), epistemology, ontology and methodology (Hanson *et al.*, 2005). Ontology refers to the “nature of reality” (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2009) “nature of human beings in the world” (Denzin, Lincoln and Giardina, 2006). It constitutes a personal view regarding the existence of reality and, therefore, varies from person to person.

Some believe that reality/social world exists independent of their assumptions and beliefs, which can be investigated objectively through empirical research but for others, social realities are constructed through social interactions which do not exist independent of researchers’ perceptions of the world in which they live (Schutz, 1962 cited in Hughes and Sharrock, 1997). The researchers with the former belief take an ‘objectivist’ position whereas the latter assume a ‘subjectivist’ stance to understand the social world. Thus, ontology suggests implicit assumption about a researcher’s cognitive space and about what he/she believes in that space to be valid in terms of knowledge, and which leads the researcher to consider how knowledge can be obtained, studied and understood – the epistemological question.

It is believed that world has numerous viewpoints and the system that operates internally in the world is called philosophy. Philosophy is apprehensive with the opinions related how the world’s mechanism is intact, highlighting mostly, on realism, understanding and the life styles.

The trust about the world is related to what we observe as realism, and an individual’s belief of realism is based on the awareness one gained and will directly effect on the research conduct (Wu *et al.*, 2016; Maria Hagan and Wassink, 2016; Van Esch and Van Esch, 2013).

Research philosophy is described as an arrangements of perspectives and possibilities regarding the enhancement and upgrading of the understandings. It is mostly founded on what the researcher is implementing when doing the research and obtaining information on a specific field. The obtained material or information may be as projected as a new idea of human inspiration but answering the particular set back in an identifiable understanding will guided to a development of a new theory (Mark Bray, Bob Adamson, 2014; Davidson, 2009).

In this research the epistemological approach will be applied because the area of the research is about the challenges and barriers faced by female entrepreneurs (South Asian and African-Caribbean) in the United Kingdom. This is obvious that they have several different challenges and barriers but the impact of those challenges and barriers are different in different cultural background which will be compared in the results.

Epistemology is related with realism and interpretivism, and as this research manifesting phenomenology that the challenges and barriers encountered by female entrepreneurs (South Asian and African-Caribbean) in the United Kingdom, are different and enlightened in a dissimilar patterns in different areas.

Therefore, interpretivism approach is required which means there is no single reality. There is no single reality but there are several different realities appeared regarding the challenges and barriers faced by female entrepreneurs (South Asian and African-Caribbean) in the United Kingdom. Epistemology is also known as a study of the knowledge which directs and structure the research.

It is related with the theories such as how, when, what and why. There are three main epistemological factors given by (Thiétart and Forgues, 1995) they are as follows

- To determine the nature of knowledge if it is an actual depiction of the reality which is present previously, or the researcher's understanding and interpretation of the independent reality;
- By establishing and processing the knowledge by using both factual explanation and by an understanding the subjective reality;
- To clarify that the knowledge is correct, reliable and logical in nature

Ontological and epistemological theories always are helpful for the researchers to choose an appropriate methodology for investigating the research issues and problems. They create several different types of research paradigms (HM Treasury, 2012). A research paradigm is described as a group of philosophical assumptions by using this a researcher is able to contact the field of research easily. A research paradigm is defined by (Greenhalgh, 2011) in two aspects;

1. A complete patterns of philosophies, beliefs and methods imparted by scientific community
2. The techniques used to resolve a particular problem and the use of the theories in a realistic assumptions

In both aspects of paradigm gives an outline to direct the process of the research by assisting a researcher in the selection of proper methodological tools to understand the field of research (Flick, 2014; Flick, 2019). An appropriate research paradigm was briefed by (Thiétart and Forgues, 1995) on the basis of epistemological positions in organizing research which are mainly used in the field of research based on entrepreneurship (Trotter, 2012; Welter, Brush and de Bruin, 2018). The research paradigms were grouped into positivism, interpretivism and constructivism on the basis of the significance of information, characteristics of the realism, construction and significance of the information, which are shown in the following table.

Table 5 Epistemological Positions of different Paradigms (Source: (Thiétart and Forgues, 1995)

Epistemological Questions	Positivism	Interpretivism	Constructivism
Nature of “reality”	Determinist Hypothesis: World is made is up of necessities	Internationalist hypothesis: World is made up of possibilities	
Status of knowledge	Ontological theory: the information object has its own quintessence (Contextual, Objective, autonomy of Subject and item)	Phenomenological theory: The epitome of the item is various (interpretivism), can't be achieved (moderate constructivism) or doesn't exist (revolutionary constructivism)- (emotional, relevant) Ward of subject and article	
How knowledge is generated?	Discovery <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The research question is formulated as “for what reasons...” Privileged status of Explanation 	Interpretation <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The research question as formulated as “what motivated actors to...” 	Construction <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The research question is formulated as “to what ends does...”

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Privileged status of understanding 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Privileged status of construction
<p>What is the value of knowledge? (Legitimacy criteria)</p>	<p>Degree of confirmation; refutability; rational consistency</p>	<p>Integrity; transferability; steadfastness; Conformability</p>	<p>Competence; “teach-ability”</p>

A paradigm of positivism is an established methodical aspect which presumes that the information can be created by using the hard realities and their connection with these realities (Pargament *et al.*, 1998; Baum, MacDougall and Smith, 2006). In the table “ontological hypothesis” of positivism, which represent that factual aspect of realism (ontological position), presuming that the researcher is totally independent individual apart from the realism. This statement presumes that the realism is present and can be methodically explored in order to exploit and to test the existing hypothesis or an information, to preserve the aspect of realism. Moreover, realism or social facts are related to positivism, in public research can be calculated through factual approaches (Hanson *et al.*, 2005). The purpose of positivism investigation is to create the “truth statement free from both time and context” to declare the integrity of the information (Leech *et al.*, 2010; Onwuegbuzie and Leech, 2007). On the contrary, theoretical practices of interpretivism and constructivism are centered on the phenomenological hypothesis which have a “subjective” ontological aspect. Phenomenological aspect is another name of interpretivism or constructivism which is not able to hypothesize the realm of terminologies of objects and their exact fundamental associations. It depends on the personal views of individuals which are obtained from particular statements and information, contrasting the positivism investigation which is based on the analysis of the exiting hypothesis. Thus, constructivism uses inductive perceptive to develop a potential association between various objects in the World (Holloway, Krogh and Giua, 1997; Thorpe, 1989; M Easteby-Smith, R Thorpe, 2002). A debate by Morgan “the whole point of phenomenology is that we cannot split off the subjective domain from the domain of the natural World as scientific naturalism has done. Subjectivity must be understood as inextricably involved in the process of constituting objectivity”.

Constructivism and interpretivism rely on several different social experiences which are laden with the participant's values and only considered as their understanding and version of reality. These practices are generated after the reaction or responses of the participants towards the positivist philosophy, debating that "rich insights" into subjective and reality of the field can only recognize by variances between the social actors who are interpreting the realism depending upon their experiences, ideas, principles and facts. Constructivism and interpretivism are alternatives of phenomenology, however the variance between these aspects is the issue of extent instead of concepts. Whereas interpretivism rely on the several different types of realities presents because of the altering analyses of social actors, therefore realism varies person to person (Blair and Lacy, 1993; Larson and Starr, 1993; Perren and Ram, 2004).

Constructivism in a social sector presume that the "social objects are not given in the World but constructed, negotiated, reformed, fashioned and organized by human beings in their efforts to make sense of happenings in the World" (Hagstrom and Daniels, 2004; Russell and Kelly, 2002). These aspects declare the understanding of social actors according to their views in the social World. Some of the famous researchers separated the terms constructivism and constructionism which were previously used as identically for each term. Constructionism highlights the relationship of the realism and the point of view of an individual surrounded by the social network, whereas constructivism promotes the position of an individual perception that identifies and develop the values to formulate a subjective realism (Morse and McEvoy, 2014; Mollen, 2020; Hasan, 2016). According to this both constructivism and constructionism portrays different ways of the social realism, which was previously known as psychological whereas recently known as sociological.

4.4 Arranging the Research Surrounded by Social Constructionism

This research is using the paradigm of social constructionism. Taking into consideration the individual realities (ontological aspect) and investigating the issues and barriers of female entrepreneurs of South Asian compared to African Caribbean origin. The constructionism beliefs that entities create the subjective point of views in their field according to their specific experiences and understandings. The thought of social constructivism draws back to Berger and Luckmann's (1967) idea that is "The social construction of reality" where they have debated that the realities are created socially by the social connections of the actors as they are continuously engrossed in creating "social order" by interpretations, explorations and reinterpretation of socially common acts. The primary beliefs of social constructionism presumes that realism is created socially, but actually it is agreed socially and cannot be

assumed by re-establishing the realities (Clarke, 2006; Padgett, 1998; Opute and Irene, 1856; Leitch, Hill and Neergaard, 2010). As this research endeavors to investigate the issues and barriers encountered by the female entrepreneurs of ethnic minorities such as South Asian and African Caribbean, in order to conduct this research an appropriate research approach is essential to enable the researcher to maintain trust with the participants to structure and investigate their social facts and to clarify their experiences regarding their social field. In examining the realism in human-beings it is expected that the reality of an observable fact is basically differs from individual to individual, where these realities are the result of social communication of an individual (Bygrave, 2007). In this research, subjectivist aspect presumes that the social realism does not occur alone rather than depend upon an individual involved socially in its interpretation and is not able to be examined without considering the effects of external impacts. The issues and barriers of the female entrepreneurs of ethnic minorities depend upon their relationship and these relations are created carefully on the basis of ethnicity and socially created according to their positions based on gender. Therefore these relationship are represented by the effects of the social communication and their understandings (Shek, Tang and Han, 2005). To investigate this obscure fact entrenched in the social setting, it is expected that the researcher should focus on the subjective realism by using a social constructionist perspective (Sheng, 2019). The previous research conducted on entrepreneurship, always uses social constructionism to form the perception through the process of entrepreneurs because constructionist philosophy generates the base for an investigation of unexplored areas of research taking into consideration that the researcher have exclusive views on the field which is under research (Gupta S., 2015; Nastasi and Schensul, 2005).

The entrepreneurship is a socially created pursuit that is “relationally responsive” and appears in conversations and discussion based on the experiences of entrepreneurs (Bygrave, 2007). The social constructivist perspective is useful in order to understand the type of entrepreneurial actions by examining the social realism created by the entrepreneurs during their conversation. The emphasis of this research is to identify the issues and barriers faced by female entrepreneurs in their businesses such as financial, managerial, personal experiences. The viewpoint of social constructivism inspects the “meaning of reality are produced by interaction of people” (Jennings and Brush, 2013; Welter, Brush and de Bruin, 2018). The significance of specific incidents, and our approach to understand them, differ from situation to situation (Isaga, 2019; Lock and Strong, 2010). Due to these differences, a

constant method of investigation is not applied. As an alternative, investigation of the biasness in the research became fundamental.

The objective of this research is to investigate the issues and barriers faced by female entrepreneurs by exploring their experiences in the development and running of their businesses. By the use of social constructionist approach, understanding of the issues and barriers in accordance to the financial, managerial, personal and etc. will be an additional help to research (Bergman, 1985).

4.5 Implementing the Qualitative Research Method

Choosing the methodology is absolute in the selection of research paradigm. Qualitative and Quantitative research method are the majorly used in the social sciences, in the recent time mixed methodology of research is also used. The difference between the methodology is based on the features of the investigation, the type of support required, the collection of data and examining procedures indicating the ontological hypotheses and the epistemological approach abide by the researcher (Ryan, 2008). Each methodology has a particular characteristic, strong points and restrictions, it's up to the researcher to take a decision which methodology could be used to analyze the problem under research. The researcher can use either Qualitative, Quantitative or mix methodology according to the research paradigm. According to Cresswell (2009) suggested that the selection of the design of the research is determined by the researcher point of view and the strategy under taken in the research, the design can be Qualitative, Quantitative or mixed in nature. In Qualitative methodology, constructivist epistemology can be used to investigate, observe and conducting interviews for data collection. According to Denzin and Lincoln (2005) stated that "Qualitative research design consider objects in their natural situations, endeavoring to make it clear, or to determine the facts according to the responses given by the people (Denzin, Lincoln and Giardina, 2006). The disadvantages and limitations of Qualitative and Quantitative research designs are discoursed in contrast of the content of the data collected and analysis of the data (Phoenix, 2018).

4.5.1 Evaluation of Qualitative Research Method

Quantitative research methodology mostly critiqued to be deficient in details and extent, depicts communication according to reasonable ideas. This design is able to proficiently test the hypotheses but may lack in the background and relative facts of the research. Moreover, the classiness of the statistical methods for analyzing the data, dominates the significance of the collected data. Whereas the disapproval of Quantitative research is related to the data

contents, Qualitative research is believed to be insubstantial in the investigation of the biasness and beliefs of the researcher. It does not tell the truth and does not document the planned investigative methodologies, adverse occurrences are not discoursed, and it does not consider the reliability and context of the data (Patton, 2002; Kuckartz, 2014; Thomson, 2011). There is no exact contradiction of these research methods.

Intellectuals like Flick, (2002); Patton, (2002); and Creswell, (2003), restated that none of the research method reciprocally complete. The selection of the methodology of the research should considered the nature of the research instead of researcher's inclination towards the research method. The paramount research method is unique in order to answer the research question in the most achievable way (Stream, Policy and Wales, 2006). Qualitative research depicts factual experiences by concentrating on the natural phenomena and every day incidents in natural situations (Miles and Huberman, 1994: 10). It is coherent that this research consider entrepreneurship in accordance of social activity happening in the natural settings and investigate by focusing the issues and barriers of female entrepreneurs of South Asian and African Caribbean origin (Rich and Ginsburg, 1999).

Qualitative research is able to examine how social practices and understanding are constructed and provide significance and creates understanding of the natural settings and makes it evident (Denzin and Lincoln, 2000; Brady, 2015). Studying the realism of life, in a natural situation is conducted by applying the Qualitative research design, which utilizes the values of the participants to describe their experiences of daily life. Hence, in this research Qualitative method is used to recognize and investigate the issues and barriers, to better understand the experiences of female entrepreneurs in running their businesses. The selection of a Qualitative research design is believed to be suitable to understand the requirements of the research aims and objectives lay out for this research. A Qualitative method clarifies participants understanding and point of view according to their experiences (Sullivan, 2012; Denzin, Lincoln and Giardina, 2006). The practices and understanding of the participants turn out to be the reality which a researcher is seeking in this research (Kalu, 2017).

The social practices and understanding of the female entrepreneurs are important in structuring the research, the Qualitative research design is reliable along with ontological and epistemological approaches in this research (Feilzer, 2010).

4.6 Research Design

The design of this research is qualitative. Qualitative research is subjective in nature which deals with assessing of the observations and understanding of communal and mortal actions

(Mary T. Holden, 2004; Hussey and Hussey, 1997). Qualitative research is inductive in nature, the researcher hardly have an idea of the details of data analysis when starting the research (Choy, 2014; Neuman, 2006).

Creswell (2009) defined qualitative research as “a means for investigating and understanding the meaning individuals or group ascribe to a social or human problem, this process involves emerging questions and procedures, data typically collected in the participant’s setting, data analysis inductively building from particulars to general themes, and the researcher making interpretations of the meaning of data” (Wahyuni, 2012).

Whilst Gilbert describes qualitative research is a process which targets to explore and examine a particular issue by explaining prospects, collecting data by conducting interviews and examining the significance of the records (Gilbert, 2007).

Qualitative research depicts real life by focusing on “naturally occurring, ordinary events in natural setting” (Miles and Huberman, 1994; Hartley and Chesworth, 2000). It is coherent in this research as entrepreneurship is a social process occurring in the natural setting and discovers the issues and barriers of social actors (South Asian and African-Caribbean female entrepreneurs) which are the main focus of the research. Qualitative research can “explore how social experience is created and given meaning and produces representations of the world that make the world visible” (Casey and Murphy, 2009).

Investigating the realism of life, in a natural setting is aided by qualitative method of research, it engages the social members to explicate how they directly experience everyday life realities (José Gómez Galán, Marcela Cazzoli-Goeta, 2007; Flick, 2014). Thus, the qualitative research style is adapted in this research to comprehend and investigate the issues and barriers in order to clarify the social experience of South Asian and African- Caribbean female entrepreneurs in the United Kingdom (Schütz and Luckmann, 1980).

The qualitative research style is suitable to target the objectives set out for this research. A qualitative style devotes identification of the “participant’s perspective” on the events and activities (Denzin and Lincoln, 2000). By studying the experiences of the participants the researcher will be able to explore the reality (Sgier, 2014).

The social experiences of the respondents (South Asian and African-Caribbean female entrepreneurs) are critical to explore their issues and barriers which influences their entrepreneurial practices. Therefore, qualitative approach is useful and reliable with the ontological and epistemological rules of this research. Creswell (2009) describes research

design as “plans and procedures for research that span from broad assumptions to detailed methods of data collection and analysis”. A design of research is the plan of the research, which enables the researcher to answer the research question (Sandelowski, 1991). The interpretation of research design implicates the determination of the strategy of the research, collection of the data and methods of analysing the data through the ontological and epistemological approaches of the research.

4.7 Unit of Analysis, Female Entrepreneurs of South Asian and African Caribbean Origin

A unit of analysis indicates the object that a researcher wants to investigate in the research. Unit of analysis is defined by Babbie (2010) as “what or whom being studied”. The what or who in the research refers to a person or group of people, or it can be a book, newspaper or a photograph, it can be a location such as a town or a state, it can also be the social communication between individual, it can also involves the incidents occurring in the natural settings (Bartkowiak-theron and Robyn Sappey, 2012; Groenewald, 2004). The selection of the unit of analysis relies on the objective and aims of the research (Bless, Higson-Smith and Kagee, 2006; Babbie, 2008).

A social attitude of entrepreneurship proposes researching entrepreneurs in regards to “what they do” than “who they are” (Gartner, 1988). This method attempts to explore the entrepreneur’s communication and contact with the external World (McCarthy, 2000).

Entrepreneurship is defined by Gartner (1985) as “an act of creating new organization”; therefore, the entrepreneur is someone who starts a new business. The selection of the entrepreneur entity as a unit of analysis supports in the implementation of a behavioral aspect for this research (Etherington, 2004). The behavior of an entrepreneur is influenced by their personal practices and understandings. As this research is comprises on how personal experiences structures the behavior of female entrepreneurs in running their businesses especially the issues and barriers they encountered. Hence, it is likely to indicate the social practices and understanding of an entrepreneur and how they explain their experiences and problems they faced whilst starting up their businesses and now running them smoothly (Burnard, 1991). Hence, this research considers an individual entrepreneur as unit of analysis in order to explore the issues and barriers they faced especially in processing their businesses successfully. Female entrepreneur’s communicates within their field to reduce the impact of the problems they face while running their businesses (Platt, 1988). The activities of female entrepreneurs are affected by the factors such as occupational, personal life, society.

Therefore, female entrepreneurs are not able to act as an independent entity. This research will aid to recognize and investigate the impact of the above-mentioned issues. In this research, the researcher aims to investigate the issues and barriers encountered by an individual female entrepreneur and how these factors influences their businesses and personal life (Parminde Bhachu, 1988).

In order to explore, entrepreneur's point of view is an important. It is coherent to use the behavioral approach in order to explore the issues which female entrepreneur are facing and the effect on their business.

Therefore, suitable unit of analysis for this research is an individual female entrepreneur which in this case are from South Asian and African Caribbean ethnicity. The choice of female entrepreneur of South Asian and African Caribbean as the unit of analysis is in harmony with epistemological approach implemented in this research.

It is also essential for this research to study the facts and experiences in the natural context (Patton, 2002). This research endeavors to recognize the impact of the issues and barriers and how the female entrepreneurs deal with these factors in their businesses. Moreover, the aim of this research is to detect the intensity of the issues and barriers faced by the female entrepreneurs of South Asian and African Caribbean ethnicity. Additionally, this research offers a comparison of the issues and barriers faced by the female entrepreneurs of South Asian in contrast to African Caribbean.

4.8 Sampling in Qualitative Research Design

Sampling in Qualitative research methodology demonstrates the section of unit of analysis amongst the group under research (Bobbie, 2008). The sampling can be done by two methods:

4.8.1 Probability Sampling & Nonprobability Sampling

In the probability sampling, the unit of analysis can be selected randomly from the selected group so that there is an equal chance of every entity to be a part of the research. While, nonprobability sampling method demonstrates the judgment of the researcher to include the unit of analysis on the basis of equal opportunity (Gilgun, 2005).

Mostly in the Quantitative research method sampling through probability method is used for the reason that the rationale of the research is to simplify the outcomes within the group under research (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019). The Qualitative research method highlights the comprehensive investigation instead of the overview of the outcomes of the research. A small size of sample is appropriate to gather the required information regarding the facts and

experiences in the research (Patton, 2002). Hence, the use of nonprobability method of sampling is more suitable in the Qualitative research design to select the participants according to the requirement. The sampling in Qualitative research is purposeful as it is selected by the researcher according to the aims and objectives of the research. In purposeful sampling the selection of the participants concurring to the identified standards set for the research (Ritchie and Lewis, 2003). The selection of the participants can be done on the basis of specific factors with a “purpose” which can help in investigating the situations in the research. On the basis of the selected unit of analysis purposeful sampling method is used in this research. The purpose of this research is to investigate the issues and barriers encountered by female entrepreneurs of South Asian and African Caribbean origin, in setting up and running their businesses, in relation to their experiences and understandings.

The main decisive factors for the selection of the participants, includes conditions of gender that is entrepreneurs, origin that is South Asian and African Caribbean and topographical location that is the United Kingdom, the factors are given below;

- i. **Entrepreneurs:** Davidsson’s criteria of identifying entrepreneurs is used in this research. He stated that an entrepreneur is different from an ordinary business owner, he describes an entrepreneur is someone who begins the “new economic activity” directing to a “change in the market place” (Hoang and Antoncic, 2003; Davidsson, 2004). Schumpeter’s definition of entrepreneurship is considered and implemented in this research. He explained that an entrepreneurship portrays the concept of newness as “new combination” (Schumpeter’s, 1934). Implemented in this research, the criteria of new combinations present the embedded inclination towards the entrepreneurship that is starting up a new business and running their current business.

Therefore, it is likely to find the inspiration of female entrepreneur in developing the new business and this can be presumed that the new entry in the market possibly will be successful or unsuccessful (Ram, Edwards and Jones, 2007). It depends on the issues and barriers they encountered in the newly developed business, the new entrepreneur might get separated from their business or close it down. Hence, it is essential to consider existent entrepreneur.

Several different definition of entrepreneurship are used in this research to distinguish among a new and existent entrepreneur, which is not the capacity of this research. For that reason, the researcher decided does not go in details anymore (Johannisson, 1996). Thus, this research considered existent entrepreneurs who are running their businesses, in order to investigate their experiences regarding the issues and barriers female entrepreneurs encountered at the

time of beginning a business and now running it (Shakeel, Yaokuang and Gohar, 2020). Brush describes existent entrepreneur as “those who are employed as owners/managers of the businesses for more than forty-two months”. This enables the researcher to identify the female entrepreneurs of South Asian and African Caribbean origin who have started their businesses in the last three years to satisfy the need of the research.

- ii. **Gender:** This research emphasizes on the female entrepreneurs.
- iii. **Ethnicity:** This research focuses on a specific minorities as a participants which is female entrepreneurs of South Asian and African Caribbean origin.
- iv. **Topographical location:** The specific topographical location in this research is the United Kingdom because the aim of this research is to target the South Asian and African Caribbean female entrepreneurs in the United Kingdom.

The participants are selected through purposeful sampling method and inclusion criteria is also used to include a particular ethnic minorities that is South Asian and African Caribbean female entrepreneurs in this research.

4.9 Finding and Gaining Access to the Participants

After identifying the targeted population for collecting the data the next phase was to identify possible participants. In order to do that telephone books, online portals and data bases were used as a tool to collect information (MacQueen *et al.*, 1998). If these tools do not have adequate information to enable the researcher to contact the possible participants, then the researcher need to draw a plan to locate the sample. A sample frame deems to the tools used for recruiting a sample. The formation of a sample frame facilitates the researcher to find the possible participants. In the first phase the researcher identified the data base that can satisfy and provide the required information that is gender, ethnicity, age of the business and location (Raco and Tunney, 2010). As a result of this, the researcher created a sample frame in which several different tactics are used which are discuss in detail in the section below;

4.9.1 Gaining Access to the Participants through Organizations

Gaining access to the participants, strategy of gatekeepers is renowned to contact the participants (Padgett, 1998; Holloway, 1997). A number of bodies are included in this strategy that is persons and organizations who have controlled to get access with the possible participants (Holloway, 1997). Due to the lack of information and updated database on South Asian and African Caribbean female entrepreneurs, the researcher contacted number of

organizations such as community welfare organizations, agencies deal in business and different borough of United Kingdom.

i. London Borough of Newham

The researcher begins to locate the sample by getting in touch with London borough of Newham as it is densely populated with South Asian and African Caribbean female entrepreneurs. Once the process of recognizing the sample, phone calls were made to the business advisor followed by emails sent to the business support and advisory team in Newham. The Newham council was not able to give any information regarding South Asian and African Caribbean female entrepreneurs, due to GDPR policy and also the data is not available for the business owner on the basis of ethnic minorities. Instead, the referrals made by the business advisor to the community welfare organizations and to the agencies deals in the development of the businesses (Haskey, 1994). This aids the researcher in stipulating the relevant information, the process of getting this information is discoursed below;

ii. The Agencies Deal in the Development of Businesses

In order to identify the South Asian and African Caribbean female entrepreneurs, the researcher got in touch with the agencies that deals in the development of businesses in London borough of Newham. These agencies are responsible to keep up the database regarding the business owners because they are directly in touch with the businesses (Cabinet Office, 2002). The researcher contacted several agencies by sending emails, especially the one who deals with the development of the businesses owned by ethnic minorities along with the following agencies; London Development Agency (LDA), Department of Business, Energy and Industrial Strategy, Minority Business Funding, Ethnic Minority Foundation (EMF). In the sent emails, the researcher gave details regarding the DBA research and requested for assistance in order to identify the possible participants. It was very useful to contact these agencies because they have given further references of the welfare and community organizations.

iii. Women Community and Welfare Organizations

After contacting the business advisor, the researcher expands the search of potential participants by contacting the women community and welfare organization. These organizations, turn out to be a great help in providing the information regarding the South Asian and African Caribbean female entrepreneurs, as these welfare association are famous in the community of ethnic minorities. Most of these organizations are based on just females

and they are responsible and trustable amongst the ethnic minorities. These organizations aided the researcher by giving referrals for the South Asian and African Caribbean female entrepreneurs, also the information regarding the research was conveyed to the chosen population, the outcome was great and several people got in touch with the researcher and showed their interest and were ready to take part in the research, the appointment for interviews were arranged (Dworkin, 2012).

4.9.2 Gaining Access of Participants by using other Tools

After contacting the London borough of Newham, the welfare and community organizations and the agencies deals with the development of the businesses, the researcher used some additional tools to gain access to the possible participants. The details of these tools are given below;

i. Magazines and Online data

In order to gain more information regarding the South Asian and African Caribbean female entrepreneurs, the researcher searched online magazines and data available on the businesses owned by ethnic minorities, by doing this the researcher was able to collect contact details of the businesses. The portals available on the businesses in the United Kingdom are British Association of Women Entrepreneurs, Women in Business. The researcher gathered the required information from these portals in order to get in touch with the business owners from ethnic minorities. However, the information was not enough to analyze or detect the gender and ethnic background of the business owners. This gap in the information was overcome by identifying the areas where the businesses are possibly owned by South Asian and African Caribbean female entrepreneurs.

ii. Door knocking strategy and phone calls

First of all, Asian's and African's named businesses were picked out from the magazines and also from online data available. The phone calls were made to gather the details regarding the ethnic background of the owner of the business. Unfortunately, most of the people were not ready to share any information regarding their origin or business via phone calls. To overcome with this issue the researcher decided to visit personally to the market in order to provide information regarding the DBA research and also to build a friendly and trustworthy relationship, as this will allow the business owner to provide the most up to date and relevant information to the researcher (Jane Ritchie, 2003). The researcher was looking forward to reduce their insecurities and hesitations regarding giving their information to a stranger. This

technique of visiting the businesses personally and identifying the possible participants is known as “door knocking” strategy (Ritchie and Lewis, 2003). The researcher visited Stratford Center, Forest Gate and Green Street markets, these markets have number of businesses owned by South Asian and African Caribbean female entrepreneurs. The door knocking technique turns out to be very beneficial for the researcher because it becomes easier to detect the South Asian and African Caribbean female entrepreneurs, after identifying the targeted female entrepreneurs, the process of the research was explained to them. Once the introductions were done the researcher was able to easily convince the business owners to participate in the research.

4.10 Data Collection

The researcher has organized face to face in-depth interviews with the participants. Interviews are very helpful research technique used to collect data (Seale, 1999) hence this method is used to collect effective and dependable data which provide answers to the research questions and also to the research aims and objectives (Saunders, 2007). According to Hussey (1997), interviewing is a focused discussion between researcher and the participants.

There are different types of interview techniques; in-depth, semi structured, structured and interviews of a group. The interviews can conduct by telephones or either face to face. Interviewing is a process of real communication between the participants and the researcher to collect data (Grudens-Schuck, Allen and Larson, 2004).

However, the interviews are frequently thought the best method of collecting the data, but the complications are mostly undervalued (Pervez and Kjell, 2002).

The selection of suitable data collection method is very important in the research because unsuitable data collection may indicate void results and will not help in achieving the research objectives.

Patton (2002) reports that “qualitative data consists of quotations, observations and experts from documents” which clarifies that the qualitative data is descriptive in nature. Generally qualitative data is text but lately it extended out to incorporate images, videos, and sound recordings (Bernard and Ryan, 2009; Patton, 2002). Observations, interviews, narrative/stories from the field all are included in the qualitative data collection methods (Flick, 2007; Creswell, 2009; Bernard and Ryan, 2009). The selection of data collection method influenced by the nature of research problem, the selection of strategy of investigation and the concept of the research. To discover the experiences, issues and barriers encountered

by South Asian and African-Caribbean female entrepreneurs in the United Kingdom, a qualitative approach is used for data collection. In-depth interview technique appeared more suitable to collect qualitative data required to answer the research questions. According to Boyce and Neale (2006) “in-depth interviewing is a qualitative research technique that involves conducting intensive individual interviews with a small number of respondents to explore their perspectives on a particular idea, program or situation”. The in-depth interview needs open ended question, and face to face interaction between the researcher and the respondents (Neale, Thapa and Boyce, 2006).

4.11 Effect of the Sampling Techniques Implemented and Report of the Chosen Participants

After an enduring process in the selected locations of research 15 participants were identified who were interested to take part in the research. Among the tools which were used to identify the participants only few were useful in gathering the required information.

4.12 Collection of Data by In-depth Interviews

After the review of the literature, the researcher acknowledged that there is a small amount of authentic data available on female entrepreneurs from ethnic minorities. The researcher decided to organise unstructured in-depth interviews by using qualitative research approach, in order to investigate how females are setting up or running their enterprises (Smith, Bekker and Cheater, 2011). Getting in touch with small business owners was not an easy task because small business sector is extremely difficult to access especially due to the pandemic of COVID-19 and the continuous lockdown. All the non-essential retail market was closed from March 2020 till date. The access to the small businesses were difficult because of the disbelief of authorities and concerns about the administrative system, especially the Inland Revenue (Coll, Richard K. *et al.*, 2008; Ram, 1994). The easiest option for accessing the female business owners was to find their details in the directories and after having access to their contact details, request for an interview through telephone, using “WhatsApp” or “Skype” video calling. Generally, the directories do not exist and due to the closure of businesses it was very difficult to contact the business owners.

To overcome this issue, opportunistic “snowballing” research method was implemented, this method works well through personal contacts and by requesting and encouraging the female business owners for their colleagues, which is the only criteria to develop a trust in the field of research. After adopting this non formal and spontaneous method it was much easy to gain their trust and cooperation, because if this trust was not maintained it was difficult to work

efficiently in the research field (Limerick, Burgess-Limerick and Grace, 1996; Oakley, 1981; Bulmer 1988; Hobbs 1988).

The approach acquired in this research, was explained by Bryman (1988) and Brannen (1992) according to them the qualitative method of research is mostly used for investigative study before intensifying the research or convert it into more complex study (Kepmenkes Keselamatan Pasien Rumah Sakit, 2011). Qualitative method is mostly used totally as a first step to conduct structured interviews and surveys (Roulston, 2010).

After finalizing the participants of the research, the researcher met them directly in order to take their written consent and to arrange their appointment for in-depth interviews. At this phase of research, the most crucial step is to select a suitable technique for the collection of data (Lopez-Fernandez and Molina-Azorin, 2011).

The selection of the technique used to collect data be subject to the type of research, paradigm of research and the selection of the technique required to inquire about the information needed for the research (Carla Willig, 2008). To find out the opinions and observations of the South Asian and African Caribbean female entrepreneurs and the issues and barriers they encountered in their businesses, a Qualitative data collection technique with the help of in-depth interviews is more suitable in order to achieve the desired answers of the questions designed for this research. Qualitative method of research include in-depth interviews with a small group of participants to investigate their point of view on a specific thought, plan and condition (Neale, Thapa and Boyce, 2006). Open ended questions are a key of an in-depth interview which can be done through face to face contact among the participants and the researcher (Ramcharan and Cutcliffe, 2001).

The aim of the researcher was to conduct the interviews at their work places to observe meticulously, how they maintain, manage and operate their businesses, but unfortunately due to the closure of businesses because of the lockdown some interviews were done on the video calls and some were done face to face after the lockdown restrictions lifted. The interviews were unstructured and in-depth and were governed by six main areas of focus such as

- Business history
- Personal background
- Initial encouragement
- Style of management
- Family support

- Socio-economic environment

Above mentioned areas were extracted by the literature review and each area carries some questions to investigate the possible issues and barriers encountered by the female entrepreneurs. The main part in designing the interview guide was the researcher's contribution along with review of the literature (M Saunders, P Lewis, 2009). During the interviews the emphasis was given to each section by gently asking inquisitive questions and deep discussions. Two interviews were conducted with all the participants, after first interview, another interview was conducted with the same participant to cover the topics which were touched superficially in the first interview, such as finances and accounts, recruiting, competition with their fellow business owners, family support, reasons of starting their business. The questions were designed to investigate each area in-depth which eventually aided in the selection of the research tool (Carla Willig, 2008).

Interviews are arranged according to the availability of the participants of the research. The participants are required to sign a consent form prior to the interview in order to maintain their trust and the privacy of the given details (Henwood and Pidgeon, 1992). The introduction of the researcher and about the research is done in the beginning of an interview, the participants are informed that their identity will be anonymous and their privacy will be maintained. During the introduction, the style of conversation depends on the understanding of the participants. The process of introducing the research and the researcher will lead to gain the confidence of the participants as this will make them comfortable. After achieving the level of comfort, the researcher seeks the approval from the participants to record the interview (Elkatawneh, 2016). The participants are assured that they can ask to stop the recording if they feel uncomfortable at any time during the interview. The recording of an interview allows the researcher to concentrate and ask relevant questions in order to gain as much information as required instead of taking long written memos which can compromise the attention of the researcher (Oakley, 2016). An interview guide is used to ask open ended questions during the interview, which allows the participants to respond accordingly. The open ended interview questions permits the participants to respond openly which will lead the openness of the interview (Tang, 2002). This openness of the interview helps the researcher to explore deeply in order to collect the required information (Schensul and LeCompte, 1999). This pattern of an interview permits the participants to reveal the information in the form of their observation and understanding without any disturbance and hindrance from the researcher. Therefore, in-

depth interviews with open ended questions are suitable in order to conduct an inductive research (Kvale, 1996; Patton, 2002).

i. The advantage of interview guide

An interview guide was created on the basis of the objective of the research along with the review of the literature was done. (Mangan, Lalwani and Gardner, 2004). The review of the literature aid the researcher to create an appropriate interview guide with open ended questions which allows the researcher to extract as much information as required for this research (Khan, 2014). The concept of creating an interview guide was taken from old researches done on the same topic. The function of an interview guide is to draw an agenda of the topics should be included in the interview. The interview guide allows the researcher to concentrate on the topics which are supposed to be covered according to the requirement of the research questions. The participants were not interrupted during the interview in order to go with the flow of detailed information being provided by the participants. Moreover, the main purpose of the interview was not compromised (Sparrow, 1999).

ii. Allocation of time, site and structure of in-depth interviews

The collection of the data was conducted at the site of the participants business, or at the mutual place decided by the researcher and the participants (Greene, 1994). In order to investigate the issues and barriers, the interviews were mostly conducted during the working hours because the researcher was trying to have an idea of the issues and barriers during the business working hours. Most of the South Asian and African Caribbean female entrepreneurs were also dealing with their family issues at the same time, this enables the researcher to investigate how they keep balance in their work and personal life (Yeomans, 2017).

In the search of comprehensive and in-depth answers, investigative questions were asked along with continuation of the answers (Abrams, 2010). The duration of the interviews were in between 60 to 90 minutes, during which the participants provided information about the issues and barriers they faced both at the time of setting up and running their businesses (Parker, 2004). Some of the interviews were lasted a bit longer, because the participant was also dealing with the clients at the same time.

4.13 Management of Data

The management and evaluation of the data begins once the researcher step in the social area of research and conduct the very first interview. Management and evaluation of the data in Qualitative method of research is mainly the techniques to store the data, to label the data, to

understand the labelled data and to convey the outcomes with the people who are reading the research (Huberman, A. M., & Miles, 1994). The data collected in Qualitative research method is basically comprises of an audio recording, memos and documents from the field. If the data collected in Qualitative research method is huge, then stocking and evaluating the data is a big task. The data should be stored in a way that it is ready to use for the evaluation which is the most important step of the research. The basis of the research is developed from Levin's (1985) point of view of five rules of managing the data, this was also repeated by Miles and Huberman (Levin, 1985; Miles and Huberman, 1994).

However it is not feasible to pass on the data directly, without arranging the data, which is the initial stage in the process of managing the data (Ikeda, 2009). The data is arranged in a form which is understandable, easy to handle which helps in the evaluation of the data. For that reason, the audio recording of the interviews was copied and every file should have a particular name, displaying the date of the interview, name of the participants and location of the interview. If applicable, the memos taken during the interview are also typed up and saved in the same pattern.

i. Transcript of Audio Recordings of Interviews

Writing the memos after listening the audio recordings of the interviews conducted with the participants is known as transcript of interviews (Kvale, 1996; Kvale and Brinkmann, 2008). Making a transcript is very important phase of the research as analysis of the data starts from this phase. Changing over of the data from recorded to hard copy, makes it easier to interpret and understand. Instead of using the recorded forms of interviews, making transcripts is an explanatory procedure as well as very complex and essential phase of the research (Grundmeyer, 2013; Kvale, 1996).

In the beginning of the data management, the audio recording of all the interviews were replicated and saved properly in order to protect and prevent the data from damaging (Nizar Souiden; Marzouki Rani, 2015). The process of the transcript of interviews illustrated in two steps which are as follows (Nagy, Biber and Leavy, 2006).

a) Forming the Exact Transcript

This is a full-length interview containing all the details in-depth such as any sounds, unfinished sentences, indications, informal discussions and dealing with the clients, in short this is the exact copy made of each and every interview (Lin, 2001).

b) Analyzing and Adjusting the Transcript

The exact transcript was analyzed and adjusted compared to the original audio recording of interviews. This is done to make sure that the true meaning of the interview is transcript and to avoid missing any information. If the interview was conducted in Urdu language (with South Asians), translation was done accurately. After all the analyses and adjustment was done the files were stored and labeled as “transcript of adjusted copies”. Finally, all the transcript was listed and documented to use in the later step of analyzing the data. This phase of transcript the interviews recording is a lengthy and tiring process, and if the interview is comprising of an hour, it normally takes several hours to transcript (Hove and Anda, 2005).

ii. Documenting the Compulsory Information

All the compulsory information regarding the interview and participants was also documented in each transcript, in order to use it if required in latest stages of the research. It is recommended to add a cover sheet which include all the compulsory information of the participants such as gender, age and ethnicity. This information can be used to create groups of the participants according to a specific topic, time, date, location and language of interview and are being useful at the time of data analysis (Crocker, 2009). Groups are made according to the cultural background, spoken language, (For example; all Urdu speaking in 1 group, Hindi speaking in another group).

4.14 Data Analysis using Qualitative Research Method

Thematic Analysis, with three coding matrix is used to analyze the data. Data coding was done manually.

The qualitative data collected was analyzed by using thematic analysis in which firstly the researcher identified the themes in the collected data, second stage is to label and organize the themes, third is to analyze the themes and in the end the completely analyzed data which was added in the research results (Komori, 2016). In thematic analysis the first step is to thoroughly understand the basic components of the collected data, and to recognize the components which are more evident. The researcher must know the type of data for example it is collected by interviews, observations or questionnaires. The researcher should be confident about the credibility and reliability of the data and that the data was collected in the best possible way. The researcher ensures that the data is not missing or loss (Ahmed, 2010). The second step to develop the themes and coding for the data and the researcher has to make sure that none of the data will remain un-coded. The third step is to name the codes and lastly is to analyze the data by names. After complete analysis the researcher will be able to draw the results (Ryan and Bernard, 2003).

The transcripts of interview, audio recording, field memos and any documents taking during the interviews is known as Qualitative data. The technique and method implemented to understand and to make sense of the data and the social incidents occurred. The term “analysis” is comprising of two words “ana” means above and “lysis” means to clarify (Dey, 1993). Moreover, data analysis dememos to divide the data into a small integral parts to better understand the facts and features and when joining those parts together to be able to understand the data (Sue Marlow, 2016; Patton, 2002). The procedure of generating, breaking up and regenerating the data converts the unprocessed data into significant results (Suri, 2011).

The selection of the technique used to analyze the data is dependable on the objectives of the research and also the method used to collect the data. The most appropriate technique of data analysis is grounded theory for this research (Kirkham, 1987).

4.15 Grounded Theory

This research is exploratory in nature and the grounded theory is selected to analyze the data. The continuous evaluation of the data may expose the underline ideas which will lead to get note-worthy and developing information (Bergman, 2010). Grounded theory is a type of Qualitative data collection method, which means to generate a theory by research which is grounded in the data. This theory comes out as a substitute to the conventional methods of data analysis which was usually comprises of testing hypothesis, authentication processes and Quantitative types of data analysis which was specifically used in social sciences. The grounded theory was issued by Barney Glaser and Anselm Strauss in 1967 (Furber, 2010). This was their official explanation of managing and understanding the Qualitative data, which was used whilst doing an observation of the participants in the research, this was done in the beginning of 1960’s. This research technique was described as an inductive invention of the theory derived from the data which was collected analyze systematically (Locke and Locke, 2001). The purpose of the grounded theory is to inquire about the reality in the natural setting, gathering information in a situational way and reinstating the collected information. Especially in social setting this theory seeks for the perspectives of the people which regulates the reason of their actions (Strauss and Corbin, 1990; Glaser and Strauss, 1967; Birkinshaw, Brannen and Tung, 2011). This theory progresses continuously during the research due to the interchange of the analysis and collection of the data (Glaser and Strauss, 1967; Glaser, 1978) (Charmaz, 2006; Bryant and Charmaz, 2010). It needs the identification of the investigation which is mostly attached to the background and the realities should be considered according

to the significance as well as the theory. Therefore, the grounded theory is originated from the data and explained by individual paradigms of the data (Glaser and Strauss, 1967).

i. Variations of Grounded Theory

Grounded theory was formed by Glaser and Strauss in 1967, on the basis of social research methodology which has progressed with the time. This progression promotes by different opinions from the beginning and known as the Strauss and Corbin methodology, Glaser methodology, deviated from the initial opinion which Glaser and Strauss introduced together. The archaic methodology of Glaser and Strauss was focused on that the researcher should enter in the field with no advanced hypothetical expectations, the participant's plan the research, and the researcher can only represent the actual analysis of the participants based on realism (Glaser and Strauss, 1967). Although, Strauss disputes that a general opinion should previously present in the mind of the researcher before entering in the field, on the basis of that opinion the researcher will be able to adapt according to the plan of the research. The methodology altered by Strauss and Corbin, emphasis on the significance that the researcher should always represent the analysis of the participants based on realism and should not be compromised during the research (Strauss and Corbin, 1990). However, Glaser's methodology depends on continuous evaluations of instances, opinions and the interactions. These variations are useful to detect the unpredictability, gaps and challenges. On the other hand, Strauss and Corbin methodology utilizes a particular set of investigative and technical phases (Harrison and Roomi, 2011). They were determined to facilitate the researchers during the phase of analysis, which comprises of in-depth investigations and processes. Therefore, they depend on a well-structured coding system that is "open", "axial" and "selective" coding system. Glaser make the use of a word "foil" theoretical explanation in order to indicate the similar theory but he was focused on authentication of an evolving theory which was critiqued by Strauss and Corbin.

According to Strauss and Corbin, the grounded theory presented by Glaser focused on an authentication instead of finding of new perceptions in the collected data for the research (Ponterotto, 2015). While field notes for meetings and center gatherings are best recorded quickly, contextualization of the examination might be a recursive cycle all through the investigation, with relevant data added dependent on member remarks (Worthington, 2009).

A new division of the grounded theory was presented by Charmaz, other than the authentication theory and the theory initially originated by Strauss, Glaser and Corbin. Charmaz presented "objectivist" and "subjectivist" grounded theory (Charmaz, 2006). The

“objectivist” approach of grounded theory established on the basis of positivist practice considering the researcher reserved professional who finds the real data regarding inevitable World. While, a “constructivist” grounded theory, focuses on the observable fact of the research and considers the evaluation of the data generated by mutual understandings and the associations with the partakers and the resources of the data (Charmaz, 2006). A “positivistic” method presented by Strauss suggests already structured coding system whereas Glaser’s type of coding methods does not incorporate grounded theory and is not able to adhere to in an inflexible method (Bryant and Charmaz, 2007). In the “constructivist” grounded theory presented by Charmaz, stated that the participants and the researcher both mutually creates the idea of social realism, in the research (Charmaz, 2006).

However, the constructivist approach of grounded theory presented by Charmaz, allows the researchers to be inductive and flexible in analyzing the data. Implementing these statements to give support to the grounded theory, goes well with the aims and objectives of this research because the constructivist approach offers open and adaptable method in the field and also during the process of analyzing the data. Appropriateness and the selection of Charmaz’s constructivist approach of grounded theory in this research is discussed thoroughly in the next section.

ii. The Selection and Appropriateness of Charmaz’s Constructivist Approach of Grounded Theory

Charmaz’s constructivist approach is used in this research because of a number of reasons. Prior to the start of this research, the researcher was already emphasizing on the aim of the research that is to investigate the issues and barriers encountered in their businesses by South Asian and African Caribbean female entrepreneurs. The context of the research clarified after using the systematic coding method of the grounded theory. Therefore, the wider context of the research turns into a detailed version due to the use of the coding analysis system of the grounded theory. It does not only simplify the wider concept of the research as well as the context became more comprehensive identifying the more specific indication of the issues and barriers of the South Asian and African Caribbean female entrepreneurs in the United Kingdom. By using Charmaz’s adaptable investigative and explanatory method the researcher and the participants was able to mutually build and understand the social realism. The adaptability of constructivist approach of the grounded theory is matched with the vigorous concept of the exploratory type of this research.

4.16 The Systematic Coding Methods used to analyze the Data

Coding is an active and adaptable systematic process which gives a connection among the theory and the data (Lye, Perera and Rahman, 2006). Coding dememos that grouping of the sections of data using a concise name which at the same time sum up and explains each section of the data (Charmaz, 2006). Three types of coding system are present in the grounded theory such as line by line coding, focused coding and theoretical coding. Line by line coding includes evaluation of the data in the textual form that is making a transcript of the data using line by line coding to detect the primary perceptions and codes. The primary perceptions were evaluated in-depth by a researcher in order to identify the relationships and variations to create a set of same perceptions. Secondly the focused coding method is used to characterize the explanation of theoretical relation among initial coding which lead to create substitute groups (Neale, Thapa and Boyce, 2006). These groups presents well-structured data which was broken up at the time of initial coding (Henderson, S., Segal, 2013). The last phase was theoretical coding which includes to identify a potential relation among the groups which assist the researcher to build description according to the combination of the initial coding groups (Charmaz, 2006). It's not necessary to use all three types of coding system in the final steps. During the single coding phase the researcher mostly use initial and focused coding systems, although these two coding systems are mainly used in the initial analysis process but can also be used at the time of theoretical coding (Klein and Müller, 2019). The analysis of the data using the coding system is discussed in detail in further section.

i. Line by Line Coding System (Initial Coding)

There are two stages in line by line coding system, use to create transcript of the interviews conducted with the participants. The stages of line by line coding are as follows:

- a) Analyzing the transcripts of interviews by using line by line coding system and the formation of the initial codes.
- b) Creating the groups of initial coding, by using the same perceptions to create a focused coding (Charmaz, 2006).

In-depth evaluation of line by line coding system was done in order to make sure that none of the perceptions is missing from the interviews conducted with the participants. The perceptions were deeply evaluated and the comparison was done in order to detect resemblances and dissimilarities present in the social incidents.

The interpretation of all the transcripts was done by using the procedure of line by line coding system which results in the development of numerous codes for every interview.

The next step was to list every transcript individually and give numbers to create the groups in order to make them easy to interpret in a systematic way.

The in-depth evaluation of initial coding system assists the researcher as the grouping codes developed from the data, creates the base and emphasis on the additional investigation of the area of research. Certain initial codes suggest the issues of South Asian and African Caribbean female entrepreneurs, with which an important section of the research was developed. The researcher was able to make perspective regarding the issues and barriers of South Asian and African Caribbean female entrepreneurs by using the data and being adaptable to catch the indication and the clues, in order to explore the research area in more depth (Neider, 1987). All the interviews conducted during the data collection, were transcript by using the initial coding. After the initial codes were developed from the transcripts, the general opinions were separated into a group and the same opinions were bunched together in order to create the base of focused coding.

ii. Development of Substitute Groups by using Focused Coding System

By the comparison of bunched up groups of initial coding, created basic groups of focused coding system by which understandable opinions were developed.

The focused codes are based on the abstract of opinions as the emphasis is on the coding system to integrate the data expressive and significant sections. To make sure that the codes are presenting the true perceptions of the participants, a comprehensive comparison of the interview transcripts was done. Similarly, all the bunched up initial codes were categorized into sets, after the comparison of the data developed from the focused codes which was again categorized into higher order sets. To summarize the relation between the sets, the researcher separated them according to “how”, “when”, “why”, “where”. The answers of these questions assist the researcher to conceptualize the developing incident and the relationship with the collected data (Sara Carter, 1992). The development of the questions was dependable on the contextual sets in the research. Every focused code was validated opposed to the data and the comparison with the rest of the codes to clarify if any additional bunching of the same codes is feasible. The questions allow and assist the researcher to identify the basic idea of every focused code and the connection with the consecutive codes.

4.17 Memos and Diagrams Designed during Data Analysis

The memos are the information written during the procedure of analyzing the data, diagrams are used to visualize the relation between the developing opinions at the time of analyzing the data (Charmaz, 2006; Corbin and Strauss, 2008). The researcher used these means which are very useful and assist the procedure of analyzing the data. Although, there is no specific guidelines available on writing the memos or designing the diagrams, it's totally up to the researcher how to determine the usage of these means to make the process of the research more precise by using his/her own skills and abilities. The memos and diagrams are designed to assist the process of analyzing the data in this research (David Grant and Kotazab, 2010). The memos were inscribed during the entire procedure of analyzing the data which were diverse according to the opinion and subject. The next theoretical stage of the research was directed by these memos. Initially these memos were explanatory but in the later step of analyzing the data they became precise and more to the point. There are three types of the memos such as **code memos, theoretical memos and operational memos**, which are used in theoretical procedure in order to record the procedure of developing a theory.

Code memos are linked with the description of various codes while theoretical memos were used to record the standard characteristics of the procedure of analyzing the data, through documenting the theoretic and proposed relation among the codes and the groups (Pandit, 1996) (Parker and Rofifcy, 1997). The operational memos were used to document the emerging research design by the use of the grounded theory (Corbin and Strauss, 2008). The diagrams and models were used to outline the relation among the substitute groups which was very helpful and enables the researcher to present the opinion by inspecting their theoretical connections. By using this model attempts to visualize the relation between the groups such as cultural concepts, the selection of career and the selection of business sector, by South Asian and African Caribbean female entrepreneurs. The model also depicts the influence of these groups on the basis of gender, religion and social context of the participants. By elucidating the configuration, this model clarifies the purpose of the presence of the South Asian and African Caribbean female entrepreneurs in the specific business sectors. Moreover, this model provides an exact information that why the female entrepreneur from ethnic minorities decides to commence or expand their businesses in the same sector. This decision is inspired by gender, religion and social context. Another same model was designed to detect the analytical relationship evolving from joining the groups together.

4.18 Theoretical Coding Integrating the Analyzed Data

Theoretical coding includes clarifying the theoretical relation among the groups created during the focused coding system. This step of coding includes merging the groups on the basis of contextual and theoretical relations which evolves during the procedure of analyzing the data (Flick, 2019). A theoretical model which was developed due to the integration of the groups, which was not decided previously or enforced by the researcher.

Initially three higher order groups were evolved from the focused coding system. These groups contains the contextual ability which allows the groups to influence the rest of the linked groups in order to articulate the theoretical model and to make the theory (Dingle, 2014).

4.19 The justification of Reflexivity

The Qualitative research illustrated by the human-being encounter (Finlay and Gough, 2003) where indicating the responsibility and dedication of the researcher with the research participants is imposed by an informative interpretation of the facts and data (Caverly, 2019). Reflexivity denotes to critical examination of one's own beliefs as a researcher, the "human as instrument" (Denzin and Lincoln, 2005:210). The responsibility of the researcher during the research, especially while collecting the data, the understanding of the research setting, participants and the researcher personal profile, fit in the community being researched, requires researchers thoughts on the research procedure. This is accomplished by the explicating the influence of the researcher on the participants and their reaction and observations and the research setting. In this research, open ended in-depth interviews were conducted during the process of data collection. Throughout the interview, the researcher's responsibility was to raise probing and enquiring questions, in order to get complete information of the facts and events under research. During the interviews with the participants, identification and perception of the research conditions and subject is not pre-decided but can be discussed (Finlay and Gough, 2003:103). The researcher already has a point of view, expectations, preconceptions and thoughts have an effect on the interviews with South Asian and African Caribbean female entrepreneurs. As the researcher being from Pakistan, have an idea regarding the culture which has a benefit that she understands the issues and barriers linked to South Asian ethnicity. Previous information and experience regarding societal life of South Asians especially Pakistani women. Due to this it was easy to contact and connect with them. These perceptions are gentle and kind but they did not judge or alter the informational outline of this research. It's recommended that while entering in the field of

research, the researcher should be with unprejudiced and should not entered with a meaningless brain (Fetterman, 1989:11 cited in Padgett, 1998). Though, in order to discover and investigate the research field with this frame of mind was not clear-cut and easy. The impact of theoretical constructivist approach was recognized at each step in designing the interview guide and discussed in the finding section. Numerous issues were faced by the researcher, during the research, along with few benefits. For example, the researcher went through a hard time in order to encourage the female entrepreneurs to take part in the interview as they were not being exposed to the research before and were reluctant to share their experiences, issues and barriers. The introduction and advantages of the research was explained by the researcher to the female entrepreneurs, in order to boost their responsibilities for the improvement of their community. Even though, this exercise turns out to be successful and the researcher was able to find the participants for the research but there is a draw- back related to it and this can be taken as biasness by the researcher that the participants were convinced to be a part of research. There is the possibility that the researcher could be judged and critiqued on the basis of unfair and controlling behavior for the benefit of getting the participants and de-shaping of the consent (Padgett, 1998:36).

The researcher uses numerous ways in order to find the participants for this research and each participant agreed to it and taking part in the research was their own decision. The consent form was presented to the participants along with the introduction of the research and each participant was fully aware of the purpose of the research. The privacy of the participant was assured by keeping their information anonymous, instead of using their actual names a substitute names were used during the research. On the other hand, the positive aspect of this is that the researcher belongs to the same cultural background that is South Asian, the fears of the participants was totally understandable and suitable tactics were implemented to manage and alleviate the fears of the participants of the research. For example, in the South Asian culture the family has a significant impact and discussing the facts in a subdued manner and emphasizing any discouraging and bad sentiment regarding their families is not acceptable and does not exercise ideally. Same is the case with African Caribbean culture if they are into their family businesses, they mostly hesitate to discuss the facts.

However, the researcher was looking forward to discover the impact of the family and their culture especially when the female entrepreneurs are running their family businesses. In order to achieve this probing questions were asked in open ended in-depth interviews, by making sure that their emotions were not muddle up and they won't get upset but to provide the insight

of the issues and barriers faced by South Asian and African Caribbean female entrepreneurs on the basis of their families. Moreover, the participants especially females from South Asian background was more comfortable to speak openly with the researcher from the same ethnic background that is Pakistan, who was able to make sense of their uneasiness, the language they speak that is Urdu and a better understanding of their religious and cultural structure in which they function.

The drawbacks of being from same ethnic background, the researcher and the participants did not pay attention to some of the issues and barriers related to the culture and they were taken as normal because both the researcher and the participant were fully mindful of the morals, customs, cultural standards and the way they live their lives. Just 20% of the example (the individual flexibility searchers) settled on a cognizant choice to enter business to profit with the opportunity to pick their own sort of work, hours, climate and associates. The ladies in this classification had recently experienced dissatisfaction in paid work and presently wanted the chance to deal with their work space and the kind of business (Roomi and Parrott, 2008). The participants make the use of sentences such as “you have an idea about our culture” these sentences, encouraged the researcher to enquire more by using probing and prompting questions with the participants, in order to investigate further about an embedded fact as the interview continued. There were chances to overlook some facts if the researcher does not have the prior knowledge regarding the cultural background and comprehensive explanation might be ignored by the participants. The correct reactions of the participants regarding the research were truly conveyed due to the use of the reflexivity approach of Qualitative research method. Inadequate appearance of the researcher might turn out to be a specific role in the participants life, which as a result alter their reactions consequently (Rossman and Rallis, 2003).

The impact of the researcher on the participants was varied and the participants reacted and replied according to the sensed expectancy of the researcher by telling the stories with which their cultural characteristics were represented deeply. Few participants were resistant to tell their stories during their interview, be a sign of obvious thought that they are not trusting the people from the same background in this story the researcher was not particularly interested and this was not the topic of investigation in this research. Despite the fact that the researcher’s unintentional and unplanned impact on the participants was inevitable. This was dealt with the use of the investigative approach of the grounded theory in which continuous contrast of the stories occurs. This enables the researcher to recognize the cases in point. Moreover, the

notes taken during the interviews, memos and the interview recording, assist the researcher to observe the field of research extensively.

4.20 Chapter Summary

In this chapter, primary Qualitative methodology highlighted in detail. Subjective ontological hypothesis of the researcher, the social constructivist epistemological method was used to explore the issues and barriers faced by South Asian and African Caribbean female entrepreneurs in their businesses. Specific approaches were used in this research were detailed, which are implemented in this research from numerous options on hand contain by the reality of Qualitative research method. The selection of South Asian and African Caribbean female entrepreneurs, as an investigative group in order to analyze their problems was governed by the aims and objectives of the research. Purposeful sampling process with snowball sampling approach were used to employ the participants. Because there were no databases available to employ the participants, a framework was designed by using different methods to get in touch with the potential participants. This include different borough of London, agencies for developing the business, agencies for welfare and social life and the gatekeepers techniques. The data collection was done through open ended in-depth interviews, taken into consideration the duration, structure and place of interviews with South Asian and African Caribbean female entrepreneurs. Once the base of the research was established, the methods and procedures are used for analyzing the data such as coding system was discussed in detail. The implementation of constructivist approach of grounded theory to analyze the collected data through interview with South Asian and African Caribbean female entrepreneurs is also discussed.

Chapter 5: Findings

5.1 Introduction

According to the aims discussed in first chapter, research findings will be analyzed in the chapter below. Main entrepreneurship themes were emerged from the interviews reported in third chapter. Those themes are organized in the “*three thematic clusters*” and several tables of data. A detailed discussion regarding these themes is presented in this chapter to both the patterns emerges from the interviews conducted. The effect of “*Normative Institutions*” that is the group features and particular features. “*Regulative Institutions*” such as financial and government features. The succeeding chapters explain the themes identified by the study as well as the methods used to arrive at them.

5.2 Normative Institutions

This research is presenting the major barriers and prospects for female entrepreneurs emerges from “*Normative Institutions*” and the major themes emerges from this research are presented in the following Figure 2.

Figure 2 “*Normative Institutions*”

The main normative variables that affect FEs' entrepreneurial experience are depicted in Figure 2 of this research. As described in third chapter the “code”, “*Social Group Network*” created through evaluating several networks that the study's respondents had identified. The

results show that in addition to their personal family—parents, in-laws, husbands, and kids—South Asian women are also impacted by their distant families and social groups.

They are the resources of “social” and “economical capital”, although they were as well connected to societal expectations, for example impact of “Patriarchal Culture”, “Religion” and “Ethnic” biasness for gender. Identification of each code's central concept and connection to other codes was made easier through questioning and study. Such as,

1. What bridges and barriers were created by social networks for female entrepreneurs?
2. What are influences of these bridges and barriers?
3. What do they think about their position within their family and why they are required to stick to their ethnic background?

Due to this, I categorized “*Social Group Network*” (SGN) and “*Social Expectations*” (SE) underneath “*Ethnic Culture*” and gave normative institutions the title of the section. I have designed a table for “*Normative Institutions*”, which is displayed below and contains Summary findings for “*Normative Institutions*”, the method of coding and capturing important components of the respondents.

The research exhibits that “*Social Group Network*” are foundation of following sub-factors:

1. “*Social Capital*”
2. “*Economic Capital*”

The unwritten standards and uncodified criteria that specify each person's place in social groupings and have an effect on behavior. These had an effect on resource access in addition to the entrepreneurial process. FEs have access to quick funding for starting up and devoted family member or the neighborhood. Moreover, boundaries and societal expectations for women were also developed via social group networks. This was accomplished through social structures (patterned expectations entrenched in role systems), cultural attitudes, values, limits, and expectations. In South Asian culture, women are still primarily responsible for the family, the kids, and the home. The effects of normative institutions are summarized in the table below, and they are covered in more detail in the sections that follow.

5.2.1 Influence of Normative Institutions

<i>“Ethnic Culture”</i>									
	<i>“Social Group Network (SGN)”</i>						<i>“Social Expectations (SE)”</i>		
	<i>“Social Capital”</i>			<i>“Economic Capital”</i>					
<i>Participants</i>	<i>Close Family Members</i>	<i>Distant Family Members</i>	<i>Acquaintances</i>	<i>Close Family Members</i>	<i>Distant Family Members</i>	<i>Acquaintances</i>	<i>Patriarchal Culture</i>	<i>Religion</i>	<i>Ethnicity</i>
i	Partner Child	Partner Family	Acquaintances in the UK and country of origin	Partner		Acquaintances	Had to take care of the family which comes first and closed her business due her partner sickness		
ii	Father and Mother Husband- to-be		Acquaintances	Parent			-	-	Her mum was expecting that she can work full time instead of being a business women
iii	Partner		Acquaintances	Partner			Partner was taking care of the finances involved in the business, he was		

							supporting her in starting the business		
iv	Partner	Partner Family	Acquaintances	Partner	Partner Family		Kids comes first	The society was pressuring her that she was working with a particular section of Muslims	
v	Father, Mother & Partner			Partner			-	-	Being a young woman, the men in the society were not taking her seriously
vi	Partner		Acquaintances				Partner was not supporting towards her achievement that's why she divorced him. Problems were created by the males in the society as they failed to understand her		
vii	Partner	Partner					Partner and		Family always first

	Kids	Family	Acquaintances				kids were important than the business		
viii	Boyfriend & Mother		Acquaintances				Separated from her boyfriend because she had to travel for business commitments		
ix			Acquaintances				Teammate were not sure that a female can manage a business		
x	Partner Kids		Acquaintances	Partner			For her family comes first due to this she has not started her venture till her kids started their school		
xi	Parents & Sibling		Acquaintances	Parent			Elder brother was not willing that she can go to other city for studies and later to start her business	Elder brother was not willing	In her culture girls get married at young age so she was worried that her

									family will force her too
xii	Father, Mother and Sibling		Childhood Friend	Father, Mother & Partner		-	She was expecting that her partner will support her against her parents in leaving the medical field		She studies medicine because her parents want her to be a doctor and she followed. Then she started traditional business and later went into mainstream business
xiii	Parents, sister and husband to be			Parents, sister and husband to be		-	-	-	-
xiv	Family		Links of the friends	Partner who passed away		Links of the friends	Her partner died when she was forty five years old then her brother supported her in her business trips	No role of Religion in getting any new businesses or problems in running her business in fact Religion supported	Respect given to a widow in her ethnicity, with the passage of time she has become confident

								her when she was sad due to her partner death	
xv	Parent	Partner family and Grandparents		Parents husband	-		Her decision was impacted by a male family member	To follow family's ritual she was expected to cover herself	She was bounded by her Grandparents, father and mother

5.2.2 SGN – Social Group Network

That's obvious the most of the FEs gets financial and societal support primarily from their close family members (principally their partners or husbands to be), followed by other close relatives (parents, partner's family, and occasionally brothers, sisters and kids) who are covered below.

5.2.2.1 Family

The research demonstrates that the family expectations and opinion have a significant influence on FEs' entrepreneurial experiences in South Asian and Black Caribbean culture. In addition to influencing business choices, their norms and beliefs also define the general perimeter of social expectations on the basis of gender roles. Moreover it is demonstrating the complicated connection of female business owner with the family. Family members contributed both material (money, labor force, services, utensils, and properties) and insubstantial sources, it was noted (reputation, experience and network). As explored in the parts that follow, this had both beneficial (in relation to supporting gender boundaries) and harmful (in relation of establishing gender limits) elements.

As new firms were being developed, family gave the required suppleness in sources allocation in order to address uncertainties and hazards of the business. Additionally, being aware of any extra resources (such as vacant space or extra property) inside the family may open up new business options for a member of the family (Alsos et al., 2014). Various types of assistance from the family have been provided, includes supporting morally, giving time, commitment and support in the form of labor, and fiscal help.

Fiscal support in the form of giving money for starting a new business or growing the current business, by paying the expenses of living cost is exhibiting in the quotes below.

Respondent XV,

“The original funding was provided by my parents' money (wedding present). Later, I took out a loan from my husband, a doctor with a decent salary who had some funds and was prepared to lend me money.”

Respondent I,

“My husband would help me over weekends and my daughter who was 16 or 17 then would help me at the shows”.

Similarly, in the case of **Respondent XI**, where her family supported her financially to broaden her business.

“I then decided to create an online platform for all the relevant business, like florist, catering, marquee, cakes, etc. this was going to cost a lot of money. For this I needed further funding for which I asked help from my father who agreed”.

Respondent XIII was living with her family in order to save her living expenses,

“Thanks to my parents and my fiancé Ed, I was able to live nearly rent-free in Wales, which would not have been possible without them. Moreover, my sister in London, who provides me with a home when I need one.”

Another respondents, who comes from entrepreneur’s family, opens her first beauty parlor in her house. The Respondents occasionally employed their family members' free time and talents for their business. The statements below demonstrate how Respondent 1 made use of her daughter and partner’s time when they are free and Respondent X, made use of her partner’s DIY abilities and avoid spending funds when opening 1st salon.

Respondent I,

“My daughter, who was 16 or 17 at the time, assisted me at the events on the weekends in addition to my husband.”

Respondent X,

“He gave monetary support as well. He was quite helpful to me in setting up the salon because he is extremely skilled in DIY projects.”

Respondent V’s partner’s family look after her kids when required

“Then, my in-laws have done an amazing job. They could be your biggest backers in any endeavor. Consequently, I never had to worry about my kids whether I went out at night or on business.”

Respondent XII's business started from home

“At first, I utilized a separate room in my home for that. Transformed it into a lovely lounge where my clients could try on the outfits.”

This is the way, she can utilize extra funds to launch her firm, and after it has become reputable, she relocated to better facilities.

Respondent IV She worked in the firm owned by her father-in-law, and her partner was amongst the business partners of that firm, and in her leisure time she created a new business with her spouse. In other words, she quickly created a profitable business enterprise by using the networks of her in-law's company. According to Carter, this is an illustration of the possibility to start a new venture in an already running organization which serves as an incubator for a current business (2000). The development of her new endeavor was less risky and unclear since the new company made use of networks that were already available to the current company. She also profited from her prior job history at the family's operating company. In another instance, assets were handed down from 1st generation to the other generation; the respondent's father gave her, his legal practice, and she turned it into a prosperous enterprise. She had learned enterprise savvy from her dad, as stated in the following quotes:

Respondent V,

“After I graduated from law school, my father (a lawyer) started his own firm of lawyers. So, when he decided he didn't want to do anything with the business, that's how I became a business owner. I had the option of working for another company or starting my own business, taking over his company, and expanding it because the market had changed and he wanted to retire. I therefore took over his company.”

Social organizations, for instance, may serve as an inspiration for inspiration people. According to **Respondent XIII**, she stated

“My entrepreneurial mum, somewhat to blame. There have probably been a lot of events in my life. The competition in which I participated in entrepreneurship is perhaps the first thing. That was motivated by a teacher who inspired you to build a small company called "Cookit GB" that made it to the finals in London. As a group of 17-year-olds, we were treated at the Savoy and got to experience the high life of London, which was exciting. You will not get teacher like him who are ready to give you an experience of your lifetime. “

The study demonstrates that control of resources is mostly held by male family members in South Asian society as opposed to Black Caribbean society (father, father-in-law, and husband). These male members provided financial assistance to FEs, but they either provided no assistance or very little assistance with household chores and family logistics. Due to rigorous societal expectations and gender norms imposed by South Asian society, this occurred.

5.2.2.2 Friends and Community

In terms of giving ties to knowledge, other relationships, and social networks that have benefited the entrepreneurial process, friends' help has been more subdued but no less significant. According to this research, 2nd generation's female entrepreneurs are more dependable on their friends to get social and fiscal support 1st generation FEs, who mostly relied on direct relatives.

Respondent IV who is 1st generation FE said,

“I met a friend on a trip to Bangladesh who referred me to someone looking to invest in a UK-based company.”

Respondent II (2nd generation FE):

“So I phoned a slew of agencies in India. I had buddies with whom I went to university. So I contacted them and asked if they knew of any firms that could construct this website. Of course, they did, and all of them appeared to be authentic and spoke to some of them”.

Respondent V is a 2nd generation FE stated that through her friends she found contacts,

“I met someone from his university at one of his home parties. This individual was the director of their university's foreign office. I learned about the university's foreign activities from her.”

Respondent XIII (second generation FE),

“My mother's acquaintance referred me to another friend of his who is a true Guru in Wales in digital marketing and other such things, and he was the one who assisted me. Support from family and friends... In that regard, I am quite fortunate, as not everyone has that kind of support system available to them”.

Social groups are important at many phases, from identifying opportunities to starting a business. For instance, the FEs' ethnic community serves as marketing source, workforce has the specialized abilities needed to run a traditional firms, and occasionally a means of social mobility.

Respondent XIV,

“We have a wide community in this region, which makes it easy to find experienced individuals to assist me with making common jewelry designs.”

Most of the FEs particularly 1st generation, who has an experience of dealing with traditional businesses, setup their business nearer to their culturally dense society.

Respondent XII,

“The majority of the employees is Asian, primarily from India or Pakistan. We can only have individuals from that ethnic background since they need to know the language, names of wedding wear, gharara, sharara... and they are more comfortable with clientele”.

Social groups are responsible and helpful for advertising FEs businesses this is mentioned in the quotes below:

Respondent V,

“So, my job used to originate from community influences, opinion makers would recommend me, so it was word of mouth, you'd ask your uncle or father or the Imam or someone well known and he'd say Aina Khan and someone else would say Aina and you'd go well okay, two people said Aina... That's how word of mouth used to work”.

Hence, it is clear that social group networks, particularly those of close friends and family, offer FEs plenty of assistance and support during their journey of entrepreneurship. But, at the same time these social group network also impose limitations & obstacles on FEs.

The patriarchal norms of their native South Asia are still present in the South Asian's, traditionally in the United Kingdom, men are viewed as the family's providers and decision-makers, while women are expected to take care of the household. This is obvious from the discussion done earlier regarding the supporting function of social group networks, patriarchal attitudes have an impact on women's entrepreneurial processes as both a facilitator and a constrictor.

Respondent XI, her close family members supported her financially to spread her venture, later mentions during her interview,

“I'm feeling thrilled about my accomplishment and want to expand, but my family has just been placing pressure on me to marry. My mum is even reaching out to family and friends to locate a suitable match for me... I'm concerned that if I marry, my husband would have different opinions about my business... What if he refuses to let me work?”

Therefore, similar social group network that is partner, parent, sibling, and husband to be are establishing gender limits; traditionally, this is anticipated that South Asian woman should marry prior to reaching to a particular age. Some activities are prohibited for women because they are judged undesirable by social norms, particularly when sources should be drawn back to the men line “*Patrilineage*” and if a woman lives with or is close to, her partner's or parent's group “*Patrilocality*” (Welter et al., 2003; Emrich et al., 2004). Respondent XI therefore believed that she is under marital pressure from her family. In addition to helping, South Asian male family members also define the roles and obligations that the family's female members must fulfil.

This is mentions in the quote below, that a marital partner observed supporting his wife because he knows that his wife is tired and she is able to cook, even though normally this is

expected from the woman in the family. This is because South Asian male dominant societies place a great deal of value on a husband's attitude and expectations.

Respondent II said,

“Yes, this is a big help if your partner is supporting you and not expecting me to cook biryani or other such things... so if I had a bad day, I always comforts me by saying that, "No, you're not doing it; I'll do it."

The above quote showing that this is their partner's decision that they have an ability to be an entrepreneur then only they will permit them to continue with their enterprise.

Respondent X,

“My husband was very supportive then, as he had seen the potential in me”.

The majority of the FEs said that they could not have continued their business without the assistance of their male family members. In other circumstances, these expectations resulted in gender limits, which are described in depth in section 4.3.2.

Individuals are regarded to be constrained by network relationships but also having chances to perform activity (Welter et al., 2003). This is observed in the research, that similar social circles that encouraged these entrepreneurs, discourages them as well, moreover no or less understanding regarding a venture or by pressurizing them, by putting hurdles in the journey of entrepreneurship. This is illustrated in the case of the Respondent V, that her partner who was supporting her financially to run her business, has consistently discouraging her as well.

Respondent V,

“So, at first, Naeem's negativity dragged me down every day. He'd tell me there was no money in my account... You owe money to others; your account is overdrawn, and so on... This negativity made me feel like I was failing at times... But I had to drag myself out of it afterwards”.

During her interview later she mentioned the name of her daughter

“I relied heavily on Naeem and Maham, and Naeem would always tell me that our business isn't earning much profit, you don't have business acumen or financial awareness, therefore you can't conduct business”.

The mental pressure she was subjected to regularly exacerbate that the emotional weight that she carried, was the price she has to pay in order to have the independence and the leisure to manage and run her business.

Other Respondent's family gave her the money for her business but also giving her mental pressure by discouraging her.

Respondent VI,

“One of my uncle in Manchester, and some of my cousins who are very established, told me, you poor thing, you're on your own and always to shatter my confidence... I felt that the more I visited them, the more they affected my confidence.”

The majority of respondents implied that this was the cost of the assistance their spouses provided in exchange for "allowing" them the freedom to work. As will be covered later in this chapter, men in the family can be hostile towards the achievements of FEs because of the potential displacement of their status. Social groupings thus provided FEs with both support and limitations.

However, throughout the time and during other events of life, FES encountered shifting expectations and boundaries. Training, knowledge, age, skills and experience may affect FEs' action to work together with both normative and regulatory organizations, as detailed in the sections that follow. As a result, societal expectations have a dynamic and hence temporal impact (such as, Respondent XI, mentions that her father's expectations and the religious boundaries placed by him and her brother were at last weakened with time passage and they accepted her as an entrepreneur).

5.2.3 Social Expectations

Businesspersons are frequently characterized as assertive, courageous, and able to take risks (Welter et al., 2003). In various civilizations, such as South Asian society, these traits are linked to masculinity (Marlow, 2002; Ahl, 2003). Female entrepreneurs are constrained by this stereotype of entrepreneurship, which may also affect how they deal with other company

shareholders such as dealers, financiers, and possible buyers (Fagenson & Marcus, 1991; Ufuk & Özgen, 2001; Bird & Brush, 2002; Langowitz & Morgan, 2003).

Tasks are explicitly formed or can develop unofficially with the passage of time via contact, differing expectancies, or by developing to serve as a behavioral guide, as stated in the review of literature chapter two (Blau & Scott 1962/2003). “Normative Institutions” can control social conduct (via obligations, mandates, and responsibilities), but they also empower and permit social activity (through privileges, rights, and licences). The uncodified attitudes and ideas that are ingrained in a society and serve to provide appropriateness are of importance to the normative institution (Scott, 1995; Welter et al., 2003). When normative standards and expectations are upheld, they become broadly accepted and take on the role of rules in society (Covaleski & Dirsmith, 1988). People adopt these principles as their own and abide by their limitations. Such as, in South Asian culture, honor of the family should always be taken into consideration, and avoid certain actions which are not permissible in their society and religion.

The sub factor of “*Patriarchal Culture*”, “*Religion*”, and “*Ethnicity*” further divided into the factor of Social Expectations according to the structure I have constructed in the table above. In the time of limiting and enabling the known effects on FEs, each sub-factor is significant.

5.2.3.1 Patriarchal Culture

The societal expectation is the same across all societies: entrepreneurs are traditionally seen able to take risks, are hostile, and brave, these attributes are linked with men (Kerr et al., 2018). This sexism of entrepreneurship restricts the kinds of businesses that women are expected to start as well as how they may engage with other company players (suppliers, investors, customers). This is considered to be severe discrimination against female business owners. All of the research subjects were significantly impacted by this aspect. Depending on each person's unique qualities of the personality, this will be covered in more detail in the following section, as well as level of education, relationship status, age and experience all of these had varying degrees of impact on their entrepreneurial process.

The quote below showing that “Social expectations” and “gender boundaries” influenced determination of expanding her venture, because first her duty is to take care of her family and also take permission from her partner.

Respondent VII,

“My salon quickly became successful, and after a few years, I realized it was too small for the quantity of clients I was receiving. However, I was unable to grow at the time

since my older son was studying for A-levels and I needed to focus on his education. I knew my husband's work was more essential, so I basically kept my business running at the same level for a few years. During that time, a chance to purchase a larger store for the salon arose, but when I addressed it with my husband, he felt it was not the proper moment”.

When it was convenient for the entire family, she moved on to the next phase of her business. In both Caribbean and South Asian cultures, the needs of the family come first. Thus, everything else, even work, must wait when a close family member needs the FE. Another reason why FEs are affected by their normative institutions is because of this.

Later she said that her partner's She further said, when she has got some experience and success, her partner's expectations and way of behaving was changed.

Respondent X,

“My company was performing extremely nicely... And my spouse quit his job a few years ago to help with admin, accounting, and IT setup for the firm”.

The expectations of the society regarding female entrepreneurs particularly important since they reinforce the previous outcomes of the literature study, such as “*Patriarchal Culture*”. In South Asian and Black Caribbean societies, men has more power than women “patriarchy”, and grown persons have more power than children (Protto et al., 2013). This research found that normative limitations are enforced in a variety of ways by parents and siblings, such as an indirect warning of socially isolation if FEs do not comply with those standards. FEs are so ingrained member of the family and are not able to separate them from their family. They acquired this way of thinking that dominance from men is embedded in patriarchal society.

This was noted that during their entrepreneurial process, all the decisions related to their business were taken by men or older family members.

Respondent X,

“During that time, a chance to purchase a larger store for the salon arose, but when I addressed it with my husband, he felt it was not the proper moment”.

Respondent XV,

“My mother spoke up for me and obtained approval from the family elders (my father, and grandparents)”.

Specific behaviors are associated with certain player through common knowledge, and therefore functions evolve, for example what is the role of a woman as compared to a man in a society. Player who adhere to the usual patterns and line of actions are able to link, whilst if they don't are more likely to experience violence. South Asian and Black Caribbean women, as stated in Chapter 2, are likely to keep the family intact (Janjuha-Jivraj, 2003; Basu, 2004). According to the research, FEs suffered hostility from male family members for failing to meet their societal standards. Respondent XI, for example, had a disagreement with her brother over picking a university and subsequently starting her own business.

They prioritize their family's demands over their career, causing a functional disagreement (wife or mother against businesswoman).

Females are expected to act in ways that are incompatible of becoming an entrepreneur. This, once again, expected from the spouse, his family, and her own family.

Respondent XI,

“Because my brother does not feel that ladies should be allowed to leave the house... He holds fairly conservative beliefs... My father and older brother were opposed to me beginning my own business”.

In the case of few FEs their entrepreneurial susceptibility, their passion of being an entrepreneur stimulated them to cope within gender based restrictions.

Respondent VI,

“My spouse always thought of me as a challenge. So, if I tell him I want to go to university or whatever, he won't let me. So I took a couple degrees in design to keep myself busy and thought about doing anything other than being a dull housewife”.

In the above mentioned case, she accumulated experience and learnings and waits for an ideal time to launch her personal firm. As she has become a working women this will have some effects on her spouse's and his family's image.

Respondent V, mentions that

“They were happy with it, except for my husband, who believed I should be looking after the children because he earns enough to maintain the family”.

This was described in second chapter, this is man's duty to provide for the family rather than a woman in South Asian and Black Caribbean society. When a FE establish her own business and be a part of financial support required for their family, this considered as she is substituting a male member of the family from his status of being a provider and losing the control of the family which is a common practice of the society. Consequently, this shift in status might be the source of opposition from male family members, as demonstrated in the majority of the instances in our study. Furthermore, although they encourage and aid her, but they want to keep up the control of the family.

Respondent V,

“The thing with Naeem – he is a typical South Asian man... on one side they want you to develop and still want you to develop under their guidance... you cannot have your own mind... and because of that I did not have that much trust in myself that I will be able to survive without him. Initially everything was being decided by my in-laws”.

FEs knows that acting honorably and obey the rules, they are respected and honored, however when they break the rules, they might feel ashamed and dishonor. You would undergo self-evaluation in such a patriarchal culture, which can cause emotions of intense regret or poor self-respect. These feelings compel you to follow social conventions (Basu & Altinay, 2003). In order to care for their kids (remain at home), take care of husband's family, and heed their

mum's admonition that this is "not a smart" way of doing the job of their choice, many of the female entrepreneurs did all three.

In comparison to 2nd generation's entrepreneurs, these societal expectations were more deeply ingrained in the 1st generation of business owners.

Respondent XIV (2nd generation)

“My spouse provided no opposition at any point; he has been working and progressing in his profession and is now working as a consultant at a nearby hospital”.

Managing their own firm build up their burden significantly in certain circumstances. They had to manage their own business as well as their personal obligations. They couldn't ask for help since their societal gender norms require them to undertake all domestic duties.

Respondent VII,

“I was SO EXCITED when I started the course in 2000, but I never imagined that one year would be so challenging. Juggling so many balls and not being able to complain because I was constantly reminded that it was my decision and that I had complete control over how I balanced all of my duties”.

Thus, patriarchy of South Asian and Black Caribbean society, biasness on the basis of gender is evident in this research.

5.2.3.2 Religion and Ethnicity Factors

For some of the entrepreneurs, the “sub factor “religion” appeared to be significant (on a personal level), but it appeared to have little impact on the entrepreneurial process. It did, however, play a more subdued part in relation to destiny (accepting that whatever happened is God's will) and relieving the stress.

Respondent VI,

“My specialty is integrative development (individual and collective transformation). Sufi (Humanity Love) element... This aspect of my religious nature assists me in dealing with life's obstacles.”

Respondent X,

“But I think everything has its time nothing happens before that”.

Respondent XIV,

“My conviction and confidence in God are that He provides for everything and that if we do sabar (show patience), everything will be well.”

The preceding are described as Tawaqul, is a divine aspects in Muslims and in Sufism. Tawaqul is doing one's best while trusting and depending on Allah to bring the desired result (Jabnoun, 2008). However, one requirement is that someone try their best to fulfil the targets and then to do Tawaqul. As a result, some deeds are required in order to attain their aim. As can be observed, Tawaqul has an impact on the deed of a businessperson. Ahmad (2011), mentions that may be business traits may arise from Tawaqul are faith, self-assurance and positivism. The traits are related to the risk taking uncertainty.

Regarding a sub factor, “Ethnicity”, almost all entrepreneurs aimed the markets which have dense cultures ties, therefore this sub factor does not have any negative effects.

Respondent V,

“Being a woman and being of a specific race may have worked in my advantage. But, I am Pakistani (not fantastic), Muslim (really not great), and a lady, oh my God, then I look young and I am not that tall, I am just 5.2" and dont have that blondness. In that regard, I have nothing to offer. So why not use that to be remembered in a unique way? I believe that's where I have got the confidence from.”

Respondent V had a difficult battle because of the religion (was not in her favor at the time owing to specific incidences), being a woman (Those days, women in the United Kingdom, use to think that they don't have any advantage, particularly among South Asian groups), and being a young female (the absence of practice and experience in the profession of law which is led mostly by men and also from her society). She skillfully exploited those characteristics in order to set herself apart from them instead of them criticizing her inadequacy. Her accomplishment was on what she has accomplished provided faith that in spite of all difficulties, she can be successful.

5.2.4 1st vs. 2nd Generation Female Entrepreneurs

According to the survey, first generation South Asian and Black Caribbean, females mostly keep their businesses surrounded by their cultural groups, whilst the 2nd generations expanded in the main industries.

Respondent V (1st generation):

“...this was near Green Street in East London, and major enterprises like that don't exist in East London, especially in the 1990s, with a young lady operating it.”

Respondent XIII (2nd generation):

“...So, I decided to create an app as a route out of corporate life and a springboard to becoming a CEO.... My Finish Line is aimed towards anyone who is preparing for a marathon, triathlon, Ironman, or simply general fitness.”

It is observed that 2nd generation's FEs picked their line of work to go beyond the conventional service industries like retail and catering and into high growth areas like IT and business services.

Some reasons of doing this are (stated by the Respondents):

- Their education has been done in the United Kingdom,
- They are influenced by United Kingdom's culture, as they were born and grew up here,

- They have good command on English language,
- They are able to use advance technology and have easy access of the customers
- They have knowledge of what policies and financial support are available from the Government for ethnic minority's women in the United Kingdom.

As a result, 2nd generation's FEs feels that they are more secure in their surroundings in the United Kingdom.

Because of this, 2nd generation women retain their ethnic cultural values while also exhibiting confidence in themselves, empathy with United Kingdom's standards, and a feeling of belonging. Therefore, 2nd generation is incorporated but not completely absorbed by the institution.

A problem with the seen and felt multicultural pressures on the 2nd generation's FEs emerged from the interviews with second generation FEs.

Respondent XV,

“However, as there was no other option, I considered this a blessing in disguise (laughed)! I agreed to the marriage proposal on the condition that I talk with their kid beforehand. My family consented to this after considerable deliberation. When I met Ahmed, I liked him and he seemed like a really open-minded person, so I gently asked him about starting and operating my own business. He chuckled and indicated right immediately that he had no objections - this was a huge relief. I answered yes to my parents' proposal, and we married in 2009.”

She continued and said,

“We lived with Ahmed's parents during our first year of marriage. I couldn't actively start the business at the time since I had family duties and a lot was going on after the wedding.”

The cultural limits of their parents, families, and the South Asian community place around them frequently conflict with the British ideals they are subjected to beyond their households (the host culture). Such as, the South Asian society prioritizes deference to elders, particularly male family members, and unquestioning submission to higher authority, but British society supports defying and confronting authority.

Another illustration is the mandatory tradition of South Asian women upholding the "izzats" (family's honor) at all times by abiding by their religious and cultural traditions. An intriguing theme of this study is how 2nd generation's FEs facing biasness on the basis of gender, this perspective they are carrying as "cultural baggage" and their parents embedded this in them with regard to the British system. This is because every sector enforced the power of their social and ethnic distinctiveness on the entrepreneurial behavior (Harper, 2003). The quotations that follow illustrate the conflict.

Respondent XII talked about when she has to prove her integrity to her parents, by following their wish of her being a doctor,

“My parents constantly encouraged me to perform well in school because they wanted me to become a doctor as well. My father spoke with one of his acquaintances to learn about medical schools in Poland and encouraged me to apply. This is how I ended up in medical school. I finished my medical degree for my parents just to prove to them that I could become a doctor, even if my heart was not in it. I was always bored. I've always been fascinated in fashion.”

Male member of the family, regardless any age, hold the power to take decisions. Respondent 11 stated, "When I finished my A-levels and was accepted by a university in London, which was my first choice, my elder brother objected, so I had to settle for my second option of Swansea University, which was closer to our residence and I could commute from home."

On asking that why her brother was opposing it? She responded,

“Because my brother does not feel that ladies should be allowed to leave the house... He holds conservative beliefs.”

But as this Respondent make a decision to start her own venture, she has to encountered more opposition,

“My father reviewed my company proposal and agreed in general that it was a decent concept, but my eldest brother was opposed. At this time, I decided... since I had already

changed my mind about my university. I told him how I felt when I couldn't attend the university I wanted to go.... He was still not convinced. Finally, my father persuaded him. That was the most joyous day of my life. I was ecstatic to launch my own company."

To some extent, 2nd generation's FEs even have some regard and value their ethnic standards. With age, education and experience, gives her the courage to approach her elder her sibling (elder brother) who had objections regarding her thought of having her own business. This is worth noting when her mom had no say in the matter; she solely speaks about male family members. As seen by the following quotation, the 2nd generation is likewise extra conscious regarding their entitlements:

Respondent XIII,

"So, I was able to take a leave of absence from Amazon to attend the boot camp... The policy stated it in black and white. It was up to my manager's judgment, but I was doing it for educational purposes to further my career and had always been sort of a high performer, and they didn't really have any reason not to."

Therefore, the conclusion is that "Normative Institutions" have an important role in the journey of entrepreneurship in FEs life. "Social Expectations and "Gender Biasness" are two main constraints that FEs has to cope with during entrepreneurial process.

5.3 Regulative Institutions

Regulators are formal institutions that demand entrepreneurs to follow their regulations. They have an influence on the entrepreneurial process via elements such as the regulatory situations (regulations and the policies of the government and organizations providing financial support) and the services of the market. Taxation, regulations of the labor market, resources of financial policies, and the social security will all be regulated. United Kingdom's external environment impacts immigrants' entrepreneurial proclivity to advance in the community (Razin, 2022). Different ethnic groups are affected with these external environment in different aspects, as outlined in Chapter 2's literature review. According to Masure et al. (2004), these groups share cultural characteristics such as hard work devotion, being from the closely knitted community,

exploratory and can take risk aptitude, very clear societal standards, unity and faithfulness, and an innate entrepreneurial proclivity of immigrants to advance socially (Razin, 2002). As was already mentioned in Chapter 2 of the research review, these environmental influences have a variety of effects on various ethnic groups. According to Masure et al. (2004), ethnic groups share a number of cultural characteristics, such as a commitment to hard labor, belonging to a tight-knit ethnic community, the capacity to take risks, very clear societal standards, unity and faithfulness and a predisposition toward entrepreneurship. These qualities determine how the outside circumstances affect them as well. A complicated relationship between the opportunity structure, which includes market circumstances, regulatory institutions, and shared resources of the group (individuals from same background, social networks – *Normative Institutions*) determines whether ethnic firms are successful (Waldinger et al., 1990). According to this survey, regulatory institutions for every entrepreneur, although depending on normative conditions, its "use" varies.

The main regulatory institutions are “*Government Policies and Financial Institutions*” the way they effect the process of entrepreneurship are depicted in Figure 3 below. The table underneath summarizes that the way these regulatory institutions have affected society.

Figure 3 Regulative Institutions

The following Table presenting the influence of the Regulative Institutions over the interviewee's female entrepreneurs. Columns 2, 3 and 4 of this table are showing Financial Institutions and 5-8 Columns are showing policies of the Government.

5.3.1 Influence of Regulative Institutions (RI)

5.3.1 Influence of Regulative Institutions (RI)							
	“Financial Institutions”			“Government Policies”			
Participants	Means of Economic Capital	Gender Barriers	Cultural Barriers	Grant from the Government	Government Policies	Legal Assistance	Advice Centers
i	Partner Loan from the Bank, Own-finances	Partner help in taking the loan from the bank			Maintaining the quality, right of the customer	Tax return maintain by Accountant	
ii	Private financiers/Grants from Government Self-finance	Biasness on the basis of gender by the private financiers	No cultural biasness	Indirect financial support such as Barclays, PWC and direct financial support through Government	HR policies of the Government supported her to take some time out from her business		
iii	Self-finance and Bank	Bank like to interact with her partner	None	Not Applicable	Marinating the quality		
iv	Loans from the bank to support finances	None	None	Not Applicable	Due to high rates. She closes her businesses because of the changes in the Government policies		

V	Loan from the bank it was difficult to get grant from the Government. Nothing available for Entrepreneurs	Gender biasness in getting the grants from the Government	The grants and scholarship are given according to the gender and ethnic background	The grants and scholarship are given according to the gender and ethnic background	First business was affected due to the change in the policy that is Government has stopped legal Aid	Doesn't Available	
Vi	Grants from the Government and private companies	Gender biasness in her culture		She does not have any employability that's why she did not get grant from the Government			
Vii	Courses and funding from the Government own savings and loan from the bank			Training courses are available along with the funding from the local Government to help women in starting their businesses	Skills for free was a policy from Government which helped her	Assistance and help was available from the Government	
Viii	Finances from the Government			Grants from the Government supported her to start or broaden	The Government was asking higher education sector to		When I opened my company and registered it as

				her business outside the country	endorse United Kingdom education internationally and to discover opportunities in order to uplift income		limited set up office opening a business account everything was smooth other than seeking help for my business plan and maintaining the finances, local council was supportive
ix	She has got grants from charities trust, European commission and Government grants	None	None	Grant from European Government	Incorporation of business policies from the Government help her in her business		
X	Loans from the bank and self-funded	None	None	Free training courses were available from the Government	The accountant maintain the high taxes. She was not happy with the policy to verify the passport		

					and the immigration status of the employees		
xi	Financial support from father and Government	None	None	Grants from the Government			Starting up business scheme was funded by local Government which help her
xii	Own-finances	Not Applicable	Not Applicable	Not Applicable		Not required	Not Applicable
xiii	In the beginning own finances and private finances	None	None	Not Applicable	Rules applicable for online businesses were present but have no restrictions	Not required	Not Applicable
xiv	Own-finances	Not Applicable	Not Applicable	Not Applicable	Started her workshop in the United Kingdom because taxes on importing things were high	Not Applicable	Not Applicable
xv	Own-finances	Not Applicable	Not Applicable	Not Applicable	None	Took legal assistance regarding	Not Applicable

						corporate insurance	
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5.3.2 Financial Institutions

A limited part in providing money through loans made by the spouses of the female entrepreneurs was performed by financial institutions (banks). According to the survey, the majority of FEs either privately funded their businesses and avoided dealing the financial institutions otherwise had their spouses handle the fiscal aspects regarding thier enterprises. The example quote is below:

Respondent I,

“No, I did not utilize any financial institutions. The initial £30K I invested (from my spouse) was just rolling in the business. And I was making money, which I was reinvesting in the concerts because they would bring me more business...and I believe that because he had done finances in my life, I never attempted to do it myself...”

Respondent VIII,

“Anyway, I'm considering establishing my own offices in these nations. I'm still living with my mother, so I don't have many living expenses and no mortgage at the present. I was able to save some money from my business, which will allow me to realize my ambition of expanding my business.”

Respondent XIV is a 1st generation FE and Respondent I, response was negative as well when I asked her if she has dealt with some financial companies.

“No, since I started with my own money and then utilized the money created by the firm to expand. In that regard, I've been quite fortunate.”

Especially at the beginning of their operations, all FEs self-financed their businesses. Due to the loans' modest size, this was not a significant impact. However, as their firm expanded, they needed a large amount of capital to spend, and to do that 10 participants out of 15 participants, turned to their social networks such as family or their own resources. This is due to the fact that in accordance with traditional South Asian and Black Caribbean cultural values, families serve as a base of support for South Asian and Black Caribbean female

entrepreneurs, enabling them to quickly access capital for business start-ups and a labor pool of devoted family members.

Generally, entrepreneurs but especially women entrepreneurs, are reliant upon the framework where immersed from, so in this instance, it is the strong male dominant culture they have, their strong male-dominant cultural beliefs, as was addressed in Chapter 2. The kinds of businesses that FEs might pursue were determined by their level of embeddedness and societal expectations (which were covered in earlier sections on normative institutions). FEs could keep the company operating at a level where she could demonstrate her abilities as a responsible wife, a modest daughter, and a nice mother. Even when they put in the same amount of hours as their male spouses, women were still responsible for taking care of the home's aged, dependent parents, and children. They found it more challenging to reconcile their household and professional responsibilities as a result. Because of this intricacy, they could be more inclined to pick businesses that let them choose their own working hours. Additionally, this motivates kids to ask for assistance from their family.

The majority of the respondents received private finance, either from their families or their own funds, and was observed that 2nd generation's South Asian and Black Caribbean entrepreneurs were the ones that went to private investors and proposed their company ideas for investment.

Respondent II a 2nd generation FE use private investor for funding, very few FEs do that so she elaborated that:

“Then a network of friends told me about an accelerated program. Just Eat is a food incubator program in which they choose five start-ups, resulting in five food businesses. Every quarter, 200 to 300 persons apply. They choose five enterprises, offer £20,000, take 5% ownership, and assist your business expand. So, I had to propose my idea in front of a panel of four Just Eat entrepreneurs. Senior citizens. There was one lady and three males. Following that, there were two rounds of activities. Then there was a third round in which you had to pitch to a larger audience. So, we got in with 250 people. Five of us were chosen. This occurred in April of 2017.”

When she sought to develop her firm, she turned to private investors once more, "Putting money into paid promotion." And now only in London we have sixty bakers. Since our inception in May 2017, we have received over 230 orders. It is both successful and exhausting. We are currently out of funds. We've depleted our £20,000 budget. We are now looking into raising funds for our next round of investment.

Because 2nd generation born in Britain, FEs have more confidence in this country than their first generation, who have experienced a variety of settings and scenarios. With a far greater understanding of the local environment and no language hurdles, they have access to possibilities which was not available for the 1st generation (their parents), this is due to some of their personal and social reasons. The 2nd generation was much confident in pitching their ideas in the local language and had easier access to financing information through their university buddies' network.

Moreover, while interacting with the financial institutions, they don't have any concerns regarding their background and their gender, with the exception of two unsatisfactory remarks concerning the grants from the Government and the funding available privately. Respondent II was successful in obtaining private money, as seen by the preceding quotation, but she emphasized on that other individual counselled her regarding their experiences.

"I will provide you an example: my Chinese business partner is pregnant. We were supposed to meet with some investors last week, but the investor's buddy advised us not to attend since she is pregnant. Because doing so would jeopardize your prospects of receiving funds. And it is simply bad. She believed that being pregnant and having a kid did not exclude me from working. She was working till her water broke. She had her kid the night before".

5.3.3 Grants Offered from Government

In the majority of situations, government initiatives to give funding and schemes aided participants in their entrepreneurial endeavors. However, there were only a few occasions when some unhappiness was expressed, such as Respondent V, was not able to have a grant from the government, she expressed her disappointment by saying, "No, basis given!" And you are aware. Tony then told me that the reason he refused you, only due to the fact that she

will be successful anyhow. The money was handed to a man who had a bad concept will be a failure and will be unable to repay. "And that taught me a lot."

It was discontent along with the justification presented in this case rather than gender or race considerations. As a result of the normative criteria outlined in the preceding section, financial institutions had a small influence in the majority of cases.

Another issue raised by several FES was the difficulty of obtaining information about government subsidies and other programs available to assist fledgling enterprises. As seen by the quotations below, they discovered this knowledge either accidentally or through their social networks:

Respondent V,

"I went to the local government and had no clue how to approach them about expanding a tiny legal company."

"Why should you be unaware that there is a government initiative to assist you?" she said.

However, in the majority of cases, the FEs profited by engaging in the training programs offered by the Government, which provided them with the necessary expertise to establish and to maintain a successful enterprise, or they received the funding to establish a firm. The following quote demonstrates this.

Respondent X,

"Of course, I did a couple online and certificate courses, as well as an English language course at a local college. Without it, I would not have been able to obtain a license to practice as a beauty therapist".

In order to provide opportunities to ethnic minorities, funding is available from the Government to maintain their social and financial mobility. ***Respondent V,*** stated that,

"There was government backing. There are much more activities and programs than there were in our day. So, for a new person, say she's in her 20s, I'd say there's a lot more for a

young lady - of my gender and faith - she can start anything and people will say oh good, almost like a box ticking now, oh good. Muslim, female, and Pakistani ticks”.

For some of the cases, these free trainings, make it easy for FEs cope with the difficulties generated due to “normative institutions” as mentioned in the quote below.

Respondent VII,

“I then opted to pursue beauty treatment and make-up training. A friend of mine told me that the local government had funds available for women interested in starting their own businesses and doing skill-based training courses. I finally gained permission to take the course from my in-laws and hubby (in that order). I was given permission since it was free and there was no financial risk involved”.

Respondent VIII,

“The UK government encouraged UK higher education institutions to promote UK education abroad and to look for new ways to boost income. Finally, I discovered that grants were available for worldwide marketing for enterprises selling to other countries. I fell into that category since my company dealt with education exports. I was able to obtain this financing in order to visit to all three places.”

Therefore, the regulatory institutions helped them to build capacities in order to operate firms effectively and supported them to earn some capital, by guiding them and by developing some skills to cope with the hurdles created by social groups.

Remarks concerning “regulatory institutions” were generally constructive and created the sense that everything is same for everyone. As a result, the partakers were not subjected to biasness based on gender or cultural restrictions imposed on them.

This research found that 2nd generation’s people are more conscious about the rules & regulations which have direct influence on an environment locally, due to time, through financial activities and social contacts. The following quotations, making it clear that from 2nd generation’s FEs leveraged their entrepreneurial chances by using human resource rules

imposed by the UK government and large corporations. In both situations, they took a break from employment to obtain the necessary training for their future enterprises.

Respondent XIII who is 2nd generation,

“I have been with the firm for almost two years. So, the policy was quite clear. Written in black and white... I wasn't asking Amazon for money to do it. I was simply requesting unpaid vacation so that I could go and spend time doing it... I've always been a high performer, and they didn't really have any excuses not to.”

Respondent II talked about the same experience,

“So I asked my boss if I might take a six-month sabbatical, and he agreed. So I took a six-month unpaid vacation.”

5.3.4 Policies Introduced from Government

FEs briefly noted how the policies from the government influenced their enterprises, for example, one of the Respondent who used to have a law firm (when it was made difficult to get legal aid) and some others stated that this is due to “BREXIT” and high corporation tax although this was similar for all. Basically, all of them mentioned how simple it was to register the company and setup business accounts in the beginning. This refers to the simplicity with which a corporation may be formed, registered, operated, and lastly managed operationally. The majority of respondents had little trouble registering their business. Government policies facilitated this process for new businesses, as seen by the statements below.

Respondent II,

“At the present, all you need to become a baker and sell on our platform is a food and hygiene level 2 certificate, and you must be registered with your local municipality.” “That's one thing the government has done, another thing the government has done is that they have

put a lot of money into a lot of corporates, so there are a lot of Financial businesses like INVESTECH, Barclays, PWC," she added."

Respondent VIII,

"I formed a limited liability company, opened a business account, established an office, and hired an accountant (who was a family friend). Everything went nicely except for the fact that I needed assistance with my company strategy and cash-flow estimate. This support was available through local council".

In two of examples, concerns were shown that is during the early phases of creating their enterprises, namely the way to handle the hurdles created, as most of the only learned about these limits when they were confronted with them.

Despite this, I have to emphasize that the restrictions from the government are cited during these situations are applied to each firm, and the Respondents experienced no discrimination on the basis of culture or gender.

Respondent IV,

"As a result, the UK government halted all property shows on all networks, not just ours. There was a property channel on Sky that was also closed, so it wasn't just us, but all similar shows. This was mostly due to the scams that occurred in Dubai..."

Later in her interview, the same participant emphasized the health and safety rules of the government and misconceptions caused by ethnic dissimilarities, saying,

"Ofcom employees took it very seriously and undertook inquiry. They assumed that it was some type of stone and asked why I was recommending it. So we had to satisfy them by demonstrating what it was and how we Asians utilize it in our meals, among other things.

There were checks in place for those programs, and we had to be extremely cautious about what we said to them. They claimed that only qualified doctors could provide advice to anybody else. Despite the fact that many were benefiting greatly from it."

But, on asking that what does she think that was it fair for Ofcom in order to explore this problem, and her response was,

“Yes, I hadn’t done anything wrong, and they were investigating for good purpose then its fine. I don't think there was any prejudice against ethnicity”.

An exemplary quote is highlighting few traits of FEs character such as flexibility, suppleness and determinations.

Few of FEs were affected by the changes in the market and they were not able to manage or were not able to calculate the capital required to run their business, also due to the change in their supply change, as a result they had to close their businesses. Same was stated by **Respondent IV**,

“BREXIT has had a significant impact on our business, particularly because we have several homes that were rented out, but suddenly Eastern Europeans are returning and our residences are empty”.

Some of the policies from the government have damaging effects on FEs enterprises as this was stated in the quote below:

Respondent V,

“Economically, in 2007, 10 years ago, the government abruptly altered the legal aid regulations... so I had to reconsider, legal aid laws were modified, and we were making such fantastic money on legal aid because we were good at what we did”.

Further she said,

“Aah it's been quite a major shift... Being an entrepreneur, winning awards, receiving loans, repaying them, dealing with growth and all the compliance that comes with it, as well as HR, client service, and just growing up your firm, are all major changes. From then, your foundation is undermined because the things you accomplished mattered nothing, since your greatest revenue sources, legal aid, which accounts for 95% of your revenue, suddenly pulls on you. So, when the other enterprises that were similar to that went bankrupt, they all lost their homes”.

In the above mentioned cases, the FEs can carry on with their businesses by changing the business plan or by changing the style of their business.

Respondent V mentioned,

“So, I said I'm not going to wait for things to become worse because I could see it coming, saying, this is just the beginning of extremely awful times, things will change, and I was correct. Things drastically altered, legal aid deteriorated. Fortunately, I moved out just at the zenith of my company's popularity in early 2008, and I had to sell it as a continuing worry. I was able to pay off the loans. Thank God, I got away with izzat (honour)!”

The sense of entrepreneurship aided to overcome a difficult period in the development of this business owing a shift in the policy of government.

Respondent XIV was not saying something regarding “regulative institutions” openly, the I had to ask her an investigative question, that if she would like to comment on the policies of the government and anything about tax system, she then replied:

Respondent XIV,

"No, since they're the same for everyone. At times I think that they should lower the corporation tax to simplify the things for mini firms. It was simple to set up the corporation. Because health and safety regulations are so stringent in the UK, my manufacturing operations are constrained. Furthermore, the pay is really substantial. As a result, I only have extremely exceptional items created in the United Kingdom. The remaining jewelry is created in Jamaica. At times, I find an element of a piece of jewelry created in Jamaica and have it assembled in the UK for a client."

However, she, like others, verified that such regulations apply to everyone.

In terms of government policy, the majority of respondents thought that an equitable playing field was given for everybody. This is obvious from Respondent IX's statement,

"When it is what it is. If you return and offer proof for why the financing is required, and it fits the criteria in terms of the funding request, the funds will be approved. It is about recognizing the need, then making a business case for why the government or company money will assist address the issue that you have identified, and then evaluating the results. That is really

essential to me, and I don't believe it has anything to do with gender. I don't believe ethnicity has played a role because we are working with impoverished groups."

Therefore, this research demonstrated the federal and local government's "Regulative Institutions" does not have any restrictions on the plans of ethnic minority's entrepreneurs, for example, by means of inequitable registration process of the companies, their regulations, getting permits, duties on import, health and safety, business rates, restrictions on the parking, or minimum living wage.

5.3.5 Identification of Opportunities till Starting a New Business

In this research, every partaker demonstrated that all of them had to go through the entrepreneurial process, which included identifying and evaluating opportunities, developing a business strategy, determining the necessary resources, and managing their resultant company endeavor. The majority went through similar procedures, but what differentiated them was how diverse variables influenced their fulfilment of the vision they had and how they conquered the elements which were in their journey of reaching the desired goal.

There is no doubt, that all of the female entrepreneurs have conducted preliminary "market research" in order to find their company potential. It was not required from the conventional business school, that they have to have a formal knowledge, such as "PEST - Political, Economic, Social, and Technological, SWOT - Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats, business plan", but to have some casual knowledge, but this was associated with the availability of the financial source (which were low) and this was major barrier for them to enter in a business field. The quotation below depicts that a typical procedure through which most of the respondents went through was to find an opportunity for business and develop it to a proper company concept.

Respondent XI,

"I noticed a few Asian marriages at the hotel during those period. And these weddings had a few mishaps, for example, during one of the weddings, the wedding cake that they had purchased did not arrive on time, and on another occasion, the bride's carriage did not arrive. The English weddings, on the other hand, were well-organized... I decided to do some investigation to find out why this was the case. I discovered that Pakistani/Indian families

will spend thousands of pounds on wedding ceremonies, clothes, food, jewelry, and so on, but will not engage a wedding planner. Following further study, I discovered that there were no Asian wedding planners in Cardiff.”

Respondent XIV,

"I started my business at the correct moment since I recognized there weren't many individuals in my town who were interested jewelry at the time."

Respondent XIII,

“So, while I was in London, I had the chance to interview the creator of Tech Club, one of the most successful coworking spaces in London and throughout the world, and she informed me that they have a place in Swansea. So, I went there to try and network in Swansea to find some other entrepreneurs or other techy people in the part of the world to try and make a go at what I was trying to do, and that's where I met another person who is the founder of Viko, which is a software company for medium-sized or small-sized retailers who can't afford their own software inventory systems, and he is very committed about making Wales a great environment for business and technology. And he gave me a position in return for what I was getting paid for the job, as well as taking me under his wing as an entrepreneurial mentee. And I believe that was the first moment I grasped the importance of mentoring. Because he was incredibly good at giving me advice on things I was doing. He had already completed the task. And he'd done it in that tough area where... doesn't exist.”

But, this is to be noted, all of the participants were not successful in translating their company concept to a commercial endeavor to the scale they had hoped for owing to a variety of obstacles. Most entrepreneurs recognized financial resources as a restrictive barrier, in both ways that is family sources and financial sources and as a result, all business start-ups are tiny. In the following quotation, for example, banks criteria of checking the credit history was the main limiting factor in getting loan, eventually she has got government’s funding.

Respondent V,

“Finally, I had to obtain the private financing on our own by demonstrating that... we had a very strong cash flow projection, company strategy, and everything”.

Respondent VIII,

“My mother was unable to lend me the money. I attempted to obtain a bank loan but was unable to do so due to my lack of credit history. Finally, I discovered that grants were available for worldwide marketing for enterprises selling to other countries”.

The entrepreneur in the following remark used to be in Wales, and the government there has money obtainable for enterprises trading abroad, this aided this woman in starting her venture, promoting it, and growing it to another nations.

Respondent XI,

"I received financial assistance from the local council office and the Welsh Assembly to set up the office." "I also got some financial support from my father," she added.

To summarize, ten of the fifteen partaker has used their family finances to start their companies, whereas five were those to employed financial and private organizations for get loan capital.

Moreover, that entrepreneurs with prior exposure were best in recognizing the opportunities for business (Ronstadt, 1988; Ucbasarab et al., 2003). As a result, people who grow up in business houses are more prepared for the advent of entrepreneurial opportunities, as demonstrated by the below quote,

Respondent IV,

"When I married and moved to London, my father-in-law had a large business. They operated a real estate business as well as a large food shop. He was the first person in London to introduce garam masala and Pakistan rice to Asians. He began with a little shop in Manor Park, but developed and expanded to make his business a success. He was a really hard worker. As a result, when I moved here, I also assisted with the family company. My spouse and my brother-in-law were both active in the family company. I used to work on the till, stock the shelves, and do other things... this sparked my interest in business."

Respondent XIII,

"My mother has showed me time and time again that is probably why I don't have any fear to take that sort of risk because I have seen my mother do it three times certainly in my life time let alone in her life time. That also helps me not be afraid since I've seen her do it before, which gives me confidence..."

Its clear in preceding statements, as this study confirms, that elder members of families play an important part in opportunity hunting, sometimes as a succession (Handler, 1990; Discua Cruz et al., 2012). However, because of different objectives, there are disagreements and divergent opinions within entrepreneurial families (Steier et al., 2009). Respondent I, for instance, shifted her precedence when her spouse became gravely sick, forcing her to stop her firm. Similarly, Respondent VII was so impacted by her mother-in-sickness laws that she had to limit the expansion of her firm.

In summary, the majority of respondents had launched small firms with minimal entry barriers regarding *"Normative Institutions"* (commitment of the family, social standards, and modest funds) and *"Regulatory Institutions"* (fiscal biasness on the terms of gender). As a result, they had to be in the competitors industries, with poor boundaries, little progress, and, as a result, less revenue. The above mentioned aspects hampered future business expansion potential. The bulk of the enterprises were racially focused, with Asians being the majority of the clientele targeted.

Respondent V,

“Probably because my company dealt with Asian countries, and even my nationality worked in my favor rather than against me. My field is primarily for the Pakistani community.”

Two enterprises have purposefully "broken free" of the constraint by expanding outside Asian culturally dense area that is global marketing and consultancy and online groceries market. This wasn't clear that if this was a deliberate tactic or if it was done intuitively due to associated groups and accessibility. Though, this might be described by Scott (1995), who identified this as a hidden components in the case of "Normative Institutions" are imbedded, which include values, societal structure and customs.

Thoughts, standards, boundaries, and normative expectation, as well as planned hopes entrenched in the systems, affected entrepreneurs in their process of entrepreneurship and influenced their choice of company ventures. In South Asian civilization, the female position is still firmly associated with kids, family, and home tasks. Even though they are working same hours as the men of the family are working, it is women's responsibility to do domestic tasks such as looking after the children, parents who are dependent on them, or any other old family members (Greer & Greene, 2003; Marlow, 2002).

According to the findings of this research, it is difficult for them to maintain the stability among household and official roles, as a result, they only have an option to work flexible and when it is convenient for them in order to maintain and fulfil their household responsibilities. Moreover, because the majority of their economical sources are related with the men in the family, so they imposed what is permissible and what's not, this shows inflexible gender norms in South Asian and Black Caribbean culture. The price of breaking free from these positions might be social isolation. As a result, societal standards limited several activities that were thought unsuitable for a girl. This investigation revealed a persistent negotiation of their gender roles.

5.4 Influence of Entrepreneurship both Individual and Personal

I created the table below to provide the summary findings of Individual and personal influence on the process of entrepreneurship in order to capture the influence of individual factors on entrepreneurship. “Age”, “education”, “business experience”, “duration of marriage”, and “presence of children” all have an influence on FEs' shift to autonomy.

Figure 4 Personal Characteristics

In the seven columns of this figure that reflects all of the significant personal aspects which influence an individual's aptitude to be an entrepreneur. An interview replies for each sub-factor have been listed and arranged in the table below.

As a new business owner, the individual plays a crucial role through the interaction of roles and is not a latent individual. The results for each person's influence on the entrepreneurial process are displayed in this table. All of the respondents had at least A-level or diploma schooling, and the majority had graduate-level training. The entrepreneurs' ages ranged (from 20 to 60 years). Their personal household (marriage, kid, and husband) and “temporal factors” had the most impact on their business development.

5.4.1 “Impact of Individual Factors on Entrepreneurial Process”

<i>Participants</i>	<i>Education</i>	<i>Age</i>	<i>Partner-(Men in the family)</i>	<i>Kids</i>	<i>Duration of being married</i>	<i>Entrepreneurial Propensity</i>	<i>Entrepreneurial Experience</i>	<i>Other</i>
I	Undergraduate	As she get older she was confident experienced and was able decide	Negative and possible influences during Entrepreneurial Process	Both positive and negative influences during Entrepreneurial Process until her elder daughter grown up and supported in her business	With years of married life the pressure from her partner and his family was reduced	Strong personality and want to improve herself and challenging conditions	Positive influence of setting up several businesses	Partner family
ii	Undergraduate		Husband to be supported her together information	Not Applicable	Not Applicable	Enthusiastic and confident ready to take risk and persistence	Financial loss while sending money for web designing to India. This was a good experience for her	

iii	Post graduate Degree		Support of the partner	Kids comes first but they were not an obstacle in her Entrepreneurial Process		She wants to be independent, ambitious personality		
iv	Post graduate Degree	Age brings confidence in her personality	Partner was influencing her both positively and negatively	Kids are prioritized than business	Partner family started trusting her as the marriage duration increases	Eager to try new things and chances	Obtained experiences from several businesses	
V	Graduated in Law	The mature men does not believe in her and often ask her that how she have a knowledge of everything, she had to be proved herself	Partner had positive influence on her Entrepreneurial Process	Partner family supported her by taking care of her children		She is persistent, confident and have leadership quality, she always have new ideas in her mind and she does not like failure	Her business was affected when the Government changed the policy because she was aware of her business environment she managed to sell her business	

							before the change was effected	
vi	Post graduate Degree		Partner has negative influence on her and he divorced her	She established several businesses, her first business was consultancy but she did everything for social benefits. She works for others which give her experience and confidence to open her own business	Divorced after some years of marriage	She is obsessed about her work, creative	She developed several businesses, such as project work, consultancy. She did all just for social benefits. As the time passes and she has got more experience by working in other companies, she has got this confidence to start open her venture.	

Vii	Beautician Courses A-Level		Partner has both positive and negative influence	In the beginning she began her business from home once her kids were at the age of going to school	Duration of her marriage influenced her positively		Her partner started to trust and support her when she has got some experiences in her business. In the beginning she only has Asian customers but later on when she was famous British customers also started to come, she is more confident now	
Viii	Diploma in Business	Started her first business when she was nineteen years old	Not Applicable	Not Applicable	Not Applicable	Looking for chances and avail them in time	when she was nineteen years old had experienced of	

							her first business	
ix	Undergraduate		Not Applicable	Not Applicable	Not Applicable	She is creative and respond according to the requirements	She has business experience of twenty seven years and always being successful in her field due to which she avails places as board of directors in different companies	
x	Undergraduate Degree and Diploma	Gained confidence with age	Partner has both positive and negative influence	She has got three kids but started her business when her kids started to go to school	She gained trust of her husband	She have leadership qualities, love to take risk and hardworking	In the beginning she commenced her venture from her residence to check the market and to	

							get some experience	
xi	Undergraduate Degree in Business	Elder brother was decision maker, later at starting her business she challenged her brother because she was more confident	Not Applicable	Not Applicable	Not Applicable	Desire to work, looking for opportunities and independent		
xii	Medical Degree	With age she gained confidence and persuaded her parents	Partner was very supportive emotionally and also financially		Was able to find the gap in the market which makes her to be ready for challenges. She is independent, confident and ambitious		She does not have any experience when she started her business but after four years in the business she decided to spread her business	

xiii	Undergraduate Degree	Time gave her experience and confidence due to which she decided to leave her job and to start training for coding and to start her own business	Dad and partner were supportive and always encourage her in every step of her life	Not Applicable	Not Applicable	Outgoing, ready to take risk and confident	She won National young Entrepreneurs award for her A-Level project. Worked two years in Amazon as operational Manager, started her own business one year ago	
xiv	Undergraduate	Sixty	When she was forty five year old her partner died which creates a big gap in her life	Her children were grown up that's why she was free and started her own business	Twenty six (widow)	Social in her society, love to help others, leadership qualities	She is running her business from thirteen years and spreading it. Had no experience t the start	

xv	Post graduate Degree	Forty five	Partner provided finances and supported her	None	Twelve	Persistence , determined, risk taker	In the business from nine years	
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5.5 Entrepreneurial Motivation of Female Entrepreneurs

The overview of the underlying causes for the participants' choice to pursue entrepreneurship is presented in Table 9. This demonstrates the different strength of the motivating “*push and pull*” elements. This topic should be viewed cautiously, though, as it is predicated on post-hoc rationalizations of the motivations for starting firms.

Table 6 Motivation for FEs

<i>Participants</i>	<i>Motivation for Female Entrepreneurs</i>
i	Like to be self-determined, motivated, love challenges,
ii	Determined, Entrepreneurial propensity
iii	Desired to do something, taking risk and challenges, independent
iv	Motivated, supported family business, determined to start her business
V	Chances of joining and running dad's business, Entrepreneurial propensity
Vi	Social reasons, self-motivated
Vii	Financial reasons, business person, hardworking and strong personality and want to do something in her life
Viii	Self-motivated, business running skills and did not get a job after finishing her study
ix	Social reasons, innovative person
X	Socially mobile, financial causes, Entrepreneurial propensity
Xi	Strong and determined person does not want to work for others
Xii	Independence, determined and bored
Xiii	Ambitious, flexible can balance between work life and family life
Xiv	Socially active life and bored
Xv	Biasness at work place, independent

But there is a recurring feature among them all—they all want to be their own boss (entrepreneurial propensity). Additionally, they are aspirational, want acknowledgment from others, and ultimately hope to achieve economic independence, social mobility, and social connectedness. The Respondents' intense enthusiasm and drive (self-motivation) to achieve, not just for material gain but also for self-fulfillment, was evident as a common element. It's interesting to note that only one Respondent cited mobility limitations in paid work (this supposed as "glass ceiling") and a motivating "push factor" for choosing to become self-employed. Some of the illustrations that illustrate numerous reasons why people started a venture:

Respondent I,

"I was a strong woman even before I married. I had a strong mentality that wanted to challenge the standards."

Respondent V,

"I have so many thoughts running through my brain. It was always going to be something imaginative, unique, and to improve people's lives."

They were motivated for their vision of being creative and for self-development, as ***Respondent I*** stated:

"... 'Money' has never been my primary business motive. My major goal was to use my talents to help with business development. Even if someone told me at the time that starting a business would only net me 10% to 20%, I would still do it. It was enough for me since the excitement and buzz it provided were so addicting. Because the process allows you to grow and learn a lot."

Respondent XIV,

"I was, indeed. My boys were both self-sufficient and married. My problem was not one of money; rather, I was bored and wanted to do something constructive and creative. I had some extra cash that I utilized to start a modest jewelry company."

As seen by the statements above, the Respondents have very strong personality and is confident, all of FEs possessed business proclivity which assisted FEs in overcoming obstacles encountered when establishing or building their own firms.

Respondent VI,

"Without getting into specifics. When I chose to leave my spouse, he began to threaten me... There was a lot of physical, mental, anguish, and sorrow, and being alone here (in the UK) on my own, with my child taken away, there were many empty periods in my life.... So, I considered how I might fill those holes and foster a sense of belonging. When you work, it's only 9 to 5, and you don't have anyone else... (sic)".

Respondent VI,

"While working 9 to 5, I felt socially isolated."

Furthermore, her personal tragedy (divorce) helped her sympathize with women in her neighborhood who were experiencing similar isolation (because of the language restrictions, and family's strict social standards). Due to this she was inspired to establish humanitarian company in order to assist the ladies in integrating into the local society by knowing the language and standards of the society. As a result, her company served like "refuge". She believed that those ladies had family responsibilities such as upbringing of their kids, caring for family elders, and attempting to settle in the host nation. South Asian women are socially isolated since their assigned societal role demands them to stay at home.

Respondent XV,

"At that time, I understood there were two obstacles impeding my desire to achieve anything with my life: my family commitments and norms, and a lack of career chances at work (perhaps owing to discrimination) - I chose to resign the job at that point. I had been considering starting a business for quite some time."

Respondent XIII,

"So, back in 2008, I was working for a firm named Amazon!! LOL ... I was working as an area manager for their operations team and was making my way up the corporate ladder, but I concluded that this was not the road I wanted to take. I've always wanted to be a CEO, a founder, and the owner of my own company. And I recognized that the route I was on was not actually preparing me to be an entrepreneur."

The aforementioned individuals concluded that her professional goals could not be met through her employment and chose to resign. All 2nd generation respondents were focused on the work; yet, they also think that their family is their key responsibility as well, therefore they arrive at compromise between work objectives and social and cultural commitments.

This is noted in the chapter of review of literature, South Asian and Black Caribbean females raised in the United Kingdom, continue to respect their communal and spiritual traditions, which occasionally clash with their job environment, forcing them to become the "boss of their own enterprises." The following comment demonstrates that a 2nd generation respondent accepted the risk of returning to Wales, because her fiancé lives there, and entering in a difficult work climate.

Respondent XIII,

"At the same time, I moved back to Wales since that's where my fiancé is and where I was hoping to finish up. So, I returned to live with him. As a result of returning to Wales, I had to rebuild my network because my previous network was now in London, in Essex, where I had been residing. So, I had to attempt to develop a network in Wales, which is actually fairly tough. The technological environment of Wales, particularly in west Wales, is virtually non-existent."

Respondent IV said,

"Snober Cookery Show was my first show... I became pretty famous in my neighborhood, and people respected me for my job - I truly appreciated it... My community adored me; whenever there was an issue, they would come to me to solve it."

These quotation demonstrates how the necessity for “*social recognition*” contact is motivating factor for FEs in establishing a businesses.

To summarize, all interviewee said that due to this business they were socially connected, were able to provide financial support to the family, and a means to help them advance in their careers. Individual ethno-cultural motivations proved to be the primary causes for business inspiration. The “*pull-type factor*” affected both 1st and 2nd generation’s female entrepreneurs among the partakers. A limited percentage of subjects demonstrated a “*push factor*”. Though, as they dug further, they discovered that the major cause was their entrepreneurial goals, which drove them to realize their dream of starting their own business. Entrepreneurship, in the end, is independence and self-employment, and the dangers it entails (particularly from external regulatory organizations, and is described in depth further) vs. less risk, steady salaried job. Most of the scholars, attempted to quantify and assess the “*push-pull*” forces that eventually contribute to an entrepreneurial choice.

Because 1st and 2nd generation FEs happened to be ambitious, determined, desire to prove them, does not wanted to work for others, desired independence and a strong wish for success, they were able to realize their dreams. All of the interviews have one thing in common, that existence of continual negotiation and conversation among the every entrepreneur, who seeks, identifies, uncovers, and develops chances, and they must traverse both from “*Normative and Regulative Institutions*”. These institutions have impact and influence of these entrepreneurs this component of the research is examined later as a perspective of the “*Temporal Dimension*”. The next section provides more perspectives on several aspects and their interactions.

5.6 Temporal Dimensions

This research also demonstrates that entrepreneurship is a series of activities which unfolds gradual procedure, however, participants' entrepreneurial propensity and possession of particular personal characteristics assisted the procedure of entrepreneurs and sense of “*External factors*” such as “*Normative and Regulative institutions*”, in few scenarios, “*Temporal aspects*” (Kin et al., 2015). These “*Institutions*” maintains steadiness and firmness, yet FE have to undergo gradual, evolutionary development. Because of the shared interplay among structure and agency, institutions should therefore, be examined as both a process and as a situation of current social standards. This includes both the institutionalization and deinstitutionalization processes (Zucker, 1996). Therefore, institutional theory and entrepreneurship have an aspect of process, hence “*Temporal dimension*” gives more strength to this discussion.

Consider how linear time structure was applied to financial contracts by private financial corporations in the majority of those instances. Before accepting the loan, the same financial institutions evaluated the preceding enterprises' historical performance (non-linearity of time). On a personal level, each person through a linear process to build up their company with long-term aims and ambitions. In order to make their upcoming endeavor successful, they also took lessons from their former endeavors (non-linear aspects of time).

In the UK, regulatory agencies, particularly financial institutions, typically base their judgments on linear or clock time. For instance, in order to obtain a loan for future results, FEs had to demonstrate their prior performance and credit history. Financial institutions lack faith in supporting young businesses or newlywed women. They won't be interested if they become pregnant or have children, goes the thinking. Women may have limitations depending on their stage in life, such as difficulty in obtaining funding for their start-up businesses since they lack a track record to provide to potential investors. The remarks below make clear that private investor have a particular point of view regarding young FEs, if they ask for investment:

Respondent II,

“They perceive women as a little weak, and they see them as having babies and getting married one day; how serious are they about business?”

She further stated regarding her young aged friend:

“So, I have an Indian buddy who has recently launched a business. She had an investor meeting. Similar to mine, except for healthy food. She had a very successful business, turning over £25000 in her first year... the investor told her that they didn't think she was serious since they assumed it was a lifestyle business. She will not be able to devote her complete attention to it since she will soon have other obligations...”

Event timing affects how female entrepreneurs migrate toward empowerment and agency, for instance through marriage, parenthood, education, and general life experience. Training, knowledge, and experience gave the FEs strength in any situation. Due to abrupt changes in government regulations, FEs have occasionally had to shut down their operations. Events cause business endeavors to move ahead and backward. For instance, because of an alteration in policies from the government, at the time of a change in the regulations of the policy of legal aid for law cases, Respondent V's business moved backward in regards of the right phase of the business.

Entrepreneurs acquire social acceptance, independence, and autonomy resulting in a variety of life circumstances, including age, experience, marriage, and parenthood. As an illustration, Respondent V's customers does not took her seriously due to her young age, at the time when she began her practice as an attorney, but through professionalism and tenacity she made a name for herself.

Respondent V,

“Then I started earning a number of various prizes, such as the ISO 9000 award and the Nexcel, which was a Government legal award. All of these things contribute to your sense of accomplishment.” “It's quite surprising they'd think a young girl would know nothing,” she added”.

Women's autonomy and authority develop through time and with experience, and as a result, their personal causal power rises and has an influence on their entrepreneurial process. It should be emphasized that timing is crucial in this situation. In South Asian and Black Caribbean culture, male family members predominantly make all home choices. When a female member of the family gets older, then she begins to have an

impact as well. It gradually transitions from a “*patriarchy*” to a “*matriarchy*”. For instance, grandparents within the family have more influence over domestic decisions than the family's younger men. As a result, as they mature and experience other life events like becoming a mother and eventually a grandma, women gain authority and influence.

Events occur as a result of a constant interaction between institutions (such as household/family culture) and entrepreneurial acts, as detailed in Chapter 2 of the literature study. These incidents may be used as analytical building blocks to track changes to the entrepreneurial process. Events are situations where changes are observed to occur in the temporal dimensions, according to Abrams (1982).

Their self-confidence builds more due to the experience of entrepreneurship e, which aids them to talk about their position in the family.

Respondent VII mentions,

"I've been giving free-lance services to companies in London and Wales for the last few years after doing a short course in theatre makeup. I am more secure now that I have gained experience and have proven myself not just as a mother, wife, and daughter in law, but also as an entrepreneur."

FEs learned with time during the process of entrepreneurship “*Time dimension*”, Such as, the very first step of entrepreneurship provides knowledge about the market, and this can be useful in the process of creating a company.

Respondent I,

"I didn't conduct any marketing when I first launched the company. I didn't have that kind of training... At the time, I was only learning how to advertise myself".

Further she mentions,

"Because I retired from the wholesale industry. So I couldn't imagine little... even though I didn't have a business, I didn't think I could only buy 15 or 20 pieces."

A demonstration of believe on herself and refusal of accepting uncertainty being FE, which was earned via experience.

Respondent X,

“In India, I assisted a friend in establishing her beauty business and had some expertise and interest in the field.”

This aided FE in establishing a firm in the United Kingdom. Influence of the Respondents' stay in the UK is one of the temporal elements that should be mentioned in respect to agency and structure. For instance, every second-generation entrepreneur entered the industry of their choosing because they are passionate about business. British-born FEs who want to succeed in the workplace may undergo specialized trainings to begin their careers with salaried job to develop the skills needed to launch their own firm. For them, business is where they should put their extensive professional knowledge. FEs considers their business as the further rung in the journey of their professional development and achievement.

As stated by Respondent VII, in order to obtain client confidence, time is examined both linearly and in terms of events that occur. "No, it didn't have any problems with that except that for the first few months, the bulk of my clients were of my ethnicity, but with time, others learned about me and I started getting local Welsh and English ladies as well."

Respondent I, had a trust on herself, that through her distinct targets she will be able to attain them. She was sure that the passage of time and once she accomplish some targets her business will succeed. Further she stated,

“I didn't conduct any marketing when I first began the firm... My company was profitable from the start. By the 2nd year, I considered how I might market my business and run quicker. I didn't do any marketing the first year. So I asked myself, how can I keep doing what I'm doing if it's a new idea?”

All of the respondents were not worried of minor setbacks along the road. A partaker who was working in internet business sector employing cutting-edge tools, had extra time constraints than others operating in much established areas. When an Indian programmers deferred the agreement, she really missed commercial possibilities, and her opponents come in to the marketplace before her:

Respondent II,

"My website, which was expected to be finished in four weeks, took six months. That took a long time. In 6 months, another company began doing precisely same thing.. So we had a rival, who was doing the same thing I did. I recall viewing their website, which appeared to be better than ours. And I immediately thought of sweets. This is not good; I need to repair it right away."

It might be claimed that they are under more pressure in a young, dynamic industry like software development and coding, etc., where there aren't many active female entrepreneurs. Unconscious prejudice that exists in certain industries prevents women from having certain abilities may be to blame for this. This is a generalized prejudice that is unrelated to any particular ethnic culture.

The scenario below demonstrates how there is unconscious bias against women in the field of software engineering:

Respondent XIII,

"My co-founder and I, for example, went to a meeting with a connection. When we sat down, he thought that my co-founder would do all of the talking. We were discussing strategy, technology, and business. Obviously, I work in technology, but he does not. So I was able to answer all of his queries far better than he could. He performed well in other areas. But this man simply believed that because I was a woman and he was a block, I would ask him all the questions. But I just let him realize gradually over the conversation that this was my area of expertise and directed such inquiries to me. Those are the little things and I don't think if I had anything that blocked me from doing what I want to do".

Moreover, this research demonstrated the family members do not trust entrepreneurs when they are young and in the early stages of their businesses. To be accepted, they must establish their credibility via prior performance and experience. Social standing is determined by the interaction of positions and time. Additionally, female autonomy/power does change as previously described as "linear and non-linear time and events" such as "age", "education", "success", "marriage" and "children". Time adds even additional layer to the discussion of how FEs constantly negotiate their gender while bucking conventional norms. As a result,

time is a key aspect in the entrepreneurial process, possibly more so from subjective and non-linear viewpoints than from chronological or linear ones.

Additionally, as noted in Chapter 2 of the literature review, time is arbitrary and can move at various speeds depending on an area, an economy, or a particular industry (Plakoyiannaki & Saren, 2006). In FEs case, “Normative institutions” typically have a past adjustment since FEs find no incentive to change their traditional conduct. This study has made clear how spouses and other close family members have an influence on the FEs' entrepreneurial conduct based on their historical perspectives and cultural beliefs. On the other side, the majority of FEs tend to be very risk-takers and future-focused. In South Asian and Black Caribbean culture, gender limits are defined by normative institutions, which causes a split and ongoing struggle.

Entrepreneurs may alter their temporal focus/orientation when they sign agreements with banks and suppliers. There are different constraints on entrepreneurs in emerging company sectors with fewer instances of the entrepreneurial process than there would be in an established, cutthroat industry. Entrepreneurs are far more likely than family members to recognize their entrepreneurial tendencies. FEs from this investigation supported that.

Respondent I,

"I was sick of listening to other people who I assumed had no knowledge." I felt doing things my way was the best way to proceed... So, in three or four days, I booked three performances, signed a partnership with two publications, and spent around £70,000 on promotion."

People in South Asian and Black Caribbean cultures prioritize their families over their careers by managing their job in a polychronic way (Hall & Hall, 1990). As a result, everything else, including their business, must wait when close family requests anything. Space and competitiveness are two additional aspects that are connected to time emphasis; polychronic ethnicities also shows suppleness and honesty in relation to space, in relation to time, as well as to be more group-oriented. Another reason, FEs are more likely than White female entrepreneurs to be impacted by their normative institutions. The statements from some of the FEs below demonstrate how the polychronic cultures of South Asia and the Black Caribbean affected their entrepreneurial journeys:

Respondent V,

"Naeem underwent therapy, which was a lengthy procedure that included a surgery. Because of his sickness, I was unable to continue with my company, and my youngest kid was too little... Then I closed, which was quite disappointing because I had huge ambitions for my business; I was going to China to acquire, and I was at the stage where I was going to build my business... It took him 3 to 4 years to recover physically and emotionally. He began working. During that period, we went through hell."

Because of this aspect, FEs in this research were underneath another time constraints as compared to their male colleagues. Because of “social expectations”, FEs' main concern was their close family and domestic obligations. In some circumstances, they had to delay or stop the growth of their business in order to care for a family member.

Respondent XIV,

"I was a full-time housewife, caring for my family (including my in-law, who resided with us) and raising children.... I didn't extend my business at first because I wanted to give her attention as well."

Respondent VI,

"At times, I had to quit working and return to India to care for my mother because I am the only child, my father has died, and my mother is elderly... This has been a persistent source of contention in my life."

Event time offers a different viewpoint on what causes drastic transformations in business. It appears in connection to things like “movements”, “events”, and “objects”. For instance, there are different phases in the business cycle, such as “idea”, “start-up”, “growth”, “expansion”, “mature”, and “exit”. This is appealing to see how, at certain developmental phases, a home institution and entrepreneur interact differently. For instance, aspiring businesspeople must demonstrate their credibility via achievement. The majority of the FEs in this research had to demonstrate their worth to their families through their business performance. They gained the credibility and confidence of their family as a result. Discontinuities and extreme change

might sometimes happen, which has an effect on their business, for instance. One of the FEs had to adjust her business strategy after BREXIT since it had such a significant impact on her house-rental firm.

Entrepreneurs acquire social standing, independence/autonomy via a variety of life events, including getting older, getting married, and having kids. For instance, when Respondent V first started her practice as a young attorney, her customers did not take her seriously. However, through professionalism and a strong work ethic, she made a name for herself.

Respondent XIV,

"...However, my experience and age have given me the courage to care after my workshop (where all workers are male) in Jamaica on my alone. They are OK now because I have the maturity and expertise to deal with them. Second, the company has been in operation for a few years, giving them confidence that it would not go out of business immediately."

Respondent XII,

"My success has inspired me to expand to English clientele beginning next year." "I've been working on it."

As a woman advances in school, gets married, has kids, or ages, her community and social networks have more trust in her talents. Unlike a family, who tells that actual time has gone before discovering that they may get popular, FEs recognizes their business susceptibilities considerably sooner than a family.

It's interesting to see how different home institutions and entrepreneurs interact at this point since budding entrepreneurs need to establish their legitimacy via achievement.

Respondent XII,

"Being away from home for over 5 years taught me independence and mature thinking. This gave me the confidence and bravery to tell my parents that I had no desire to practice medicine and that I had completed my degree for them."

This research also demonstrated the “risk-taking” behavior FEs, or their inclination to make decisions while considering the possibility of uncertain results (Stewart & Roth, 2001). For

example, all of them has made current economical sacrifices in exchange for potential future gains. We can say the “risk-taking” has “current” and “future temporal” emphasis, when a “risk-taker assesses potential future outcomes while acting in the present, as mentioned in the review of literature chapter two. Though, as “risk-taking” might involve “thrill-seeking” here people concentrate at maximizing their present experiences, we may claim that “risk-taking” convincingly associated with present attention than potential focus (Bluedorn & Denhardt, 1988; George & Jones, 2000).

Respondent I,

"It was incredible!! It provided me a lot of experience and confidence to ultimately launch my present business. My educational and commercial backgrounds were not the same. I simply had this feeling... I had such faith in myself that anything I bought and did would sell."

Respondent VII,

"I was SO EXCITED when I started the course in 2000, but I never imagined that one year would be so challenging. Juggling so many balls and not being able to complain because I was constantly reminded that it was my decision and that it was up to me how to balance all different duties..."

This research demonstrated FEs' ongoing efforts to build their human capital in an oppressively patriarchal South Asian and Black Caribbean society in order to acquire some measure of empowerment. This is related to FE's capacity to surmount obstacles in the establishment and expansion of their enterprises. The deliberate efforts made by FEs to further their education, expand their professional networks, and learn latest expertize reveal that FEs transformation from powerless to having kind of measure of power and influence. The aforementioned discoveries gave this study unprecedented depth and a new dimension (temporal aspects) that no other researchers had before exploited in the context of FEs.

Further, 15 open ended, unstructured interviews were conducted showing fifteen businesses, are summarized:

Table 7 Details of Businesses of Interviewed FEs

<i>Interviews</i>	<i>Authorized As</i>	<i>Business Type</i>	<i>Number of Employees</i>	<i>Business Age</i>	<i>Working As</i>
<i>i</i>	<i>Ltd</i>	<i>Wedding range, retail</i>	<i>Six</i>	<i>Eleven years</i>	<i>Owner</i>
<i>ii</i>	<i>Partnership</i>	<i>Online market place - food</i>	<i>Two</i>	<i>Two years</i>	<i>Chief Executive</i>
<i>iii</i>	<i>Partnership and Ltd</i>	<i>Retail and manufacturing</i>	<i>Eleven</i>	<i>Twenty five years</i>	<i>Director</i>
<i>iv</i>	<i>Ltd</i>	<i>Food, Health & Marriage services</i>	<i>Three</i>	<i>Thirteen years</i>	<i>Owner</i>
<i>v</i>	<i>Ltd</i>	<i>law firm</i>	<i>Two</i>	<i>Five years</i>	<i>Director</i>
<i>vi</i>	<i>Ltd</i>	<i>Management Consultancy</i>	<i>One</i>	<i>Four years</i>	<i>Director</i>
<i>vii</i>	<i>Ltd</i>	<i>Beauty Therapy Business</i>	<i>Twelve</i>	<i>Fifteen years</i>	<i>Director</i>
<i>viii</i>	<i>Ltd</i>	<i>Consultancy business for education sector, International marketing</i>	<i>Five</i>	<i>Eight years</i>	<i>Director</i>
<i>ix</i>	<i>Group Venture</i>	<i>Charity in education sector and social entrepreneurs</i>	<i>Twelve</i>	<i>Twenty seven years</i>	<i>Assistant CEO</i>

<i>x</i>	<i>Ltd</i>	<i>Beautician</i>	<i>Fifty</i>	<i>Eighteen years</i>	<i>Director</i>
<i>xi</i>	<i>Ltd</i>	<i>Event Management</i>	<i>Three</i>	<i>Two years</i>	<i>Director</i>
<i>xii</i>	<i>Ltd</i>	<i>Fashion sector</i>	<i>Twelve</i>	<i>Four years</i>	<i>Director</i>
<i>xiii</i>	<i>Ltd</i>	<i>Tech company</i>	<i>Four</i>	<i>One year</i>	<i>Director</i>
<i>xiv</i>	<i>Ltd</i>	<i>Jewelry business (retail)</i>	<i>Fifty four</i>	<i>Thirteen years</i>	<i>Director</i>
<i>xv</i>	<i>Ltd</i>	<i>Online - Event Management (Baby Showers)</i>	<i>Fifty two</i>	<i>Nine years</i>	<i>MD</i>

Table number 7 presenting the in-depth information of 15 enterprises used in this research. The demographics of these enterprises was selected to indicate the entrepreneur distribution all over the United Kingdom. After 15th interview, I have realized that I have reached to the saturation point of the data because there was nothing different from the previous interviews. The FEs were repeating almost same information which were said by other in the past due to the fact that they all belong to the same cultural background.

Everyone has begun as SMEs and are still actively involved with SMEs. Due to the high startup costs (barrier to entry), this represents the majority of Asian entrepreneurs (male or female), but this is not always a bad thing because SMEs have a significant economic influence in the United Kingdom (Dhaliwas, 2000; Jones et al., 2010). This is often true for all early phases of entrepreneurship, when starting a small firm is simpler. Except for high growth companies that have rapidly expanded from SMEs, there is very little entrepreneurial activity within larger enterprises.

Family obligations were a crucial factor in the FEs' inability to expand, forcing them to either alter the direction of their firm or temporarily close it. There are several other causes no-slow growth, with economical sources and commitments and restrictions from the family. The quote below is presenting this:

Respondent I,

“I couldn't launch a retail business, because I lacked the necessary funds. So I discovered that in the wholesale sector, you just lease a warehouse... As a result, he entered the wholesale industry... ”Then I couldn't continue with my company since my husband was unwell, and my youngest boy was too young... So, I closed, which was quite disappointing because I had high aspirations for my business”.

5.7 Demographics of the Participants

Table 8 Summarizing Research Participants and their details

<i>Interviews</i>	<i>Age</i>	<i>Qualifications</i>	<i>Marital status</i>	<i>No. of Children</i>	<i>Migrants (first generation or second generation)</i>	<i>Spoken Language</i>	<i>What is your first language</i>
i	Forty Eight	A levels or equivalent	Wedded	Three	first generation	Jamaican Patois and English	English
ii	Twenty Eight	Undergraduate Degree	Committed	Zero	second generation	English and Urdu	English
iii	Fifty two	Masters in Economics	Wedded	Two	first generation	Jamaican Patois and English	English
iv	Fifty Eight	Undergraduate degree	Wedded	Four	first generation	Bengali, English	Bengali
v	Fifty One	Postgraduate Law degree	Wedded	Two	second generation	Urdu, Punjabi, English	English
Vi	Fifty Two	Diplomas and undergraduate degree	Separated	One	first generation	Hindi and English	Hindi
Vii	Forty Three	Postgraduate degree	Married	Two	first generation	Jamaican Patois and English	English
Viii	Thirty Two	HND business & A-levels or equivalent	Single	Zero	second generation	Jamaican Patois and English	English
ix	Fifty One	Postgraduate education degree	Married	One	second generation	Urdu and English	English
X	Forty Five	Undergraduate Degree and various diplomas	Wedded	Three	first generation	Hindi and English	Hindi
Xi	Twenty Four	Under graduate	Single	Zero	second generation	English and Hindi	English

Xii	Twenty Seven	Under graduate	Married	One	second generation	English and Urdu	English
Xiii	Twenty Five	Under graduate	Engaged	Zero	second generation	English and Bengali	english
Xiv	Sixty	Under graduate	Single	Two	second generation	English and Jamaican Patois	english
Xv	Forty Five	Post graduate	Wedded	Zero	second generation	Bengali & English	english

In Table 8, personal details as well as the location of the 15 participants are shown and in table 7 all the information regarding their businesses are presented.

Education is highly regarded in South Asian society as a method of achieving corporate success and social mobilization (Hopkins, 2018).

Respondent I,

"Anyway, I married my husband, who was 14 years my senior and the doctor... He urged me to return to school since he is an intellectual kind of person. But I was different; I was more interested in art and creativity than in schooling. But I didn't know how important education was for everything, and even now I think and regret that I should have finished my school - even though he was extremely supportive and I could have continued my education...but I didn't."

The participant who made the above statement believed that education was crucial for managing a firm; when pressed further, she stated that having a strong understanding of business, marketing, and finance techniques would have been advantageous. The quotations that follow demonstrate how crucial linguistic abilities and experience are to the participants since they provided them the confidence and power to shape numerous elements they encountered while engaging in the entrepreneurial process.

Respondent V,

“As a Pakistani woman, your English needs to be ten times better than any English person, my father used to remark. So, in order to be considered on an equal playing field, my written English had to be excellent, and my speaking had to be ten times better than everyone else's. So I had to learn to talk, pitch, and perform public speaking at a level I had never experienced in front of 5000 people, and I had to accept it as the standard.”

Respondent X,

"In India, I assisted a friend in establishing her beauty business and had some expertise and enthusiasm in that field... Of course, I did a couple online and certificate courses, as well as an English language course at a local college (which were free at that time). Without it, I would not have been able to obtain a license to practice as a beauty therapist."

Respondent VII,

"I was able to persuade my husband and his parents since I had worked as a salon manager and knew how the business is operated..."

It is clear that respondents believed their experience and education provided the ability to have a voice in the normative and regulatory organizations in which they were engaged. This agency was obvious in two primary ways.

First of all, schooling gave them the in-depth information they needed to create their business strategies before beginning their companies. The second benefit was that they were considerably more professionally accepted by normative (an educated individual is given far more credit than an ignorant one) and regulative institutions because to their improved preparedness. As previously noted, a respondents who did not finish her schooling expressed remorse a few times throughout the interview, demonstrating uncertainty and a lack of confidence. She believed that if she had received formal schooling to improve her business acumen, she might have handled her company process more effectively. She actively educated herself, nevertheless, using a variety of resources, as opposed to obtaining official

credentials. This has a temporal component as well (event time; described in the research review chapter), since women who are educated enjoy greater respect and agency within their families, households, and communities.

In addition, all of the first-generation South Asian women married early due to cultural traditions, with the exception of participant 11. Further investigation revealed that due to their cultural traditions, young ladies from this region could not have migrated to the UK alone.

Respondent II,

“My folks are traditional, and quite fussy about 'pardha...They married me at the age of 17 in India to my husband, who was 14 years my senior...”

Respondent III,

"I arrived to the UK in 1986 as a very young female, approximately 20 years old, after getting married."

The proportionate distribution of 1st generation (birth abroad) and the 2nd generation (birth in the United Kingdom) business owners identifies the commonalities and contrasts in the variables influencing their entrepreneurial experiences. The groups were native English speakers, therefore it was up to them to decide which their first language was.

5.8 Business Location

Business location is a crucial consideration influenced by several factors. According to earlier research on SME entrepreneurs, the majority of the entrepreneurs who own small enterprises chose to position them near their clients (Dhaliwal, 2000). The geographic factor, however, is not the only one to consider; accessibility to business (nearer to their family so employees can fulfil their family obligations), availability of a suitable opportunity, rental costs, business rates, less expensive labor, mutuality, belief, and cultural principals were all significant factors as well. Powerful ties with their culture inspired them to assist the ethnic community in addition to starting businesses connected to the ethnic network or enclave (Dana, 2007). The following quotes provide a strong case for these elements.

Respondent IV,

“I was inspired to operate my business effectively because of my community and the affection I received from my community. My community adored me; if there was a problem, they would come to me for a solution. I am quite well-liked in the Asian community.”

Her closeness with the community provides respect and love which gave her the driving force to run a successful business.

Respondent X tried to stay nearer to her house so that she can deliver her family responsibilities and commitments of her business effectively, she stated:

“After saving enough money, I opened my first salon in Bradford, near to my home.”

Staying in the society gives FEs suitable work force but at the same time they also encounter some social problems because they are after all a woman.

Respondent XII,

“Because we have Pakistani outfits, we only recruit Pakistani girls. Even though we pay well, most of our employees are first generation, as second generation do not want to work in Ilford. They would rather work in the city. The majority of the employees is Asian, primarily from India or Pakistan.”

Respondent XIV,

“It (the company) is fairly near to where I live since renting a property in this location was less expensive. There is a close-knit Jamaican population in this region, which makes it easy to find qualified employees to assist me with making standard jewelry designs.”

Because of the type of their business and aforementioned “normative”, “social” and “economic” issues, most of the businesses are thus situated at high-streets. 2nd generation enterprises did, however, branch out into more established industries. The 2nd generation of FEs are not prepared to merely focus on their cultural society, as can be seen from the

following comment, in part because they are more confidence since they are more comfortable within their home culture and in part due the easy access to the technology..

Respondent II,

"So you're not mainstream in the sense that if you own a business... I'm talking about unheard-of bakers who will be like mothers who prepared donuts at home, a lady who bakes baklawa and even 'methai'."

She continues and says regarding business location,

*"I don't want to stretch myself too thin in London... I should try it. I recall reading a book titled *How to Build a Community and a Marketplace*. Because what I was establishing was a market place, a platform that links consumers and bakers, and it said that one important to keep in mind is not to expand too soon, so start with a very small local region and test the market, and I selected London for that."*

Respondent XIII, 2nd generation, for her business, used E-Platfrom.

"We were also working on a similar idea that really merged pretty beautifully with my ideas, so after a few conversations, we agreed to sort of build up my app. We agreed to collaborate as business partners, and now we have an app that we are developing together."

Therefore, 2nd generation's FEs varies 1st generation FEs, that they are much self-assured, using technology and entering mainstream business areas. The first generation, however, was more concerned with the placement of ethnic enterprises in their neighborhoods.

The aforementioned explanation of the "demographic data" demonstrates how societal expectations within a culture's borders of gender and ethnicity affect judgments about the sort of company and where it should be located. Education was seen as a crucial component in preparing FEs for the launch of their businesses as well as enabling FEs to enjoy more greater acceptance professionally, with both "Normative and Regulative Institutions" So

assisting FE in overcoming some of the normative and regulatory constraints. The parts that follow go into further detail and analysis of this element.

5.9 Chapter Summary

In conclusion, it can be said that the three primary thematic clusters “*Normative Institutions*”, “*Regulative Institutions*”, and “*Personal Characteristics*” discussed in the aforementioned segments are connected and share ideas. Each cluster has a part to play in setting boundaries for FEs in terms of ethnicity and gender, as well as possibilities and restrictions.

The study demonstrates that normative institutions, particularly the close-knit family, particularly the male family members, have a significant influence (both good and negative) on the entrepreneurial process that South Asian and Black Caribbean FE go through. The participants' social culture, on the one hand, served as a resource of Economic and social capital, giving them access to networks and crucial personal and private fiscal sources for starting their businesses. Conversely, this was crucial in establishing boundaries in patriarchal cultures, where women were expected to perform the roles of mother, wife, and daughter both within the home and in the wider society.

It is noted, nonetheless, that these females underwent a temporary shift to female's independence. Experience, Age, education, personal traits, and length of marriage, children, children's ages, enthusiasm, and drive were main elements that maintained this shift and a good effect on their entrepreneurial growth procedure. How they manage their personal challenges as well as the fight to conform to everyone else's social standards creates a perpetual struggle for social space. Their social status and the ferocity of their conflict were influenced by the quantity and types of capital (gender capital, economic capital, social capital, cultural capital and human capital).

Institutions with regulatory authority did not provide a significant challenge for respondents. Moreover, they developed enabling frameworks for FEs and assisted FEs in achieving independence via parity in systems and procedures. The interviewees also stated that there had been no racial or gender discrimination by the regulatory institutions. Conversely, we had some indicators from the interviews that “*financial institutions*” were biased against women. These issues were resolved either by entrepreneurial tendencies or early assistance from male family members.

The respondents' individual traits were another relevant element. Their powerful, independent, and optimistic attitudes appeared to drive via their thoughts and by disabling any structural impediments and social inhibitions far earlier, which aided FEs to get through the journey of entrepreneurship.

This research also revealed a relationship among activity and frameworks in UK's FEs' process of entrepreneurship. The study has revealed that the participants are causally significant, but also they are a part of “Normative” (particularly family and household) and “Regulative” institutional structures that both limit and facilitate their propensities for entrepreneurial behavior. The inclusion of temporal aspects in the study is made intriguing by the idea of interaction (going back and forth).

Another intriguing discovery I made was that the situation, especially the close family is the key element in outlining their function and influencing what's deemed as gender-appropriate viewpoint. The patriarchal ideals of their native countries are still present in South Asian and Black Caribbean ethnic cultures in the UK; men are still viewed as the family's providers and decision-makers, while women are expected to take care of the home. Both enablers and restrictions, patriarchal norms have an impact on the entrepreneurial process of women. Initial financial assistance came from some men, but they also had opinions on how women are portrayed and given roles. But because of temporal changes, FEs must continually negotiate their gender in order to achieve their own goals.

Chapter 6: Summary of this Research Study

6.1 Introduction

This chapter evaluates value of the “conceptual framework” and the efficiency of research approach. The chapter also analyses main results, inferences made, and the ramifications that followed. Additionally, it outlines limits, future study goals, and comments in addition to making a major and unique contribution to knowledge.

6.2 Overview

In this research, I looked at the crucial elements that, within the framework of institutional theory, may either encourage or inhibit the entrepreneurial activity of FEs in the UK. Being an entrepreneur myself, one of the reasons I studied this subject was to satisfy my own curiosity and investigate the opportunities and challenges that other South Asian and Black Caribbean female entrepreneurs encounter, especially in the context of their environments. By comprehending the factors that oppose or by utilizing the support and the development of new project, an entrepreneur pass by a process of recognizing, locating, developing, and assessing an opportunity. Institutional theory offered a novel theoretical framework to investigate FEs' entrepreneurial experience in this changing setting.

The environment in which entrepreneurship occurs has drawn the attention of numerous academics (Davidsson, 2003; Welter, 2011; Zahra & Wright, 2011; Spedale & Watson, 2013; Watson, 2013). Early research on entrepreneurship primarily concentrated on: personal characteristics and entrepreneurial dispositions as the main factors explaining entrepreneurial outcomes (Gartner, 1988; Aldrich & Wiedenmayer, 1993) or on the opportunities these entrepreneurs chose to exploit, the types of firms they founded, and firm structures, value creation (meso level) (Eckhardt & Shane, 2003; Aldrich & Ruef, 2006; Lackeus, 2018). The application of institutional theory, a macro-level approach, in recent research has mostly focused on understanding why change happens in existing organizations rather than on how institutions impact entrepreneurial activity, according to Bruton et al. (2010), Holm (1995), Maguire, et al., (2004) and Greenwood & Suddaby (2006). Institutions are ongoing components of someone's life which gives power to social systems through time and space (Gidden, 1984). They transfers from one generation to the next generation, sometime stay the same or sometime changes with time (Zucker, 1977). Several researchers such as Baumol (1990), North (1990), Wright et al., (2005), and Scott (1995), highlighted the importance of institutions and how they affect the entrepreneurial process. The institutions stipulates boundaries and describe their roles, by permitting some

actions and behaviors by predicting the social behaviors (Krasner, 1988; North, 1990; Scott, 1995).

In this study, I examined the ways in which opportunities were molded and how people's decisions to engage in entrepreneurial activity were influenced by “social norms”, “value systems”, “identities”, and “beliefs”, as well as by explicit and implicit regulatory requirements. The institutional context discusses how normative and regulatory issues interact with FEs while they engage in their “entrepreneurial process”. This contact and relationship are complicated and dynamic in nature and incorporate the idea of time. This study is an original contribution to previous research on entrepreneurship within the context of institutional theory for this particular environment because previous research on entrepreneurship in the context of institutional theory as applied to FEs has paid little attention to these aspects.

The decision to employ the qualitative approach of unstructured interviews as the most pertinent for attaining the study objectives was made in light of the nature of the research field, the contextual framework used, the literature evaluation, and my personal observations. The selection of interpretivism as an epistemological position, the use of qualitative research, and the application of thematic analysis to achieve the research goals were appropriate because they took into account subjective realities (at the ontological level) and studied the dynamic entrepreneurial process of female entrepreneurs of South Asian and Black Caribbean origin in the UK. The following section highlights the main results.

6.3 Key Findings and Analysis

Using the theoretical framework established in the research framework, this part seeks to give a cogent explanation of the major findings from the preceding chapter. Figure 5 below maps the three theme clusters I created from my empirical data (normative institutions, regulative institutions, and personal traits) onto a conceptual framework for the entrepreneurial process.

Figure 5 Conceptual Framework Entrepreneurial Process

The normative cluster demonstrates that the social group network, particularly the immediate family, is a key resource for gaining access to both social and financial resources. Furthermore, this culture has extremely strong male-dominant norms because of societal expectations based on cultural and religious values. Financial institutions and governmental regulations, on the other hand, were the two main components in the cluster of regulatory institutions. By equalizing processes and systems, they often produced a more supporting framework. The center cluster of personality qualities demonstrates how entrepreneurs go around and around these many obstacles thanks to their strong entrepreneurial instincts and motivation. The main temporal aspects that influence their shift

to empowerment and, consequently, agency over structure. They are given more agency over structure due to factors including their age, duration of marriage, number and ages of children, business experience, education, and expertise. However, the progression of this change through time is not linear. When engaging in their entrepreneurial experience, FEs continually negotiate gender within the context of a variety of institutional elements (both normative and regulative).

In summary, the personal traits of the FEs and their shift toward empowerment assist to mediate between the two. There is a difference between normative and regulative institutions. As discussed in Chapter 2 (Literature review) and Chapter 4 (thematic framework), the three main components and sub-factors of this framework do not affect the entrepreneurial experience of FEs independently; rather, they are interconnected and interdependent in nature, creating both opportunities and barriers. I was able to identify some of the key elements (described below) in the context of the institutions that affected and influenced FE's entrepreneurial path through the use of this framework. The parts that follow go over the research's conclusions in light of the major findings.

6.3.1 What are the main challenges and barriers faced by female Entrepreneurs of an Ethnic Minority?

How gender-designated limits generated by the institutional environment present themselves for FEs in the UK is a crucial issue that was addressed by the preceding chapter of this research. Systems and support offered by these social institutions are recognized with helping FEs succeed and even get access to entrepreneurship. The same institutions, nevertheless, turned into enormous obstacles for other FEs, who labored mightily to get beyond them. Due to their enormous influence, these institutions therefore play a key role in the fundamental difficulties and impediments that female entrepreneurs from ethnic minorities must overcome.

6.3.1.1 Key Normative Factors

According to the study's findings, both first generation and second generation FEs' entrepreneurial experiences were influenced more by normative institutions than by regulative ones.

When FEs were pursuing their entrepreneurial endeavors, normative institutions provided the majority of their support. For instance, both direct and extended family members

provided practical aid in the form of encouragement to start along the entrepreneurial path, money support, location assistance, and office assistance. So, the immediate family provided both material and moral assistance, particularly the male family members. It may be claimed that small enterprises do depend on family for resources, but in South Asian and Black Caribbean cultures, male members control this to a higher extent than in Britain's "indigenous" culture (Wang, 2018). When their business obligations were viewed to have an overt influence on family obligations (towards children, husbands, and in-laws) or social norms and expectations, these normative institutions posed obstacles for them.

The results of this study showed that gender relations were not fixed; rather, FEs were discovered to be continuously re-negotiating, re-setting, and opposing the gender limits imposed by the radically patriarchal South Asian and Black Caribbean society. This was accomplished by enhancing their education, gaining knowledge, and developing abilities.

The eldest male family member, known as the patriarch, serves as the leader of the joint family structure known as *kunba* in South Asian culture (Qadeer, 2006). Roles may be explicitly created or they may grow naturally over time through contact, during which time differential expectations arise to direct behavior (Blau & Scott 1962/2003). For instance, men and women in South Asian society have quite distinct rights and obligations. Therefore, normative institutions not only control social conduct through mandates, responsibilities, and obligations, but they also empower and facilitate it through rights, privileges, and licenses.

The primary responsibilities of South Asian women are to maintain the family unit and to provide for their husbands and children (Basu, 1998, 2004; Basu & Altinay, 2003). The attitudes and ideas that are ingrained in South Asian culture on an ethnic and religious level reinforce the legitimacy of patriarchal ideals and conduct. South Asian culture generally accepts and upholds these normative standards and expectations. On the one hand, these norms place restrictions on FEs through the obligations, mandates, and responsibilities placed on female family members. On the other hand, FEs clearly demonstrate a reliance on the male family members for assistance with many entrepreneurial operations, such as handling finances, accounting, or occasionally interacting with suppliers.

The majority of FEs were slowed down in their advancement by embracing such patriarchal cultural standards, which were a major restricting factor. The effect of this did, however, lessen through time and as a result of life experiences, with assistance from the altering and developing (temporal) dynamics of the normative institutions (family, culture,

and societal) themselves. By taking a stand and moving on with their "dreams," some FEs may have even modified the prevailing family and societal standards and made it easier for those who followed in their footsteps.

According to the study, male family members' direct effect was very powerful. The difficulties that FEs encountered were numerous and varied simply because of this issue. A majority of the participants were married, some as young as 17 and some at young ages. Most of the time, women had to accept that their male partners had more power over them; this was the recognized cultural standard within which they had to function. It was also discovered that first generation FEs were more adversely affected by family members. Their entrepreneurial flair was occasionally overridden by the spouse (or in-laws/parents) based on lack of specialized entrepreneurial expertise on their side, which was a severe hindrance to operating their enterprises.

FEs are a part of the group-based dominance hierarchies of their society, which favor adults over children and men over women (patriarchy) (Pratto et al., 2013). This further underlines the potential and limitations for FEs. Due to a number of strongly ingrained, discriminatory socio-cultural attitudes and customs in their society, FEs did not have access to the same possibilities as men, such as freedom of choice in employment and free time to pursue their goals. One of the FEs, for instance, had to shut down her company to care for her sick husband, and in another instance, her brother prevented her from enrolling in the university of her choosing because he did not want her to live away from home.

They are sacrificing their ambitions in one area of their work in order to be able to function in another. Interviewee 1 terminated her first firm, for instance, but when her spouse recovered and she expressed a wish to start a new business, there was less opposition.

Even while their male family members frequently "granted" them the freedom to work or launch a business, there was always a cost, primarily in the form of increased psychological pressures from ongoing guilt. As a result, the study shows that FEs struggle to balance their own goals with the obligations they have to their families under cultural norms. Consequently, there is a continual conflict between these two elements, which is implied and occasionally directly voiced by the participants in this study's interviews. The main challenge for FEs is how to balance their own goals with gender norms and role expectations (what is the right conduct for them to exhibit?). Working under continual emotional stress, people occasionally opted to act responsibly even when doing so would have served their best interests. Similar to facing regulative systems, confronting normative

systems may also cause powerful emotions, although these are distinct from the emotions brought on by breaking rules and regulations (Scott, 2014).

When someone violates standards, they often experience shame or humiliation. However, people who consistently behave admirably may experience sentiments of respect and honor. When standards are followed or broken, there is frequently a significant amount of self-evaluation involved, such as increased regret or repercussions on self-respect. Such feelings offer powerful inducements to follow accepted norms. This is the cause of some FEs ceasing their lucrative businesses in order to fulfil their obligations to their immediate families. FEs regularly dealt with emotional stress when juggling their many duties as an entrepreneur, wife, mother, daughter, and daughter-in-law at home. They were unable to express their dissatisfaction and exhaustion because they were afraid they would be asked to give up their entrepreneurial endeavors in order to focus on their primary responsibilities to the family. Even when women were prosperous in their company, they had to exercise caution since they were seen as undermining the male family members' ability to support the family financially, which had a bad effect on the family's 'izzat' in society.

The research demonstrated that FEs' available time for business was not time of their choosing because of normative restrictions. Their entrepreneurial process was occasionally slowed by cultural perspectives of time, or in some cases altogether stopped for a few years. Their primary duty is to take care of household tasks and obligations since they have no alternative because family comes first in their society. They had less time to develop their business as a result of their acceptance of this scenario. As a result, the time for commercial initiatives is also "GIVEN" or "ALLOWED" because of cultural restrictions within the patriarchal ideals of South Asian and Black Caribbean society. Due to the fact that they had to start and stop several times, some FEs' entrepreneurial experience was sporadic.

6.3.1.2 Key Regulative Factors

This study has demonstrated that all female entrepreneurs in the UK were typically treated equally by the regulatory environment. The study also shown that, in comparison to normative institutions, regulative factors—such as financial institutions and governmental rules and regulations—played a comparatively little influence. In the UK, the regulatory institutions would typically apply to all entrepreneurs equally, but because of cognitive and normative variables, their effects are varied.

According to the research, all of the cases had identical features of taxation, company rules, and labor legislation. Finance, taxation, and company regulations, on the other hand, were often handled by the male household members or outsourced. Banks in particular did not contribute much to the money raised through loans from financial institutions. The firms were mostly self-financed. The male members of the immediate family would arrange minor bank loans when they were needed. Only two entrepreneurs, mostly from the second generation, looked for private investors. This was made possible by their comfort speaking the language in which they pitched their ideas and the ease with which they could acquire information regarding financing on social media. Aside from two instances when gender discrimination was noted, there were no problems while dealing with financial institutions in terms of gender or ethnicity.

Similar to this, the direct involvement of the government did not appear to have any appreciable impact on the entrepreneurial process, either by easing or obstructing it. This was only briefly discussed in a few instances, such as when one of the interviewees who managed a law business (around the time when legal aid was made more difficult to acquire) and a few others brought up HR rules, corporation tax, and BREXIT. In general, everyone praised how simple it was to create the company and open business accounts throughout the initial setup procedure. As was the case with Interviewee 4, other business owners had been impacted by market shifts, their inability to anticipate the cost of doing business, and changes to their supply chain, forcing them to close their doors. Overall, statements on the government's support of the entrepreneurial process received good feedback. The only other thing worth mentioning is that, rather than playing a passively constructive and supporting role, government may be pushed to be more aggressive in terms of reaching out to FEs.

The study also demonstrates that first and second generation FEs differ from one another. Given their upbringing and education in the UK, this study revealed that second-generation FEs were more familiar with procedures and governing bodies. This indicates that they are better equipped to deal with regulatory institutions than first-generation FEs because of their location, experience, expertise, and duration of residence in the UK. Due to the development of explicit and tacit knowledge, second-generation FEs engaged with and responded to regulative (and normative) limits differently. First, second generation FEs tended to be more nomadic and flexible in where they located their enterprises, as opposed to first generation ones, who tended to grow their firms in the community where they were raised. Second, first generation FEs primarily created ethnic firms, but second generation

FEs more frequently entered mainstream industries. Due to their training and experience in the UK, second-generation entrepreneurs were more likely to seek guidance and funding from public, commercial, or private sources, such as acquaintances and professional networks, than from their immediate families. The study therefore demonstrates that while the UK's regulatory institutions were the same for all entrepreneurs, FEs were affected differently as a result of cultural, cognitive, and normative variables.

6.3.2 How do they deal with these challenges?

This section describes how FEs dealt with and surmounted gender norms and social expectations while pursuing their entrepreneurial endeavors. According to the research, FEs are continually negotiating their status within gender- and ethnic-based constraints in their families and, in certain circumstances, throughout their communities. Entrepreneurs affect and shape institutions as well as being influenced by them, according to Henrekson and Sanandaji (2011). This research clearly demonstrates the reciprocal interaction between institutions and entrepreneurs through FEs ongoing quest for agency. They empowered themselves in many ways, such as via education, experience, and professionalism. The study revealed that FEs took advantage of every chance to increase their social, economic, or human capital in order to improve their entrepreneurial experience. Along with other aspects, these opportunities were produced by normative and regulatory institutions. FEs are skilled at spotting them and taking advantage of them.

In the UK, regulatory authorities developed FE-supportive frameworks and assisted them in achieving autonomy via parity in systems and procedures. The regulatory environment also gave them opportunity to develop human capital through free training programs, education, and financial resources. The capacity of women to make decisions and choices, which enables them to decide the course of change and question the status quo, is one of the major elements of agency (Kabeer, 1999). Some of the FEs had taken the deliberate decision to use human capital to transcend racial and geographic divides. In several instances, free training offered by the UK government helped the respondents cope with their normative issues. Environmental limitations were also caused by changes in governmental regulations and environmental conditions, such as BREXIT, although in the majority of situations, FEs were able to survive by altering their business strategy or changing their business model entirely.

The major role that temporal considerations had in the FE's entrepreneurial process, particularly in terms of their ongoing gender negotiations, is one of the key findings in connection to them. They found it easier to negotiate their situation and challenge the

gender/role constraints imposed by normative institutions by using chronological time and occurrences. Age, business experience, and life milestones like marriage or the birth of new children, for instance, all significantly contribute to enabling FEs to defy conventional restrictions.

Both first- and second-generation FEs make a conscious effort to further their education, obtain work experience, and learn new skills. This shifts them from being powerless or compliant to acquiring some measure of control and the ability to question social norms. In a highly patriarchal South Asian and Black Caribbean society, there is therefore a persistent effort to expand their human capital. Some of this agency developed over time as a result of puberty, changing family roles, and seniority.

This is related to FE's capacity to surmount obstacles in the establishment and expansion of their enterprises. The study demonstrated that, although having some empowerment, second-generation FEs are still engaging in gender negotiations with the British educational system while dealing with their parents' instilled "cultural baggage." Each culture—ethnic and host—imposes the force of its cultural distinctiveness on entrepreneurship. For instance, an individualistic host culture stands in contrast to an ethnic culture that is more collectivistic.

The interviewers' personal traits were another relevant consideration. Their business venture was aided in its beginning by their strong, independent, and optimistic personalities—personalities that were first supported by their family. This same persistence, in certain cases, also seemed to drive through their ideas by swiftly overcoming any social inhibitions and structural impediments, which aided them at various phases of their entrepreneurial process.

Additionally, their faith, particularly their trust in Tawakkul, enabled them to overcome some institutional obstacles. Tawakkul is the act of giving one's all while trusting in Allah to bring about the desired result. However, one of the requirements for this is that the individual makes every effort to attain goals before having Tawakkul. This requires activity in order to accomplish the aim. This study demonstrates the impact of Tawakkul on FEs, which was seen in their increased strength and confidence in the face of challenges. According to Ahmad (2011), optimism and self-assurance are two entrepreneurial traits that may come from Tawakkul. These traits may be explained by their high appetite for risk and tenacity, which enabled them to go over institutional obstacles and take advantage of opportunities.

6.3.3 Practical Recommendations to further bolster performance of Female Entrepreneurs of ethnic minorities in the United Kingdom

FEs run against a number of societal barriers early on in their journeys as they try to realize their goals and reach their potential. To start their businesses, they must face a number of obstacles, including start-up challenges, financial obstacles, obstacles connected to the market and skills, obstacles resulting from their personal attitudes and worries towards making decisions to become entrepreneurs, and more.

The conclusions drawn from this study have shown how many of the problems can be resolved in the right setting with assistance from society, particularly their own families, and the government. As a result, the government should launch additional new initiatives and schemes to aid women entrepreneurs in further overcoming these barriers. Diverse measures should be implemented with multi-year strategies to support a FE's endeavor from its inception to its departure, where women gain additional perks, discounts, or help.

Additionally, as literacy rates rise and higher education becomes more accessible, society's perception of women engaging in entrepreneurship is shifting. In the ever-changing environment, the government should not only widely publicize the numerous efforts for women entrepreneurs but also establish up centers specifically designed to support them. Additionally, a single point of contact for women business owners staffed with knowledgeable and experienced people might assist the women business owners in managing the onerous government processes, handling tax-related difficulties, and completing legal formalities. By providing them with the skills and knowledge necessary to establish a successful firm, designing training programs and workshops that are more pertinent to the current situation and programmers that address the needs of women entrepreneurs at different stages of the firm's life cycle would greatly benefit them.

6.3.4 Summary

I've been successful in putting the institutional restrictions that FEs encounter their entrepreneurial experience in context. This study succeeds in addressing the research issues and achieving the research goals.

In conclusion, male dominance in South Asian culture is one of the primary causes, which has an influence on FEs' entrepreneurial process both positively (by generating chances) and negatively (by establishing limits). The study, however, found that for the respondents, this resulted in more limitations/barriers than possibilities. One of the main normative obstacles was the fact that the FEs were given the freedom and time to grow their businesses in the

South Asian society, which has extremely strong patriarchal beliefs. For these FEs, this border is especially important since it had the most impact on their entrepreneurial career. The FEs had to deal with a heavier emotional load as a result of this normative barrier. They managed a variety of obligations relating to both gender and business throughout their entrepreneurial process without complaining. This was the cost they had to pay in exchange for being given the time and flexibility to operate their own business.

However, the degree to which these circumstances affected these FEs' agency and power changed throughout time. The conflict between FEs' contrary temporal perspectives—which are more future-oriented—and typical South Asian cultural values—which are past-oriented—kept FEs motivated to continue working toward a better future. Second, people obtained agency as a result of temporal occurrences like experience, education or training, knowledge, age, and marriage, which allowed them to persuade institutions to act in their favor.

This empirical study summarizes that FEs continually gender negotiate within the parameters that have been set up for them based on gender. They also work hard to shift to female autonomy over time, which helps them on their business path.

6.4 Value of the Research Study

The theoretical addition this study makes to the body of knowledge and body of research on ethnic entrepreneurship, with an emphasis on FEs in the UK, is what gives it value. This will help us comprehend this ethnic group better and how macro-contextual variables affect entrepreneurship. The conceptual framework created by this study may be used to the comparison of the entrepreneurial experiences of various ethnic female groups. This study also raises awareness of the challenges and ongoing struggles that FEs encounter when building their businesses. However, given how heavily this society is dominated by men, the knowledge learned might be used to South Asian professional women who are focused on their careers.

Through the study technique and design, I was able to gain a higher degree of trust, allowing me to gather a wealth of insightful information on FEs' entrepreneurial experiences. Even though I belonged to this culture, I wasn't seen as a part of the South Asian population that lives in large cities because I only arrived in this nation in 2018 to further my education. For this reason, I had to build a relationship with this group by frequent engagement by participating in community events and joining community groups, which gave the research a quasi-ethnographic feel.

This was a time-consuming but effective way to meet and attract people from a community that, for a variety of reasons, had a negative view of outsiders. Participants might not have been as willing to divulge private information about their families for study purposes if this had not been done. Additionally, the study used a variety of methods to find participants. Community welfare, social, religious, and charitable groups were some of these sources. Since the bulk of these groups were exclusively for women, it was simpler for me (being female) to participate in them. As described in Chapter 3, I have engaged not only with the participant but also with the data I gathered at various phases of organization and interpretation. As a "cultural insider," I had some prior knowledge of the South Asian and Black Caribbean cultures under inquiry (I have numerous friends from the Caribbean), which gave me the chance to apply my expertise to provide the study with in-depth analysis and interpretations. As a result, this study design may add to the body of knowledge on how to do qualitative research on females, particularly those from ethnic groups where there is a lack of confidence in outsiders.

Applying the right institutional incentives is essential for supporting businesses in a more direct and efficient way. According to Duflo (2012), the relative status of women in society and the degree of economic growth are strongly positively correlated across nations and time. Therefore, empowering women would not only be a noble objective in and of itself, but may also be used as a weapon to hasten economic progress. It is particularly pertinent since many governments are actively attempting to boost entrepreneurial activity and because entrepreneurship plays a vital influence in a country's economic well-being. This study emphasizes the value of empowering women through the previously described proper government policies, particularly in ethnic minorities where patriarchal norms are still prevalent. The study demonstrates that the UK government's policies are appropriate for delivering training and education, but more accessibility and clarity are required.

My research's practical consequences include giving policymakers important information that will help them better understand female entrepreneurship and the critical elements that contribute to its success. This information might help in the future in developing stronger social, cultural, and economic policies to empower women.

6.5 Limitations and Reflection

It is common knowledge that comprehensive geographic coverage and the quantity of respondents in each location are crucial requirements for research. This research has limitations in this regard. The study concentrated on business owners in the cities of London,

Birmingham, Bradford, and Cardiff since it is thought that the ethnic group under study is heavily represented in these locations. I had to choose respondents who were business owners because of the nature of the research topic and aims.

Access to the study's concerned respondents was a significant barrier. Due to the restricted availability of data, alternative sources of data collecting (councils, APWA, and BPF) had to be utilized. Finding and enlisting the individuals required a lot of time. The Data Protection Act, which limited particular access to female South Asian and Black Caribbean enterprises and fostered mistrust of this group, was a related barrier. In the end, the most important resources for locating and contacting social, religious, welfare, and organizations are social networks. Consequently, the respondents were located using a variety of means.

The sample size has always been a problem in qualitative social science research. But in this study, the guiding idea of saturation has been used to preserve the research's rigor. In this investigation, 15 participants were enough to reach this saturation limit (Creswell, 2009).

The epistemological/ontological approach of social constructionism was the methodology selected for the study. Thematic approach provided the basis for the data analysis technique. This approach's drawback was that I am a member of the study's ethnic/cultural group. However, by being aware of this fact, this insider prejudice was reduced. Additionally, by having intimate knowledge of cultural, ethnic, national, religious, and linguistic factors, the research group may be better understood, allowing for a deeper examination of the environment for female entrepreneurs. One major benefit of being an insider was the amount of trust that was developed with the respondents, which led to considerably more candor and depth in the comments during the interviews, yielding fresh perspectives. Few conventional researchers could have facilitated access to and clarification of respondents' opinions in the manner I have. Although a researcher's membership in the community might lead to certain bias concerns or overly close relationships with respondents, it is the only method to have access to knowledgeable, eloquent members of the FE community. Additionally, I assert that my level of social proximity during interviews "inside one's own "cultural" group" (Ganga and Scott, 2006) really contributes to creating a knowledge of the social environment in which the respondents related their tales.

Coding techniques had to be established for manual coding, interviews (data sets), selecting the data items that displayed patterns (themes), assessing the original themes, and improving them. Finally, a thematic map based on institutional normative/regulative

principles was created as a result of this. It took a long time to gather, store, and analyze the data in this three-stage process. Many of the interviewees, it may be said, would transition from English to their native tongues during the interview. Another thing to note is that the temporal aspects were discussed (indirectly) throughout the interview process and how they affected the entrepreneurs' decision-making. This was not specifically explored, though, so there may be need for more research in this area.

Finally, it is important to note that the range and scale of the enterprises that were examined are limited. Future research might include extending the study of both of these topics and going beyond the three present geographic regions.

The entire process of conducting this research was quite intriguing. I discovered a lot about the aspirations and realities of South Asian and Black Caribbean female entrepreneurs in the UK. Even though I am a South Asian female entrepreneur and have experienced similar things, the participants—who came from a variety of family backgrounds and came from various places—taught me a lot about the various facets of South Asian culture and society. In many respects, it helped me gain perspective on my personal path by bringing to light ideas I had never considered. For instance, my husband and I both supported gender equality, but after reading this research, I began to wonder whether my independence would have been "allowed" to me if my spouse had not?

In addition to bringing socially constructed notions about gender and entrepreneurship sharply into focus, this dissertation emphasizes the complexity and ongoing growth of entrepreneurial literature. Ultimately, there is a lot of room for more investigation given the options, perspectives, and notably the problems revealed.

6.6 Suggestions for further Research

It would be insightful to use comparison studies to examine the generalizability of the research's findings. FEs in the UK, for instance, can be compared to other female business owners from ethnic minorities in terms of their experiences. By comparing the UK FEs to other FE groups in other Western nations, more comparative study is also necessary to elucidate structural and contextual implications on findings analysis. A national comparison may be made as a result of the investigation of various host cultures, which would enrich this qualitative study even more. Additionally, there is room to expand on this research by examining several angles, such as a comparison of FEs in this country and Pakistan.

This research demonstrated that because of a variety of strongly ingrained discriminatory socio-cultural attitudes and practices in their community, FEs did not have access to the same possibilities as men, such as freedom of choice in employment and free time to achieve their goals. The research did not reveal if this condition is prevalent in all cultures where men predominate or whether it simply occurs in groups or countries where a certain religion predominates, but this might be investigated in the future.

To gain a complete picture, male members may be researched. Their opinions on how men behave, peer pressure, do they have same barriers like FE's have to face, or may be new male entrepreneurs compares to old ME's, etc. A comparison of FEs in urban and rural Britain can be investigated for this purpose. This should demonstrate whether the difficulties faced by South Asian and Black Caribbean women identified in this research are widespread in the UK or whether they differ depending on the size of the South Asian or Black Caribbean Diasporas in various regions of the UK, particularly the manner in which male behavior toward the FEs in these two distinct diaspora situations.

The study's developing themes might benefit from quantitative research on some of them. Examples include empirical studies of the ongoing gender negotiations that FEs must make. This might assist in developing frameworks and policies to assist FEs who are unaware of their rights in Britain.

The deductive nature of this research endeavor may ultimately aid in the creation of a UK company directory owned by South Asian and Black Caribbean female entrepreneurs. As I previously indicated, it was difficult for me to locate companies operated by South Asian and Black Caribbean women. It would also be beneficial to broaden the surveys' geographic scope to cover many more regions inside the UK. Because Pakistan is a large nation with many cultures and languages in each of its areas, as well as because India is a larger country than Pakistan and has more diverse cultures and languages throughout its territory, South Asian and Black Caribbean cultures are not monolithic. Thus, there is a need to explore the variation of impact of normative and regulative institutions on FEs from different regions through a quantitative study done at a larger scale.

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Appendices

Appendix 1:

Interview Guide

My Name is Nida-E-Sehar, I am doing DBA from University of West of Scotland. I am conducting this interview because I am doing a research under University of West of Scotland. The title of my research is Challenges and Barriers faced by Ethnic Minority Female Entrepreneurs (South Asian and African – Caribbean) in the Small Businesses in London. My project is about (SOUTH ASIAN) Pakistani, Indians, Bangladeshis and African Caribbean women running their businesses in the UK, I would like to discuss about your experiences of running a business in the UK. The purpose of the study is to compare the difficulties and issues faced by women of different ethnicities while working in the UK.

Questions

1. Demographics

- a) What is your ethnic background?
- b) Did you born here or migrated from your country of origin? If yes when did you migrated to the UK? (Migration Date)
- c) If migrated what was the reason for the migration?

2. Experience of a New Place

- a) How was your experience and feelings of a new environment in the UK?
- b) Why did you decided to settle in the UK?

3. Background of the Business

- a) When did you start this business? (Date)
- b) What was the reason of starting this business? Is this a family business or you have decided to step in to this business on your own or were you influenced by someone?
- c) Did you start this business in order to support your family financially or this was just your passion or you were trying to be independent?
- d) While starting the business what was your feelings as being from different ethnic background, were you scared that you will have difficulties in setting up the business or you were confident that you will do it comfortably?

4. About your Business

- a) Is this your first and only business if not than what are your other businesses, are they running or closed?
- b) If you have closed or change a business what was the reason to do so?
- c) Is this business running smoothly or do you have any difficulties in running your business?
- d) What are the most common problems you face day to day in this business?
- e) Are you the soul owner of this business or do you have any partner or staff who is contributing financially in this business?
- f) Do you have employees to help you in this business?
- g) What was the difficulties and issues you had in the beginning of this business?
- h) How did you cope and overcome those problems?
- i) What about your surrounding businesses are they helpful at the start time or you had to deal with the problems as well?
- j) How do you feel now after being in this business from quite a while?
- k) How do you cope with the competition? Is there healthy competition which helps you to improve your business?

5. Personal Network

- a) Are you supporting your family financially through this business?
- b) How many family members do you have? Are they supportive? (Morally, financially, physically)
- c) Do they help you in this business?
- d) Do you take ideas and help from your family members in order to expand or run your business smoothly?
- e) Did you faced any problems whilst starting the business from your family?
- f) Do you have any problems now running this business from your family?
- g) Do you have someone to look after your business when you are not around?
- h) Is it easy to manage work and home together, how do you manage your work and family life?

6. Social Circle

- a) Do you have friends?
- b) Are they from the same ethnic background or from different ethnicities?
- c) Do they support you in your business? (Morally, financially, physically)
- d) Who is more supportive friends from your ethnic background or others?
- e) Do you face any difficulties from your friend's side?
- f) Does your friends also own some businesses, do you have competition with them?
- g) Do you take ideas and help from your friends in order to expand or run your business smoothly?

7. About Customers

- a) How do you welcome your customers?
- b) Do you have regular customers if yes how often they contact or visits you?

- c) What are the common group of people who visits you, are they from same ethnic background or different backgrounds?
- d) What difficulties or issues you encounters normally from customers?

8. About Suppliers

- a) Who supply you goods?
- b) Do you use different suppliers or you have regular suppliers?
- c) Are you using this supplier from the beginning or did you change your suppliers?
- d) If yes why did you change the supplier?
- e) Is your supplier from the same ethnic background or some other?
- f) What are the problems you normally faced from your supplier?
- g) Do you think if you are from any other ethnicity you will face all those problems?
- h) How often you order goods (frequency of purchase)
- i) How do you contact your supplier?
- j) How many days does it take from ordering to receiving the items?
- k) Do you import some goods from your homeland?
- l) If yes is it easy to import items from your country of origin to the UK?
- m) Do you pay huge amount of tax on imports?
- n) Do you face any difficulties in importing goods?
- o) Is there any financial support available from the authorities? (Government or charity)

Appendix 2:

Consent Form

I _____, understand the procedure of this research and I am happy and willing to take part in this research regarding the Challenges and Barriers faced by Ethnic Minority Female Entrepreneurs (South Asian and Black – Caribbean) in the Small Businesses in the United Kingdom.

I understand that my participation in this research is voluntary and I am able to withdraw at any time and I don't have to provide any reason for the withdrawal.

I understand that the researcher will record my interview and later it will be written word by word. I do understand that whatever information I will provide in this interview will be confidential and only to be used for the purpose of this research. I am aware that the recording will be securely stored in accordance to the Data Protection Act and GDPR.

Participant's Name:

Date:

Signature:

Researcher's Name:

Date:

Signature:

